

Captain Thomas Brown (1785–1862): his life and molluscan taxa

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Abstract. A biography is provided for Captain Thomas Brown, who lived in Scotland and England, and is known to have visited Ireland and France. He chiefly made his living as a writer and publisher of popular natural history books, and eventually as a curator of the Manchester Museum. In malacology, he is most noted for two editions of a book on the Recent molluscs of the British Isles, one edition of a book on its fossil fauna, and a major paper on Carboniferous molluscs. Sadly, most of the types of his Recent species have been lost. Brown introduced 43 genera and 440 species, including unavailable names published in synonymies. Some genera are still in use. The species include 46% gastropods, 43% bivalves, 9% cephalopods, and 2% other classes. The species are 45% Recent, 23% Carboniferous, 10% Quaternary, 7% Jurassic, and 15% other epochs. We additionally list 13 taxa that have been misattributed to him. About a quarter of his taxa lack modern placements.

Here we designate *Sipho striata* T. Brown, 1827, to be the type species of *Sipho* T. Brown, 1827, affirming its place as a junior synonym of *Puncturella* R.T. Lowe, 1827. We designate *Turbo graphicus* T. Brown, 1818, as the type species of *Pyramis* T. Brown, 1827 [*non* Röding, 1798, *nec* Schumacher, 1817], ensuring its position as a junior synonym of *Cingula* J. Fleming, 1818. We designate *Brochus striatus* T. Brown, 1827, as the type species of *Brochus* T. Brown, 1827, ensuring its place as a synonym of *Caecum* J. Fleming, 1813. We designate *Planaria alba* T. Brown, 1827, as type species of *Planaria* T. Brown, 1827 [*non* *Planaria* O.F. Müller, 1776], fixing its position in the synonymy of *Gyraulus* Charpentier, 1837. We designate *Cochlea virgata* da Costa, 1778, as the type species of *Heliomanes* T. Brown, 1844 [*non* Newman, 1840], ensuring its placement as a synonym of *Cernuella* Schlüter, 1838. *Naticopsis mazaevi* Coan & Goodwin, 2026, is proposed as a replacement name for the Upper Permian *Natica minima* T. Brown, 1841, *non* I. Lea, 1833. *Volutopsius golikovi* Coan & Goodwin, 2026, is proposed as a replacement name for the Recent northwestern Pacific *Fusus castaneus* Mörch, 1848, *non* T. Brown, 1827.

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INTRODUCTION

Captain Thomas Brown is probably one of the least-known personalities of the conchological world of the first half of the 19th century, and certainly in the U.K. Although he got a passing mention in Melvill (1890: 215), it was not until early in the next century that Nicholson (1913: 4–5) gave a short description of the man and his time as curator of the Manchester Museum. Writing of his published works in a paper on workers in ornithology, Mathews & Iredale (1922: 176) commented that “the methods of publication of his conchological writings proved so complex that even the indefatigable Sherborn, who probed into the matter, was compelled to confess that finality had not been achieved in his results”. And it was not just his published works. Sherborn (1905: 360) went further, suggesting “Captain Brown’s

history is so imperfectly known that it would be difficult to string together any running story”.

Indeed, no portrait seems to exist. Figure 1 is a letter showing his signature. The addressee is a “Dr. Fleming”, who has been identified as Dr William Fleming, magistrate, antiquary and shell collector from Pendleton, near Manchester.

Further short notes about his molluscan works were given by Reynell (1921), Kennard & Woodward (1928), Sherborn (1939), Salisbury (1945: 150–151), and Ellis (1982). The biographical black hole was partially filled by John Wilfrid Jackson (b. 1880 – d. 1978), who followed Brown as a curator at Manchester Museum, but while Jackson (1944) dealt comprehensively with Brown’s publications, he included relatively few details about Brown’s life and since then, little else has come to light. It now seems

Figure 1. A letter to Dr William Fleming, showing Brown's handwriting and signature. (J. Wilfrid Jackson Archive—originally in Buxton Museum & Art Gallery, now at Derbyshire Records Office, Matlock.)

appropriate to draw together the few sources of information about the life and work of Brown and to provide a list of the molluscan taxa he described.

BROWN'S LIFE

Thomas Brown was born on April 8, 1785, in Perth, Scotland, and was baptised two days later. His parents were John Brown, a printer, and Jean Auchterlonie. John and Jean had married on May 12, 1784, so Thomas would probably have been their first child.

Little is known of Thomas Brown's early life except that he was educated at Edinburgh High School (Anonymous 1863). He grew up in a Great Britain at war with Napoleonic France, and in 1805 aged 20, after starting a career as an engraver with Scott's of Edinburgh, he enlisted in the Forfar & Kincardine Militia as an ensign. This regiment was on "home defence" duties during this period of instability. At that time, there were no standing police forces, and maintenance of law and order was carried out by such militias. Initially, with 918 men in 10 companies under Lt.-Colonel Robert W. Duff, his militia brigade was based at Musselburgh, but then moved to Glasgow Barracks in 1806, the

first of a series of deployments in Scotland. When the north of England was troubled by Luddite attacks, the regiment was moved south to Newcastle upon Tyne and then to Tynemouth in June 1811.

He was first married during this period to Agnes, whose maiden name is unknown (b. 1791 – d. 1850). They had four daughters, Emily Neilson (b. 1810 – d. 1855), who was born in Newcastle, Elizabeth Ramsay (b. 1813 – d. 1836), Josephine (b. 1816 – d.?), and Jane Douglas (b. 1820 – d. 1843).

In November 1812, the regiment was on the move again, first to Stockport and subsequently across to Manchester on January 27, 1813, by which time Thomas had been promoted to Captain, a rank he highlighted for the rest of his life. It was while quartered with his troops in this city that he began to pursue his childhood interest in natural history. When the militia left Manchester on March 28, 1814, it sailed to Ireland, where it was quartered at Clonoony and then Naas Barracks, and Captain Thomas Brown took advantage of his spare time to "assiduously" collect molluscs (McMillan 1970: 198), and he sent a report on his collections to the Wernerian Society mentioned at a meeting in December 1814.

The war in mainland Europe ended with the abdication of Napoleon in April 1814, and Brown's regiment remained

in Ireland awaiting “disembodiment”. However, Napoleon escaped from Elba early in 1815, initiating the Hundred Days Campaign, and disembodiment was delayed, with units continuing in service after the Battle of Waterloo. The Forfar & Kincardine Militia remained at Naas until September 12, 1815, when it moved to Downpatrick. It finally left on March 2, 1816, and returned to Scotland to be disembodied. Brown used his discharge pay to buy a flax mill in Fife, Scotland, which unfortunately soon burned down, the loss uninsured.

The first volume of his edition of *Goldsmith's History of the Earth* (Brown 1814–1819) had already been produced and he decided to support his family by becoming a naturalist-publisher. His first malacological book was *The Elements of Conchology* (Brown 1816) (Fig. 2), both publications begun while he was still in the militia. It did not take long for him to become well enough known in natural history circles to be elected a Fellow of the Royal Society of Edinburgh on January 26, 1818, at the age of 32.

In 1819, the Edinburgh University Senate sent him to Paris to acquire the large collection of Louis Dufresne (b. 1752 – d. 1832), chief of the preserving department at the Jardin des Plantes. As well as securing that collection, which included molluscs, he also learned a variety of preservation techniques from Dufresne. Hoping to apply his new skills, Brown himself reported (Brown, 1833, *Taxidermist's Manual*: vi) that “I was, however, prevented from being of that service to my country which I could have wished, owing to some unaccountable jealousy of the Professor of Natural History; although I was offered by the Senatus Academicus the situation of Keeper of the Museum.” Brown did not become Keeper and that offer seems to have been vetoed by Professor Robert Jameson (b. 1774 – d. 1854), a mineralogist whose courses covered both zoology and geology and whose lectures are said to have bored Charles Darwin. Jameson had built the museum up as his own personal fiefdom.

About this time, Brown collaborated with William Elford Leach on an article on Conchology for the 6th edition of the *Encyclopaedia Britannica* (Leach & Brown 1823), the plates drawn by Brown.

In 1838, the Manchester Museum, then on Peter Street (Fig. 3), sought a curator after William Crawford Williamson (b. 1816 – d. 1895) resigned. Thomas applied and was appointed. Jackson (1944) noted that eight other applicants were rejected because “the parties appearing to be wholly unacquainted with natural history”. Brown was to serve the Museum as Curator for the next 24 years. Eagar (1977: 13) recorded that he “appears to have worked exceptionally hard on behalf of the museum, especially” at a time “when there was little money and no extra staff”.

Figure 2. Title page of Brown's first malacological book was *The Elements of Conchology* (1816). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/15963654>.)

After his first wife Agnes died in 1850, Thomas remarried, on February 5, 1853, to Mary Kenderdine (née Critchley). Mary (b. ca.1793 – d.1875) had also been married before, in May 1818 to Lieutenant Richard Kenderdine (b. 1792 – d. 1834), and there had been four children from her first marriage.

Jackson (1944) noted that Brown and his wife Mary became members of the Manchester Field Naturalists' Society “on its inauguration in 1860, and he was rarely absent from the soirees”.

Figure 3. The Manchester Natural History Museum on Peter Street (centre), with the Theatre Royale on the right. (Image courtesy of Manchester Libraries, reproduced under <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/> .

Figure 4. Title page of Brown's *Illustrations of the Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland* (1827). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/41107039>.)

By 1861, he and one daughter by his first marriage, Emily, together with two servants, were living at 95 Plymouth Grove, Chorlton upon Medlock, Manchester. Apparently,

none of Brown's daughters married, so he did not leave any "genetic legacy" through direct descendants. Brown's death occurred on October 8, 1862, at Chorlton-on-Medlock, and he was interred in the Dissenters' Cemetery on Rusholme Road (Anonymous 1863). His first wife Agnes and two of their daughters, Emily and Jane, were also buried there. Unfortunately, no headstones survived after the graveyard was converted in 1955 into a public park, Gartside Gardens, their bodies probably remaining undisturbed under it. A copy of *The Illustrations of Fossil Conchology* (1849) in the Manchester Museum is inscribed: "Presented to the Natural History Society by Emily N. Brown as a small mark of her appreciation of the kindness of the Members of the Council of that Institution and other friends, on the occasion of her father's decease, 1862" (Jackson, 1944: 19). He died a respected member of the Manchester scientific community, described (Anonymous 1863) as "venerable and kind-hearted" and an "able curator".

After her husband's death, Mary went to live with her son Frederic Kenderdine and his family at Morningside, Old Trafford. She died there on April 17, 1875, leaving an estate valued at less than £3,000.

MALACOLOGICAL PUBLICATIONS

Thomas Brown completed several important malacological works—the *Illustrations of the Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland* (1827) (Figs 4, 5), *The Conchologist's Text-Book* (1833) (Fig. 6), the *Illustrations of the Fossil Conchology of Britain and Ireland* (1837–1849) (Figs 7, 8), the *Illustrations of the Recent Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland, ...*, 2nd ed. (1838–1844) (Figs 9, 10), and a substantial paper on Carboniferous molluscs (1841b), as well as many smaller papers.

OTHER MALACOLOGICAL CONTRIBUTIONS

In addition to his several books and papers on molluscs, Brown was noted for two other malacological developments. While the dredge had first been invented by the Danish naturalist Otto Frederik Müller (b. 1730 – d. 1784), Brown is credited with promoting it for shell collecting and he gave a detailed description of its construction and usage in *The Taxidermist's Manual* (1833: 107–110, figs 1, 2). Brown's dredge "was essentially an iron bar formed into a triangle with a lower edge adapted for cutting into the sea bed; a net was attached for the reception of detached organisms and the whole contraption was secured to a rope

Figure 5. Part of plate 33 of Brown's *Illustrations of the Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland* (1827). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/41107125>.)

and dragged along behind a boat”, signalling “a new era in collecting techniques, this implement subsequently playing a major part in the discovery of many molluscs new to science” (Dance 1986: 95). Brown also invented a special freshwater version for “the large Swan-Muscle (*Anodonta cygnea*), and other Anadons” lying deep in the mud (p.105, pl. 5, fig. 5) (Fig. 11).

Brown also gave a detailed methodology for cleaning and storing shells, and in particular a recommendation that washed and dried shells should be oiled. Brown (1816: 136–137) wrote: “This practice of oiling shells is a new one, and I believe I was the first who thought of it and have communicated it to all my friends who collect shells; and it has been generally approved. Indeed, one friend who had a very large collection, was so pleased with the effect it produced, that he washed off the gum from all his shells and oiled them.” The oil he recommended was called “Florence

oil”, which we assume would have been olive oil. At the time, a common practice was instead to cover shells with a solution of gum arabic, a tree sap, which Brown noted that “they all shine with great lustre, even although many of the shells should themselves be dim in a natural state”. Now, neither practice is recommended for scientific collections.

PURPORTED PLAGIARISM

Brown found himself on both sides of plagiarism allegations. The best-known example concerns the famous author Edgar Allan Poe (b. 1809 – d. 1849), who certainly borrowed from Brown in a foray into conchology. Keen (1936), Matheson (1945), Johnson (1974), and Dance (1986: 143–144) gave accounts of Poe's *The Conchologist's First Book* (1839), and later Dance (2005: 102–105) noted that much of it had been lifted from Brown's *The Conchologist's*

Figure 6. Title page of Brown's *The Conchologist's Text-Book* (1833). (Modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/12173349>).

Text-Book (1833). Poe was induced to undertake the project by Thomas Wyatt (b. 1797 – d. 1873), who found that his own expensive shell book was not selling well and wanted to commission a cheaper version, with a surrogate author, that was sufficiently different from the first to avoid copyright infringement. Dance concluded that “The truth of the matter largely exonerates Poe, who seems to have been shamefully used by Wyatt.” Gould (1993) largely concurred with Dance that Wyatt came out of the affair with the least credit. Poe, “perennially broke and often drunk”, accepted \$50 for “fronting and helping in the preparation”. Gould quoted Poe’s claim that he wrote the “Preface and Introduction and translated from Cuvier the accounts of the animals”. Of these, Gould credited Poe with the translations and that he

Figure 7. Title page of Brown's *Illustrations of the Fossil Conchology of Britain and Ireland* (1837–1849). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/57606422>).

may well have done the Preface, but he found that about a quarter of the introductory text was lifted from Brown. Perhaps the most amazing fact about the whole affair was that, according to Gould, *The Conchologist's First Book* was the only book by Poe that was successful enough to have been published during his lifetime!

Brown was also cast as a perpetrator of plagiarism in relation to some of his ornithological works. In 1833, the Lizars firm published the first volume in what turned out to be a popular series of natural history part works called *The Naturalist's Library*. Allen (2010: 198) observed that “this predictably attracted an imitator”, namely Lauder & Brown’s *The Miscellany of Natural History, vol. 1. Parrots* (T. Brown 1833–1834), the first number of which appeared only a few months after the other series had started (Fig. 12). Since the *Naturalist's Library* did not publish their volume (no. 10) on parrots until 1866, after Brown had died, this imitation was just about the structure and style of the two works. However, Lauder and Brown’s textual “piracy” was also laid bare

Figure 8. Part of Plate 5 from Brown's *Illustrations of the Fossil Conchology of Britain and Ireland* (1837–1849). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/57606651>.)

in a scathing review of the Parrot volume in *The Athenaeum* (Anonymous 1833). This led off with “The volume is creditable to the binder, discreditable to the editors, and useless to the public”. Briefly asserting that the design was “stolen”; the plates “coarse and inaccurate”; the style “mean”; and original reflections “ridiculous”, they went into great detail

to demonstrate that “the great mass of the matter is unacknowledged plagiarism” and was derived from the “Supplement on Scansores from Griffith's Cuvier”.

Writing much later, Alfred Newton, in his monumental *Dictionary of Birds* (1896: 30–31, footnote 3), made similar comments about other Brown ornithological works:

Figure 9. Title page from Brown's *Illustrations of the Recent Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland, ...*, 2nd ed. (1838–1844). (Image from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/10921172>).

Capt. Thomas Browne's [sic] *Illustration of the Genera of Birds*, begun in 1845 in imitation of Gray's work [*The Genera of Birds*], is discreditable to all concerned with it. It soon ceased to appear and remains incomplete. Had it been finished it would have been useless. The author had before (1831) attempted a similar act of piracy upon Wilson's *American Ornithology*.

NATURAL HISTORY PUBLICATIONS

Dance (1986: 94) described Captain Thomas Brown as "a voluminous writer and jack-of-all-trades in natural history". Certainly, no one could dispute the first part of the statement—his first edition of *Goldsmith's History of the Earth* was 2,288 pages, the second 2,314 pages, *The Zoologist's*

Text-Book has 578 pages, and *The Complete Modern Farrier* tops out at 732 pages. Appendix A lists Brown's non-malacological books. Some of these natural history books had short chapters on molluscs, but of no taxonomic significance. Not covered in our paper are his many journal articles and contributed book chapters on birds, fish, and other non-malacological subjects.

As regards the breadth of his natural history knowledge, it extended across the animal kingdom, but he never published anything on plants. Conchology and domestic animals were his strongest areas. Allen (2010: 198) observed "Undeniably he had a wide knowledge of the subject dating from boyhood, with land and freshwater Mollusca as his primary concern". Nicholson (1913) described him, slightly less grudgingly, as "a good all-round naturalist for those days, with a specialist's knowledge of conchology, fossil and Recent". What is evident is that many of his publications, and not just the conchological ones, were popular and commercially successful. His *Taxidermist Manual* went through as many as 29 reprintings, and *The Complete Modern Farrier* merited at least 32, the final one as late as 1904, more than 40 years after his death. There was a popular work on butterflies and moths, and *A Dictionary of the Scottish Language* (1845), and Nicholson (1913) judged that he edited one of the better editions (1833) of Benjamin White's *The Natural History of Selborne*, the original of which had first appeared in 1789.

Ornithology was clearly not one of Brown's strengths and his incursions in this area were all unsuccessful. The first, the ill-fated *The Miscellany of Natural History (Parrots)* in 1833 has already been considered above. It was followed by *Illustrations of the Game Birds of North America* (1834), which as Faxon (1919) pointed out, was "nothing but sixteen plates ..., issued with a different title-page" from his larger work titled *Illustrations of the American Ornithology of Alexander Wilson and Charles Lucien Bonaparte* (1835). All three works were commercial failures and ended with a single printing, ironically making them extremely valuable today because of their relative rarity.

RELIGIOUS VIEWS AND MESMERISM

Brown took his religious faith seriously. When living in Manchester, he is believed to have been associated with The Scotch Church, St. Peter's Square, and he frequently incorporated expressions of faith into his books. Brown was unequivocal in his view of Man as the pinnacle of Creation. In *The Conchologist's Textbook*, we read "As the Almighty has formed nothing in vain, these creatures, so low in the scale

Figure 10. Part of plate 4 from Brown's *Illustrations of the Recent Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland . . .*, 2nd ed. (1838–1844). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/10921190>.)

of being, must have particular uses allotted them in the plan of creation". He was happy to accept the Scriptures as fact, for example quoting them as clearing up the issue of "when horses were introduced into Egypt" (Brown 1830: 21).

Like many others of the time, it seems that for Brown, blind faith trumped scientific curiosity. For example, one did not need to understand the how and the why of bird migration, it was sufficient to know that the stork and the swallow (Jeremiah 8: 7) are "aware of their appointed times", and

"the times of their coming." Barber (1980: 25) was particularly scathing about the elevation of faith over reason, noting that all Brown has to say about insect metamorphosis is "He finds it odd; he cannot explain it; he presumes that God knows what He is doing."

A fellow Protestant and member of the Scotch Church was the Surgeon James Braid (b. 1795 – d. 1860), who Brown probably met originally in meetings of the Wernerian Society in Edinburgh, and like Brown subsequently

Figure 11. Brown's freshwater-mussel dredge from *The Taxidermist's Manual* (1840, 5th edition: pl. 5 fig. 5). (Image modified from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/22493214>.)

moved to Manchester. Braid was an innovative orthopaedic specialist but was best known in the medical world for his theory and practice of hypnotism—then called mesmerism. Brown espoused Dr Braid's methods and gave lectures not only supporting his discoveries but also giving practical demonstrations (Fig. 13).

NETWORKING—FRIENDS, COLLEAGUES, AND FINANCIERS

Like many others of the Victorian era, Brown seemed to relish networking with influential and wealthy people. While the latter may have been a means of securing financial support for his publications in the form of subscriptions, not everything was about self-interest, and in 1843 he was involved in the establishment of the Manchester Scientific Fund Society, a public society with the “immediate purpose of saving several “scientific men in humble life” from utter destitution” (Secord 2005: 34).

Very few items of Brown's correspondence seem to have survived so it is difficult to trace all his friends and contacts, although one newspaper report on the proceedings of a Manchester Natural History Society Council meeting, tells of correspondence with Richard Owen concerning the “skull of a dugong, and some fossils from Moreton Bay”.

He was at various times a member of many societies, where he crossed paths with influential associates, including the British Archaeological Association; the Manchester Natural History Society; the Manchester Geological Society, for which he served as a Council Member in 1840–1841; the Royal Physical Society of Edinburgh, for which he acted as President; and the Linnean Society. Some lesser-known bodies appear on the title pages of his books,

Figure 12. Plate 1 from *The Miscellany of Natural History. Volume 1 Parrots* (1833–1834). Carolina Parrot, engraved by Joseph B. Kidd. (Image from Biodiversity Heritage Library, <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/43023793>.)

MESMERISM.—CAPTAIN BROWN'S LECTURE ON THE DISCOVERIES OF MR. BRAID, OF MANCHESTER.

On Tuesday evening Captain Thomas Brown, M.W.S., late president of the Royal Physical Society, delivered a lecture on the subject of mesmerism, at the Portico, Newington, before a highly respectable audience, amounting to between 130 and 150 individuals, including several ladies and medical gentlemen of the town and neighbourhood. The discoveries were not those of Captain Brown, but of Mr. Braid, a surgeon, of Manchester, who, it was stated, had exhibited the influence of mesmerism on almost every individual at first trial, including somnolency, insensibility to pain, the cataleptiform state, somnambulism, sleep-talking, dancing, and various evolutions as desired.

Figure 13. Brown espoused Dr William Braid's practice of “mesmerism” and gave lectures with practical demonstrations. A notice from the *Liverpool Standard and General Commercial Advertiser* of December 24, 1841.

including the Bolton Literary and Philosophical Society; the Kirwanian Society; the Syrio-Egyptian Society of London; and the Edinburgh Phrenological Society. Probably some of these involved minimal activity, but Brown certainly took a strong part in the Manchester scientific scene and gave lectures to various local bodies. Figure 14 shows a notice for one of these from the *Manchester Courier* of December 3, 1842.

Another source of information about Brown's networks comes from the front matter of his books, which often contained a dedication leaf. These either thanked dignitaries, probably as part of a patron--client relationship, or expressed gratitude to friends and colleagues. Among the former were variously the Duke and Duchess of Buccleuch & Queensbury, while of a friend and artist John Burnet, Brown noted "in remembrance of the many happy hours we have spent together, in youth". Sir Thomas Dick Lauder was both a dedicatee (*The Conchologist's Text-book*), joint author (*The Miscellany of Natural History. Volume I Parrots*), and a financial backer of the latter work. *The Elements of Fossil Conchology* was inscribed to Edward Holme, President of the Manchester Natural History Society. On some occasions a longer list of thanks was appended. In *Illustrations of the Recent Conchology* this included the well-known Edward Forbes and William Bean.

A third source of information about his associates are the people who collected the species he described or had specimens in their collections that he studied. Of those most often mentioned, we are unable to find information about only two Scottish collectors: James Gerard [not James G. Gerard, of Aberdeen, later of British India, b. 1795 – d. 1885] and Stewart Ker. The others frequently mentioned were:

- Lieutenant-Colonel Richard Bingham (b. 1741 – d. 1824), the collector of many of Brown's Recent species.
- Edward William Binney (b. 1812 – d. 1881), a geologist, his name associated with eight of Brown's Paleozoic fossils.
- Thomas William Embleton (b. 1809 – d. 1893), a mining engineer, credited with having a fossil collection, from which Brown described six species.
- John Fleming (b. 1785 – d. 1857), a Reverend from Edinburgh, was probably the owner of five fossil species.
- Samuel Gibson (b. 1790 – d. 1849) of Manchester, noted for his collections of fossils, insects, and plants. His name is associated with some 30 of Brown's Paleozoic fossils.
- Thomas Glover (b. 1795 – d. 1887) is listed under three freshwater clams, all now synonyms.
- Rev. Joseph Goodall (b. 1760 – d. 1840) was credited with having collected six of Brown's Recent species, none now

Figure 14. A notice for a "Conversazione" at The Royal Manchester Institution, from the *Manchester Courier* of December 3, 1842.

- recognized. The genus *Goodallia* W. Turton, 1822, was named for him.
- William Elford Leach (b. 1791 – d. 1836). Brown had a manuscript by Leach and credited him with many ms names. Only two of the ms names and one collected species are still considered valid.
- William Lyons (b. 1766 – d. 1849). Brown credited him with the material for two species but rendering him as "George"; only one of the two is now considered valid.
- William Nicol (b. 1771 – d. 1851), a Scottish geologist, is credited with collecting two Recent species and one manuscript name, none now considered valid.
- Charles Prideaux (b. 1782 – d. 1868), a noted collector and cousin of W. E. Leach, was listed under three of Brown's species, none now valid.
- William Rhind (b. 1797 – d. 1894) was a geologist, who was credited with collecting four of Brown's fossil species.
- James Smith (b. 1782 – d. 1867), dredged specimens in Scotland described by Brown; he also wrote about the Pliocene. About 15 Brown Recent and Pliocene specimens came from him.
- Sir Walter Calverley Trevelyan (b. 1791 – d. 1879) is listed under six Recent species, none now in use.
- William Turton (b. 1762 – d. 1835) is noted as the collector of four species, none now valid.
- William Crawford Williamson (b. 1816 – d. 1895), Curator at the Manchester Museum before Thomas Brown, is credited with having collected a few of the fossil molluscs described by Brown.

EPONYMS

Although there are many molluscan species named *browni*(i) or *browniana*, as well as several generic names based on the name Brown, we know of only five molluscan species specifically named for Capt. Thomas Brown: the Recent *Scaphander brownii* Leach, 1852, a synonym of *Scaphander lignarius* (Linnaeus, 1785; *Bulla*), the Carboniferous clam *Carbonicola browni* Trueman & Weir, 1946, the Carboniferous cephalopod *Goniatites browni* McCoy, 1844, the Carboniferous cephalopod *Orthocera brownii* T. Brown, 1841,

which Brown credited to “Gibson ms”, and the Recent *Anodonta browni* Bourguignat, 1881, a synonym of *Anodonta anatina* (Linnaeus, 1758). It had been asserted that *Brownia* A. d’Orbigny, 1841, and *Rissoina browniana* A. d’Orbigny, 1842, were named for T. Brown, but it is more likely these were named for Patrick Browne, author of *The Civil and Natural History of Jamaica* (1756), who Alcide d’Orbigny referred to repeatedly in his books as “Brown”.

TYPE MATERIAL

Only a scattering of type material from his early works has come to light. Apparently, he gave many specimens to Lady Jean [“Jane”] Home [née Lizars] Jardine (b. 1801 – d. 1871, who had a large shell collection. She was the wife of Sir William Jardine [M.D.] (b. 1800 – d. 1874), a noted Edinburgh naturalist who specialized in birds. Her family, the Lizars, were deeply involved in publishing natural history books, including those of William Jardine, and they produced the first edition of Brown’s *Illustrations of the Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland* (1827). It is not known what happened to the collections that were in Jardine Hall, which was torn down in 1964.

Some type specimens were from the collection of William Lyons (b. 1766 – d. 1849), and two lots ended up with his collection in the Tenby Museum (TENBM) (Oliver *et al.* 2020). Three fossil types have been recognized in the Natural History Museum of the United Kingdom (NHMUK). Two species of Recent *Buccinum* have been located in the National Museum of Scotland (NMS), which also holds some specimens of non-T. Brown species figured in his books on the malacological fauna of Great Britain. It should be noted that many of Brown’s species were based on a figure or figures in the works of others, such as James Sowerby, so relevant type material may be in the eventual repository of that collection, the NHMUK. Many species were based on the collections of others and might eventually be found if these collections reached public institutions. Brown also listed new names that appeared only in the synonymies of other available species, and as unavailable names, they would not have been Brown type material.

After Brown settled into the job at the Manchester Museum [MM], his types went there, but as Jackson (1952: v–vi) pointed out, there have been many losses over time, and earlier catalogues, such as that of Bolton (1893), listed specimens as primary types that were in fact only topotypes. Brown’s fossil types present there have been isolated and numbered. None of his Recent material has been located

there. The catalogue by McGhie (2008) listed none, and an effort by one of us (BG) to find any was unsuccessful.

For type localities, we have usually updated place names to match modern usage (e.g. Devonshire becomes Devon) or added the names currently in use. In a few cases, where no confusion is likely, we have retained Brown’s original, for example Lough Strangford, which is now Strangford Lough.

BROWN’S TAXA

We have gone through Brown’s published books and papers for his new taxa, both genera and species. We have also searched Sherborn’s (1922–1933) compilation as well as online databases for his taxa, or for taxa that have been mis-attributed to him. This was not a simple task and required much additional research to figure out which taxa are really his, and there remain some ambiguous cases. Brown also made many spelling errors, including multiple spellings of his own taxa, having caught only some of these in his lists of Errata.

Brown made his own drawings and plates. He often packed as many images as possible onto a single plate. But while he sometimes grouped related images, sequential numbers were often scattered around a crowded plate to optimize image space. Over time, printed numbers have faded, and the eventual scanning of books can make the numbers in the scans even harder to read. Brown also made numbering errors in his texts, caption pages, and indices. Often the numbering mistakes were noted in the lists of Errata, but not all the errors were caught.

A particularly frustrating paper is on the Pleistocene and Holocene fossils of the Nice area of France. Thomas Allan (b. 1777 – d. 1833), a Scottish geologist took a vacation trip to Nice in 1816 or 1817. He made observations and notes on the stratigraphy, and was led by a local natural historian, Antoine Risso (b. 1777 – d. 1845). On his return, he published a significant paper on his findings (Allan 1818), which was discussed by Barale (2020a). It contained an appendix describing the new fossil species by Thomas Brown (1818b). The descriptions and figures in this appendix are fairly good, although Brown used odd generic allocations and got some of his figures wrongly cited in his text. Some of the species seem to predate taxa described by Risso himself or by others. Unfortunately, the type material of Brown’s species has not come to light, and the paper has often been ignored. Indeed, the names of Mediterranean taxa potentially involved are so well entrenched that ICZN Code Art. 23.9 (Reversal of Precedence) would probably apply to those Brown species

that are recognized as being earlier. Risso himself published on the geology of that area, whose work was summarized by Barale (2020b).

With regard to Brown's many Carboniferous taxa, it should be noted that there was an unrelated Reverend Thomas Brown (b. 1811 – d. 1893) who published on the Carboniferous Mollusca of Scotland in the 1860s.

Altogether Brown introduced 43 genera and 440 species, including unavailable names published in synonymies. Some genera are still in use. An additional 31 misspellings of his own taxa or those of others are listed. The species include 46% gastropods, 43% bivalves, 9% cephalopods, and 2% other classes. The species are 45% Recent, 23% Carboniferous, 10% Quaternary, 7% Jurassic, and 15% other epochs. We additionally list 13 taxa that have been misattributed to him. About a quarter of his taxa lack modern placements.

Brown also described taxa of other phyla that are not discussed here: about eight Foraminifera, two corals, one nematode, seven annelids, three brachiopods, one barnacle, and one fish. Here we do list the two taxa described in molluscan genera that proved to belong in other phyla. Taxa misattributed to him are listed below a centred dot (•) under the relevant families along with the two species belonging to other phyla.

In the list below, the Brown works referred to are given in the bibliography of his books and papers following the list. Only those papers with new taxa or with noted misspellings are included in the taxonomic list and given codes keyed to the bibliography. Some works appeared in parts, sometimes issued over several years:

- T. Brown, 1827-C1, *Illustrations of the Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland*, 1st ed.
 T. Brown, 1837–1841-F, *Illustrations of the Fossil Conchology of Britain and Ireland*
 T. Brown, 1838–1844-C2, *Illustrations of the Recent Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland, ...*, 2nd ed.

Other works are given letter codes following a date if there was more than one cited work in a given year, such as 1841a or 1841b; papers not cited are not given letter codes. Other abbreviations include:

ICZN	International Commission on [or Code of] Zoological Nomenclature
M	Type species of a genus established by monotypy
MM	Manchester Museum
NHMK	Natural History Museum of the United Kingdom, London
NMS	National Museum of Scotland, Edinburgh
OD	Original designation of the type species of a genus
SD	Subsequent designation of the type species of a genus
TENBM	Tenby Museum & Art Gallery, Wales

Because Brown's non-molluscan books are so often confused in the literature, we have here provided a list of them and their various editions immediately after the Brown molluscan bibliography.

Class Cephalopoda

Orthoceratidae McCoy, 1844

Note: *Orthocera* Lamarck, 1799, was used for species in this family, but is a junior homonym of *Orthocera* Modeer, 1789 [Foraminifera] (ICZN Opinion 2003, 1973).

ascicularis, *Orthocera* — T. Brown, 1841b: 220, pl. 7, fig. 39, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 249, pl. 29*, fig. 29. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10235, holotype (Bolton 1893: 19, as *O. "acicularis"*; Jackson 1952: 126). — Current status: uncertain.

brownii, *Orthocera* — T. Brown, 1841b: 220, pl. 7, fig. 40, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 249, pl. 29*, fig. 30. — Type locality: High Greenwood, near Hebden Bridge & Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10236, holotype (Bolton 1893: 19, as "Gibson"; Jackson 1952: 126). — Current status: uncertain.

cornuibex, *Orthoceras* — T. Brown, 1838-F: 41, pl. 28, fig. 13. — Type locality: High Greenwood, England; shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. New species based in part on one of two figures of *Orthocera annulata* J. Sowerby, 1816, by J. Phillips (1836: pl. 21, fig. 10). — Current status: uncertain.

gibsoni, *Belemnites* — T. Brown, 1841b: 220–221, pl. 7, fig. 41; 1849-F: 249, pl. 29*, fig. 28. — Type locality: Crimsworth Dean, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; "limestone shale". — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10234, holotype (Bolton 1893; Jackson 1952). — Current status: *Orthoceras gibsoni* (T. Brown, 1841) (Bolton 1893: 19; Jackson 1952: 94).

microscopica, *Orthocera* — T. Brown, 1841b: 220, pl. 7, figs 37–38, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 249, pl. 29, figs 26–27. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; shale — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

obtus, *Orthocera* — T. Brown, 1841b: 219–220, pl. 7, fig. 36, *ex* Gibson ms. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10026, holotype (Bolton, 1893: 19; Jackson 1952: 126; Nudds 1992: 86). — Current status: uncertain.

Goniatites, s.l.

- discors, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 29, pl. 31, figs 18, 18*. New species based on two of the six figures of *Goniatites gilbertsoni* J. Phillips, 1836 (p. 236, pl. 20, figs 29–30). Phillips' page number was misquoted by Brown as "238". — Type locality: Bolland, Queen's County [Ballyadams, County Laois], Ireland. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: uncertain.
- discrepans, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1838-F: 28, pl. 21, figs 8, 15. New species based on two of four figures of *Goniatites looneyi* J. Phillips, 1836 (p. 236, pl. 20, figs 32, 34). — Type locality: High Greenwood, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: *Dimorphoceras discrepans* (T. Brown, 1838) (Moore 1938: 123–125, text-fig. 5), or perhaps senior synonym of *D. looneyi* (J. Phillips, 1836; *Goniatites*).
- dorsalis, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 214–215, pl. 7, figs 11–12, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 247, pl. 21*, figs 11–13. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; nodules in limestone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.
- intermedius, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 213–214, pl. 7, figs 6–7, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 246–247, pl. 21, figs 6–7, *non* Münster, 1839. — Type locality: High Greenwood near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.11798, holotype (Bolton 1893: 15; Jackson 1952: 108). Both preoccupy *Goniatites intermedius* Kobold, 1933. — Current status: uncertain.
- jugosus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 215, pl. 7, figs 14–15, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 247, pl. 21*, figs 14–15. — Type locality: Near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM, "holotype" (Bolton, 1893: 15), but not so listed by Jackson (1952). — Current status: uncertain.
- kenyoni, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 216, pl. 7, figs 19–20, *ex* Gibson ms. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10239, holotype (Bolton 1893: 15; Jackson 1952). *Dimorphoceras kenyoni* (T. Brown, 1841) (Jackson 1952: 109). — Current status: *Glyphiolobus kenyoni* (T. Brown, 1841) (Ruzhentsev & Bogoslovskaya 1971: p./figs unknown).
- longthorni, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 216–217, pl. 7, figs 23–26, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 247–248, pl. 21*, figs 24–26. — Type locality: Near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; soft shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM "syntypes" (Bolton 1893: 16) but not so listed by Jackson (1952). — Current status: uncertain.
- minutissimus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 218, pl. 7, figs 29–31, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 248, pl. 21*, figs 29–31. — Type locality: Millwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10240, holotype (Bolton 1893: 16; Jackson 1952: 109). — Current status: uncertain.
- paradoxicus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 216, pl. 7, figs 21–22, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 247, pl. 21, figs 21–22. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10243, holotype (Bolton 1893: 16; Jackson 1952: 109). — Current status: uncertain.
- parvus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 217–218, pl. 7, figs 32–33, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 248, pl. 21*, figs 32–33. — Type locality: Hoole Bottom, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10238, holotype (Jackson 1952: 110). — Current status: uncertain.
- proteus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 217, pl. 7, figs 27–28, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 248, pl. 21*, figs 27–28. — Type locality: Lob Mill, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM, "6 syntypes" (Bolton 1893: 1) but not so listed by Jackson (1952). — Current status: *Hudsonoceras proteus* (T. Brown, 1841) (Lacchia *et al.* 2015: 76).
- smithii, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 218, pl. 7, figs 34–35, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 248, pl. 21*, figs 34–35. — Type locality: Millwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10244, holotype (Bolton 1893: 18; Jackson 1952: 110). — Current status: *Homoceras smithii* (T. Brown, 1841) (Lacchia *et al.* 2015: 76).
- splendidus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 215–216, pl. 7, figs 16–17, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 247, pl. 21*, figs 19–20. — Type locality: Near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10242, holotype (Jackson 1952: 110–111). *Dimorphoceras splendidum* (T. Brown, 1841) (Moore 1938: 119–120, text-figs 8, 16). Type species (OD) of *Metadimorphoceras* Moore, 1958. — Current status: *Metadimorphoceras splendidus* (T. Brown, 1841).
- subsulcatus, *Goniatites*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 214, pl. 7, figs

9–10, *ex* Longthorn ms; 1849-F: 247, pl. 21*, figs 8–10, *non* Münster, 1832. — Type locality: Near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; nodules in limestone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM “syntypes” (Bolton 1893: 17) but not so listed by Jackson (1952). — Current status: uncertain.

undulatus, *Goniatites* — T. Brown, 1841b: 213, pl. 7, figs 1–5, *ex* Gibson ms; 1849-F: 246, pl. 21*, figs 1–5. — Type locality: Lambert’s Clough, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10241, syntypes (Bolton 1893: 17; Jackson 1952: 112). — Current status: *Homoceras undulatum* (T. Brown, 1841) (Lacchia *et al.* 2015: 76).

Nautiloids, s.l.

goniolobatus, *Nautilus* — T. Brown, 1838-F: 36. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Nautilus goniolobus* J. Phillips, 1836.

Ammonites, s.l.

allasii, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 244, pl. 20*, fig. 1. — Type locality: Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Jurassic. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

artigyrus, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 26, pl. 29, fig. 5. Brown cited Phillips’ page and figure. “Type material”: MM LL.230, “holotype” (Jackson 1952: 81). — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Ammonites arcigerens* J. Phillips, 1829 (p. 163, pl. 13, fig. 9).

calcar, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 246, pl. 20*, fig. 4, *non* Zieten, 1831, *ex* Benz ms. — Type locality: Scarborough, England. — Type age: Jurassic; Thomas Allis collection. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

cookii, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 244, pl. 20*, fig. 7. — Type locality: None given. — Type age: none given. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

costatus, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 6, pl. 5, fig. 2. — Type locality: Ringmer, Sussex, England; limestone. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian?). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

cornuoides, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 7, pl. 5, fig. 8. — Type locality: Whitby, England. — Type age: Jurassic (Early). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

dissimilis, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 246, pl. 20*, figs 11–13. — Type locality: Scarborough, England; calcareous grit [Lower Calcareous Grit Formation]. — Type age:

Jurassic (Callovian). — Type material: MM L.11495, holotype & “genotype” (Jackson 1952). Type species (OD) of *Eboraceras* Buckman, 1918. — Current status: *Eboraceras dissimilis* (T. Brown, 1849) (Buckman 1918: xiv, 118a–c, pls 118A–B; Jackson 1952: 84–85).

minimus, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 27, pl. 20, fig. 6. — Type locality: Yorkshire, England; Speeton Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Early). New species based on an unnamed *Ammonites* “like *A. parvus*” of J. Phillips (1829: 187, pl. 2, fig. 46). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

ptychomphalus, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 17, pl. 13, figs 2, 11. — Type locality: Bolingbroke, Lincolnshire, England, sandstone [Spilsby Sandstone Formation]; Mr. Wier; Yorkshire, England, Kimmeridge Clay [Formation]; Normandy, Oxford clay. — Type age: Jurassic–Cretaceous (Oxfordian–Berriasian). New species name but in the synonymy of *Ammonites plicomphalus* J. Sowerby, 1822 (p. 82, pl. 359; 1823: p. 145, pl. 404). — Current status: presumably synonym of *Subcraspedites plicomphalus* (J. Sowerby, 1822; *Ammonites*).

rotifer, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 246, pl. 20*, figs 14–15, *ex* Williamson (1841: 147, *nomen nudum*). — Type locality: Scarborough, England; calcareous grit [Lower Cretaceous Grit Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Callovian). — Type material: MM LL.11494, holotype (Buckman 1918: 113a–c, pl. 113, figs 1–3; Jackson 1952: 90; Nudds 1992: 86). — Current status: uncertain.

selliguius, *Ammonites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 13, pl. 10, fig. 3. — Evidently intended as a replacement name for *Ammonites laevigatus* J. De C. Sowerby, 1827 (p. 93, pl. 540, fig. 1 [January 1, 1827]), *non* *Ammonites laevigatus* J. De C. Sowerby, 1827 (p. 135, pl. 570, fig. 3 [September 1, 1827]), which Brown had listed on his p. 15. Sowerby’s volume mistakenly listed by Brown as 7 instead of 6 for the renamed species, perhaps accounting for the fact that he renamed the senior homonym. — Type locality: Crockerton near Warminster, England; Miss Bennet; & Cheriton, near Sandgate, Kent, England; Dr. Fitton; clay. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. Brown’s new name is not to be confused with nor is it preoccupied by *Ammonites selliguius* Brongniart, 1822. — Current status: synonym of *Ammonites laevigatus* J. De C. Sowerby, 1827, now *Robertoceras laevigatum* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1827).

Hamites, s.l.

annulatus, *Hamites* — T. Brown, 1837-F: 3, pl. 1, fig. 10. — Type locality: Wiltshire, England; green sand [Lower

- Greensand Group]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Aptian-Albian). Brown noted that this had been figured by Parkinson (1811: 144, pl. 10, fig. 5) as *Hamites* sp. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Hamites parkinsoni* J. Fleming, 1828 (Klein 2015: 90–91).
- costatus, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 3, pl. 1, fig. 8. New species based on one of the three figures *Hamites intermedius* J. Sowerby, 1814 (p. 139, pl. 62, fig. 2). — Type locality: Folkestone, Kent, England; clay [Gault Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: uncertain.
- incurvatus, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 3, pl. 1, fig. 4. New species based on Parkinson (1833: 144: pl. 10, fig. 2). — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: would be Parkinson's material. — Current status: *Hamites incurvatus* T. Brown, 1837 (Klein 2015: 86).
- inflexus, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 3, pl. 1, fig. 12. New species based on Parkinson (1833: 144–145: pl. 10, fig. 3). — Type locality: Shotover Hill, near Oxford, England; [“Shotover Iron Sands” = Whitchurch Sands Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Valanginian). — Type material: would be Parkinson's material. — Current status: uncertain.
- lyelli, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 3, pl. 1, fig. 3. New species based on Buckland (1836: 65, pl. 44, fig. 11, *Hamites* sp.). — Type locality: Folkestone, Kent, England; clay [Gault Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: would be Buckland's material. — Current status: uncertain.
- multicostatus, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F, pl. 2, fig. 9. — Type locality: Hamsey, England; Mrs. Mantell. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian-Cenomanian?). Discussed and figured but not named by Mantell (1822: 123, pl. 23, fig. 5). — Type material: NHMUK-PI-OR-36572, holotype. Type species (OD) of *Plesiohamites* Breistroffer, 1947. — Current status: genus and species remain *nomina dubia* (Klein 2015: 112).
- rectus, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 3, pl. 1, fig. 11. New species based on Parkinson (1833: 144, pl. 10, fig. 1). — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: would be Parkinson's material. — Current status: *Hamites rectus* T. Brown, 1837 (Klein 2015: 92; Pandey *et al.*, 2021: 949–950, text-fig. 3G–I).
- undulatus, *Hamites*** — T. Brown, 1837-F: 1–2, pl. 2, fig. 11. — Type locality: Isle of Wight, England; G.B. Snow & Benson; Oxfordshire, England; R. Wright; chalk marl. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). New species based in part on the second of two figures of *Hamites armatus* J. Sowerby, 1819 (p. 59, pl. 234, fig. 2). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: synonym of *Anisoceras armatus* (J. Sowerby, 1817) (Klein 2015: 27–31).

Belemnites, s.l.

- electrinus, *Belemnites*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 249, pl. 29*, figs 23–24. — Type locality: Lyme Regis, Dorset, England. — Type age: Jurassic (Early). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.
- voluminus, *Belemnites*** — T. Brown, 1838-F: 42, pl. 29, fig. 10. New species based on one of the five figures *Belemnites mucronatus* Schlotheim, 1813, as figured by J. De C. Sowerby (1829: 205–207, pl. 600, fig. 7). — Type locality: Norwich, England; chalk. — Type age: Cretaceous (Late). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: uncertain.

Class Polyplacophora

Not sorted by family, but family names provided for reference.

- achatinus, *Chiton*** — W. E. Leach & T. Brown, 1823: 402; T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 35, figs 4, 12; 1844-C2: 65–66, pl. 21, figs 4, 12–13, 15. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Callochiton septemvalvis* (Montagu, 1803; *Chiton*) (Kaas & Van Belle 1998: 11; figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 42, pl. 12). [Callochitonidae]
- discrepans, *Chiton*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 35, fig. 20; 1844-C2: 65, pl. 21, fig. 20. — Type locality: Tenby, Wales [1844]; George Lyons. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: TENBM.1983.4588, lectotype (Kaas 1985: 598–602) & 6 paralectotypes. — Current status: *Acanthochitona discrepans* (T. Brown, 1827) (Kaas & Van Belle 1998: 63; Alf *et al.* 2020: 49, pl. 19; Oliver *et al.* 2020: 25–26, fig. 12; Dell'Angelo *et al.* 2025: 295). [Acanthochitonidae]
- foliatus, *Chiton*** — T. Brown, 1818b: pl. 9, fig. 1. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Lepidopleurus cajetanus* (Poli, 1791; *Chiton*) (Dell'Angelo *et al.* 2025: 24–28, fig. 3, as “Allan”; figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 35, pl. 10). [Lepidochitonidae]
- fuscatus, *Chiton*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 35, fig. 17; 1844-C2: 66, pl. 21, fig. 17. — Type locality: Firth of

Forth, Scotland. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Chiton fuscatus* J.E. Leach, 1852.

— Current status: synonym of *Lepidochitona cinerea* (Linnaeus, 1767; *Chiton*) (Kaas & Van Belle 1998: 78; figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 47, pls 17–18). [Tonicellidae]

quinquivalvis, *Chiton* — T. Brown, in W. E. Leach & T. Brown, 1823: 402; 1827-C1: pl. 35, fig. 22; 1844-C2: 67, pl. 21, fig. 22. — Type locality: none given; Tenby [1844], Wales; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Lepidochitona cinerea* (Linnaeus, 1767; *Chiton*) (Kaas & Van Belle 1998: 155; figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 47, pls 17–18). [Tonicellidae]

Class Scaphopoda

acuminatum, *Dentalium* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 243, pl. 98, fig. 74, *non* Deshayes, 1825. New species based on *Dentalium entalis* Linnaeus, 1758, of J. Sowerby (1814: 159, pl. 70, fig. 3). — Type locality: Hordwell [Hordle] Cliff, Hampshire, England, “etc.”; London Clay [Headon Hill Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Priabonian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. Both Deshayes’ and Brown’s species preoccupy *D. acuminatum* Gardner, 1878. Listed by Steiner & Kabat (2004: 558). — Current status: uncertain.

labiatum, *Dentalium* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata], pl. 1, figs 4–5; 1844-C2: 117, pl. 56, figs 4–5, *non* W. Turton, 1819. — Type locality: Lough Strangford, Ireland; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Neither of Brown’s accounts mentioned Turton. Listed by Steiner & Kabat (2004: 607). — Current status: synonym of *Antalis entalis* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Dentalium*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 401; figured by Cossignani & Ardovini 2011: 497).

striatum, *Dentalium* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 8, *non* Born, 1778, *nec* Link, 1807, *nec* J. Sowerby, 1814, *nec* Lamarck, 1818. — Type locality: Holy Island, Northumberland, England; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Listed by Steiner & Kabat (2004: 648). All preoccupy *Dentalium striatum* Eichwald, 1830, and of Ivanov, 1926. — Current status: uncertain.

Class Gastropoda

Unallocated Gastropods

Spira — T. Brown, 1838-C2: viii, 20, 144, pl. 8, figs 34, 37–39, 42–44, 46, 50–52. An available generic name with seven originally included species mostly based on juvenile gastropods. A subsequent designation of a type

species would be pointless. The seven taxa were from unfigured listings in Montagu, generally taken in turn from still earlier works: *Helix globosa* Montagu, 1803 (p. 444), *ex* Boys & Walker (1784: 7, fig. 25, juvenile whorls of a gastropod); *Helix reticulata* “Montagu”, 1803 (p. 444), originally Kanmacher, in G. Adams (1798: 636, pl. 14, fig. 12, *ex* Jacob ms, juvenile whorls of a gastropod); *Helix coarctata* Montagu, 1803 (p. 445), *ex* Boys & Walker (1784: 8, fig. 30; juvenile whorls of a gastropod); *H. tubulata* “Montagu” (1803: 446), actually J. Adams (1797: 67, pl. 13, figs 35–36, juvenile whorls of a gastropod); *H. variegata* “Montagu”, 1803 (p. 446), actually J. Adams, 1797: 67, unfigured, *non* Gmelin, 1791; *Helix nitidissima* “Montagu”, 1803 (p. 447), actually J. Adams (1800: 4, pl. 1, figs 22–24, a possible *Omalogyra*); and *Helix bicolor* “Montagu”, 1803 (p. 447), actually J. Adams (1800: 4, pl. 1, figs 25–27, also a possible *Omalogyra*). Brown’s images were all copies. — Type locality: various. Type age: Recent. Wenz (1938: 647) tentatively associated Brown’s genus with *Omalogyra* Jeffreys, 1860, noting the only probable adult specimens among the original images. — Current status: *nomen dubium*.

Notes: *Helix reticulata* Kanmacher, in G. Adams, 1798, preoccupies L. Pfeiffer, 1857. *Helix globosa* Montagu, 1802, preoccupies Godwin-Austen, 1876, and others. *Helix coarctata* Montagu, 1803, preoccupies L. Pfeiffer, 1849, and A. Klein, 1853. *Helix nitidissima* J. Adams, 1800, preoccupies E. A. Smith, 1885. *Helix bicolor* J. Adams, 1800, preoccupies *Helix hortensis bicolor* Picard, 1840 (but the latter is a synonym).

compressa, *Melania* — T. Brown, 1843-F: 96, pl. 33*, figs 28–29. — Type locality: Gisborne [Gisburn?], Yorkshire, England; S. Gibson; Gibson collection. — Type age: Jurassic (Middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

deptfordensis, *Melanopsis* — T. Brown, 1843-F: 95, pl. 45, figs 22–23. New species based on one of the seven figures of *Melanopsis fusiformis* J. Sowerby, 1822 (p. 36, pl. 332, fig. 5). — Type locality: New Cross, near Deptford & Isle of Wight, England. — Type age: Eocene (Priabonian)? — Type material: would be among Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

multicostatus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 252, pl. 37*, figs 3–4, *non* Anton, 1839. Both preoccupy *Fusus multicostatus* Morris & Lycett, 1851, and of Whitfield, 1892. — Type locality: Staffordshire, England; Dudley limestone [Much Wenlock Limestone Formation?]. — Type age: Silurian. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain; not Fasciolaridae (Snyder 2022: 134).

obtusa, Cassidaria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 49, fig. 3, in synonymy with *Buccinum obtusissimum* J. Adams, 1797, which was based on the larval whorls of a gastropod, as was Brown's image. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: uncertain.

Bellerophontidae McCoy, 1852

expansus, Bellerophon — T. Brown, 1838-F: 38, pl. 26, fig. 29. — Type locality: Bolland, Queen's County [Ballyadams, County Laois], Ireland. — Type age: Carboniferous — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Bellerophon expansus* J. De C. Sowerby, in Murchison, 1839. — Current status: uncertain.

sulcatus, Bellerophon — T. Brown, 1838-F: 38, pl. 26, figs 23, 26 [no month date], *non* Potiez & Michaud, 1838 [Oct.]. — Type locality: Bolland, Queen's County [Ballyadams, County Laois], Ireland. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

Euomphalidae C.A. White, 1877

Crassidorsa — T. Brown, 1843-F: 98. Type species (M): *Planorbis equalis* J. Sowerby, 1816. — Type age: Carboniferous. This J. Sowerby species preoccupies *Planorbis aequalis* C.A. White, 1880, which is in current use for a fossil *Biomphalaria*. — Current status: synonym of *Straparollus* Montfort, 1810.

Patellidae Rafinesque, 1815

albumena, Patella vulgata var. — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 63, pl. 20, figs 12, 14. — Type locality: Cullercoats, near Tynemouth, Northumberland, England; T. Brown; Portmarnock, Ireland; T. W. Warren. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Patella ulyssiponensis* Gmelin, 1791 (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 421, by implication through its synonymy with *P. athletica* W. Bean, 1844; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 55, pls 32–33).

communis, Patella vulgata var. — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 63, pl. 20, fig. 15. — Type locality: none give, but probably England. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Patella vulgata* Linnaeus, 1758 (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 421; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 55–56, pls 34, 78).

conica, Patella vulgata var. — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 63, pl. 20, figs 1, 4, 6. — Type locality: Bamburgh Castle & Holy Island, Northumberland, England; Balbriggan & Killybegs, County Down, Ireland; all T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current sta-

tus: synonym of *Patella vulgata* Linnaeus, 1758 (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 421; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 55–56, pls 34, 78).

greenwoodi, Patella — T. Brown, 1841b: 224, pl. 7, figs 58–59; 1849-F: 256, pl. 21*, figs 58–59. — Type locality: Near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10237, holotype. — Current status: synonym of *Orbiculoidea nitida* (J. Phillips, 1836; *Orbicula*) (Jackson 1952: 57) [Brachiopoda].

Lottiidae J.E. Gray, 1840

clypea, Patella — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 37, figs 9–10; 1844: 64, in synonymy with *Lottia testudinalis*. — Type locality: Arran, Scotland; Stewart Ker; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Testudinalia testudinalis* (O.F. Müller, 1776; *Patella*) (Jeffreys 1865: 248; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 56, pl. 35).

Eotomariidae Wenz, 1938

Cochlicarina — T. Brown, 1843-F: 99–100, covering four J. Sowerby species. Type species (SD Knight *et al.* 1960, as “obj.”): *Helicina compressa* J. Sowerby, 1813. — Current status: objective synonym of *Ptychomphalus* A. Agassiz, 1839, which has the same Jurassic type species.

Plethospiridae Wenz, 1938

Caliendrum — T. Brown, 1838-F: 52, pl. 32, fig. 20. Type species (M): *Buccinum vittatum* J. Phillips, 1836, *non* Linnaeus, 1767. — Current status: valid Carboniferous genus (Wenz 1938: 168, text-fig. 262), but Phillips' species name will need to be replaced if there is no synonym.

Phymatopleuridae Batten, 1956

bicostatus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1841-F: 73, 261, “pl. 37*, figs 11–13” [actually pl. 33*, figs 65–67]. — Type locality: Witherell, near Clitheroe, Lancashire, England; mountain limestone [Clitheroe Limestone Formation]; Samuel Gibson; Gibson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous (Visean). — Type material: MM, holotype, not located. Preoccupies *Turbo bicostatus* F. A. Roemer, 1855. — Current status: possible synonym of *Worthenia tabulata* (Conrad, 1835; *Turbo*) (Jackson 1952: 59).

Pleurotomariidae Swainson, 1840

dubia, Pleurotomaria — T. Brown, 1842-F: 87, pl. 40, fig. 27. — Type locality: Bolland [Ballyadams, County Laois], Ireland; mountain limestone. — Type age: Carbonifer-

ous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

fibula, *Pleurotomaria* — T. Brown, 1842-F: 85–86, pl. 40, fig. 6. Unnecessary replacement name for *P. strialis* J. Phillips, 1836 (p. 227, pl. 15, fig. 9), “as it was too near to” *Pleurotomaria striata* J. De C. Sowerby, 1836. — Type locality: Bolland [Ballyadams, County Laois], Ireland. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Current status: synonym of *Pleurotomaria strialis* J. Phillips, 1836.

Cirridae Cossmann, 1916

gloveri, *Cirrus* — T. Brown, 1841b: 223, pl. 7, figs 46–47; 1849-F: 255, pl. 21*, figs 46–47. — Type locality: High Greenwood near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10231 (Bolton 1893: 14; Jackson 1952). — Current status: *Straparollus gloveri* (T. Brown, 1841) (Jackson 1952: 54).

turbanoides, *Cirrus* — T. Brown, 1841-F: 80, pl. 41, fig. 24. New species based on *Cirrus nodosus* “var.” of J. Sowerby (1818: 35, pl. 219, figs 1–2, 4). Brown mistakenly cited Sowerby’s figure(s) as “24”. *Cirrus nodosus* itself was originally published by J. Sowerby (1816: 94, pl. 141, fig. 2). — Type locality: Dundry, England; lower oolite [Inferior Oolite Group]. — Type age: Jurassic (Aalenian-Bajocian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

Fissurellidae J. Fleming, 1822

Sipho — see: *Sypho*.

Sypho — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata] & iii [corrected to “*Sipho*”], pl. 36, figs 14–16, 20 (two species); 1833: 100; 1843-F: 103; 1844-C2: 61, non *Sipho* Fabricius (1823), but that is an unavailable work. — Type species (**SD herein**): *Sypho striata* T. Brown, 1827, a synonym of *Puncturella noachina* (Linnaeus, 1771; *Patella*). Misspelled by J.E. Gray (1847: 147) as *Siphon*. Preoccupies *Sypho* Mörch, 1852, ex Klein ms [Buccinidae]. — Current status: synonym of *Puncturella* R.T. Lowe, 1827, which has the same type species.

radiata, *Sypho* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata — corrected to “*radiatus*”], iii, pl. 36, fig. 20; 1844-C2: 61, pl. 12, fig. 20, in both references in synonymy with *Patella apertura* Montagu, 1803. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Diodora graeca* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Patella*) (Jeffreys 1865: 267; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 60, pl. 38).

striata, *Sypho* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata — corrected to “*striatus*”], iii, pl. 36, figs 14–16; 1833: 100, pl. 14,

fig. 21; 1844-C2: 61, as a synonym of *S. noachina* “Smith” [Linnaeus, 1771; *Patella*]. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker; Ker & Lady Jardine collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Puncturella noachina* (Linnaeus, 1771) (Jeffreys 1865: 258; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 62, pl. 40).

sulcata, *Emarginula* — T. Brown, 1843-F: 104, pl. 48, figs 16, 16*, 17, non Blainville, 1819. New species based on *Emarginula* sp. J. De C. Sowerby (1826: 34, pl. 519, fig. 4). J. De C. Sowerby’s *E. scalaris* was based on his figure 3. — Type locality: Ancliffe, England; oolite [Corsham Limestone Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Bathonian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

Trochidae Rafinesque, 1815

dubius, *Trochus* — T. Brown, 1841-F: 75, pl. 39, fig. 10, non Dillwyn, 1817. New species based on *Trochus* sp. of Mantell (1822: 109, pl. 18, fig. 7). — Type locality: Hamsey, Sussex, England; grey chalk marl. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian-Cenomanian?). — Type material: would be Mantell’s material. Both preoccupy *Trochus dubius* R. A. Philippi, 1844, and of A. Aradas, 1846/7. — Current status: uncertain.

littoralis, *Trochus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 45, figs 1, 4; 1838-C2: viii, 18, pl. 11, figs 1, 4. — Type locality: Killylough, County Down, Ireland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *T. littoralis* Brusina, 1865, a synonym of *Jujubinus striatus* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Trochus*). — Current status: synonym of *Trochus cinerarius* Linnaeus, 1758 (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 516–519, pl. 65, figs 1–3, pl. DD, fig. 1, 1a; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 70, pl. 50, as *Gibbula*), now *Steromphala cineraria* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Affenzeller *et al.* 2017: 804).

martini, *Trochus* — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 99–100, pl. 1, fig. 26, ex J. Smith ms; 1844-C2: 129, pl. 57, fig. 11. — Type locality: Kyles of Bute, Scotland; T. Brown; Isle of Man, England; E. Forbes; Dublin, Ireland; Alder. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Clelandella miliaris* (Brocchi, 1814; *Trochus*) (Jeffreys 1865: 327; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 68, pl. 46).

perforatus, *Trochus* — T. Brown, 1838-C2: viii, 18, pl. 57, figs 9–10; T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 99, pl. 1, figs 3–4. — Type locality: Kyles of Bute, Scotland; James Smith, in deep water. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. The figures were added after the descriptive

text was printed and were cited only in the Index (p. viii) and in the Errata (p. 145). — Current status: synonym of *Trochus cinerarius* Linnaeus, 1758 (Jeffreys 1865: 312; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 70, pl. 50, as *Gibbula*), now *Sterromphala cineraria* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Mollusca-Base).

tathami, Trochus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 254, pl. 33*, figs 50–52. — Type locality: Settle, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Current status: uncertain.

torosus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1818b: 462, pl. 10, fig. 9 [mis-labeled “6” in text]. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Trochus torosus* Kiener, 1850, a synonym of *Micrelenchus purpureus* (Gmelin, 1791; *Helix*) and of Kirchner, 1915 [Devonian]. — Current status: synonym of *Gibbula fanulum* (Gmelin, 1791; *Trochus*) (herein; figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 71, pl. 51).

vestrarius, Rotella — T. Brown, 1833: 80, pl. 12, fig. 18. — Current status: incorrect subsequent spelling of *Umbonium vestiarium* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Calliostomatidae Thiele, 1924

aureus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 46, fig. 23; 1838-C2: viii, 17, pl. 10, fig. 23. — Type locality: Seaton, England; W. C. Trevelyan. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Genus changed to *Margarita* W. E. Leach, 1819 [now *Margarites* J.E. Gray, 1847] in 1838 in Index [p. viii] and Errata [p. 145]. — Current status: synonym of *Calliostoma zizyphinum* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Trochus*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 535; 1852: 259, as *Trochus*; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 82, pls 71–73, 78).

discrepans, Trochus — T. Brown, 1818a: 519–520, pl. 24, fig. 4; 1827-C1: iv, pl. 45, figs 20, 23; 1838-C2: 19, pl. 11, figs 20, 23. — Type locality: Holywood, Ireland; Miss Templeton; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Calliostoma zizyphinum* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Trochus*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 491–495, pl. 67, figs 1–6, as *Trochus*; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 82, pls 71–73, 78).

Margaritidae Thiele, 1924

inflatus, Trochus — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 102, pl. 10, figs 10–11, *ex* Smith ms; 1849-F: 254, pl. 33* [listed in text as 33 in error], figs 60–61, *non* Blainville, 1830. — Type locality: Dalmuir, Scotland; J. Smith. — Type age: Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possible synonym of *Margarites groenlandicus*

(Gmelin, 1791; *Trochus*) (Jeffreys 1865: 300; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 83, pl. 73).

olivaceus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 46, figs 30–31; 1838-C2: 17, pl. 10, figs 28–29. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: *Margarites olivaceus* (T. Brown, 1827) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 34).

Microdomatidae Wenz, 1938

mancuniensis, Turbo — T. Brown, 1841a: 63, pl. 6, figs 1–3; 1841-F: 74, “pl. 37*, figs 15–16” [Errata: should be pl. 21, figs 38–39]. — Type locality: Collyhurst, Manchester, England; E.W. Binney; red magnesian marl [Manchester Marls Formation?]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: Manchester Geological Society Museum, now missing. — Current status: synonym of *Glyptospira ? helicina* (Schlotheim, 1820; *Trochilites*) (Pattison 1970: 141, pl. 20, fig. 6).

Skeneidae W. Clark, 1851

Delphinoidea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, figs 32–47, 50–52 (10 species). Type species (SD Knight *et al.* 1960: 271, as “obj.”): *Helix serpuloides* Montagu, 1803, which is the type species (SD J.E. Gray, 1847) of *Skenea* J. Fleming, 1825. — Current status: synonym of *Skenea*, the type genus of this family.

Delphinoidea — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 19. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Delphinoidea* T. Brown, 1827.

Platyoceratidae J. Hall, 1879

minutus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1841a: 63, pl. 6, figs 4–5; 1841-F: 74, “pl. 37*, figs 17–18” [Errata: should be pl. 31, figs 40 & 74], *non* T. Brown, 1818, *nec* Michaud, 1828, *nec* Totten, 1834. — Type locality: Collyhurst, Manchester, England; E.W. Binney; red magnesium marl [Manchester Marls Formation?]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tunstallia helicina* (Schlotheim, 1820; *Trochilites*) (Hollingworth & Barker 1991: 358–359, text-figs 15–16, 22.2-1), the type species of *Tunstallia* Hollingworth & Barker, 1991.

Naticopsidae Waagen, 1880

minima, Natica — T. Brown, 1841a: 64, pl. 6, figs 22–24; 1849-F: 255–256, pl. 21, figs 63–65, *non* I. Lea, 1833. — Type locality: Newton, Manchester, England; red marl. — Type age: Permian (Upper). — Type material: NHMUK. PG.4565, neotype (Hollingworth & Barker, 1991). — Current status: *Naticopsis minima* (T. Brown, 1841)

(Pattison 1970: 142, pl. 20, fig. 7; Hollingworth & Barker 1991: 356, text-figs 4, 11, 12.5-7; Mazaev 2015: 960–963, pl. 34, figs 14–15), but as a junior primary homonym, the species name needs to be replaced; **here we here propose *Naticopsis mazaevi* Coan & Goodwin**; named for the Russian paleontologist Alexey V. Mazaev for his work on such Paleozoic gastropods.

Coelostylinidae Cossmann, 1908

gibsoni*, *Rissoa — T. Brown, 1841a: 64, pl. 6, figs 15–17; 1841: 79, 260, pl. 21*, figs 69–70, 76 [in text mistakenly as pl. 37*, figs 31–33]. — Type locality: Collyhurst, near Manchester, England; magnesian marl [Manchester Marls Formation?]; E.W. Binney; Binney collection. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: NHMUK.PG.4464, neotype (Hollingworth & Barker 1991). Synonym of *Coelostylina* ? *leighi* (T. Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 143, pl. 20, figs 11–12; — Current status: *Coelostylina gibsoni* (T. Brown, 1839) (Hollingworth & Barker 1991: 361, text figs 21, 22.3-4).

leighi*, *Rissoa — T. Brown, 1841a: 64, pl. 6, figs 9–11; 1841: 79, 260, pl. 21*, figs 36–37, 68 [in text mistakenly as pl. 37*, figs 25–27]. — Type locality: Collyhurst, near Manchester, England; magnesian marl [Manchester Marls Formation?]; E.W. Binney; Binney collection. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Coelostylina* ? *leighi* (T. Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 143, pl. 20, figs 11–12).

minutissima*, *Rissoa — T. Brown, 1841a: 64, pl. 6, figs 12–14; 1841: 79, 260, as *Turbo*, pl. 21*, figs 71–73 [in text mistakenly as pl. 37*, figs 28–30], *non* Michaud, 1830. — Type locality: Collyhurst, near Manchester, England; magnesian marl [Manchester Marls Formation]; E.W. Binney; Binney collection. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Coelostylina* ? *obtusa* (T. Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 145, pl. 20, figs 8–9).

obtusa*, *Rissoa — T. Brown, 1841a: 64, pl. 6, figs 19–21; 1841-F: 79; 1849-F: 260, pl. 21*, figs 60–62 [in text mistakenly as pl. 37*, figs 34–36]. — Type locality: Collyhurst, near Manchester, England; magnesian marl [Manchester Marls Formation?]; E.W. Binney; Binney collection. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Rissoa obtusa* Cantraine, 1842, now known as *Obtusella intersecta* (S.V. Wood, 1857; *Rissoa*). — Current status: *Coelostylina* ? *obtusa* (T. Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 145, pl. 20, figs 8–9).

pucilla*, *Rissoa — T. Brown, 1841a: 63–64, pl. 6, figs 6–8;

1841-F: 79, 260 [Errata; changed to *R. pusilla*], “pl. 37*, figs 22–24” [Errata: should be pl. 21*, figs 41, 66–67], *non Rissoa pusilla* Grateloup, 1828, *nec* R. A. Philippi, 1836. — Type locality: Collyhurst, near Manchester, England; magnesian marl [Manchester Marls Formation?]; E.W. Binney; Binney collection. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Coelostylina* ? *leighi* (T. Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 143, pl. 20, figs 11–12).

Cerithiidae J. Fleming, 1822

triangularis*, *Murex — T. Brown, 1818b: 462, pl. 9, fig. 18. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Murex triangularis* Risso, 1826. — Current status: possible *Cerithium* species (herein).

Potamididae H. Adams & A. Adams, 1854

minutum*, *Cerithium — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 48, fig. 27; 1838-C2: 9, pl. 5, fig. 27, in synonymy with *Strombus turboformis* Montagu, 1808, in both editions. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: Montagu’s taxon is now regarded as a synonym of *Cerithideopsis costata* (da Costa, 1778; *Strombiformis*).

politus*, *Potamis — T. Brown, 1841-F: 67, pl. 37, fig. 21. — Type locality: Southfleet, Hamsey, Croydon, Kent & Charlton, England; plastic clay [Woolwich Formation?]. — Type age: Paleocene-Eocene (Thanetian-Ypresian). — Type material: not located. Brown quoted *Cerithium politus* “J. Sowerby” (1822: 50, pl. 339, fig. 3) in the *Mineral Conchology*, but the reference cited is instead labeled as a small variety of “*Potamides melanioides* (J. Sowerby, 1816; *Cerithium*)”, and there was no *Cerithium politus* in Sowerby. — Current status: perhaps synonym of *Potamides melanioides* (J. Sowerby, 1816).

Turritellidae Lovén, 1847

cingulata*, *Turritella — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 101, pl. 1, fig. 23, *non* G.B. Sowerby I, 1825, *nec* Grateloup 1832. — Type locality: Clay near Glasgow, Scotland; given by a workman to J. Smith. — Type age: unknown. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

pentangularis*, *Turbo — T. Brown, 1818a: 522–523, pl. 24, fig. 7. — Type locality: Dublin, Ireland; W. Turton. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Vermicularia lumbricalis* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Serpula*) (Turton 1819: xi; figured by B.M. Anderson & Allmon 2024: 25–26, text-figs 27–36).

phillipsii*, *Turritella — T. Brown, 1841-F: 70, pl. 38, fig. 4. New species based on *Turritella* sp. of J. Phillips (1835: 94,

pl. 2, fig. 38). — Type locality: Speeton, England; Speeton Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Early). — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: uncertain.

Capulidae J. Fleming, 1822

Piliopsis — T. Brown, 1849-F: 144. Subsequent incorrect spelling of *Pileopsis* Lamarck, 1822.

acuminata, Trichotropis — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 126, pl. 57, fig. 15, *ex* Jeffreys ms. — Type locality: Rothesay Bay, Scotland; dredged by James Smith; Oban, Argyleshire, Scotland; J. G. Jeffreys. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Published by Jeffreys himself only in 1867. — Current status: synonym of *Ariadnaria borealis* (Broderip & G.B. Sowerby I, 1829; *Trichotropis*) (MolluscaBase; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 135, pl. 107).

minutus, Pileopsis — T. Brown, 1841b: 223–224, pl. 7, figs 55–56; 1849-F: 256, pl. 21*, figs 55–57. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain, but too early to be Capulidae.

umbilicatus, Fusus — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 98–99, pl. 1, fig. 2, *ex* J. Smith ms. — Type locality: Rothesay Bay, Scotland; dredged by J. Smith. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Had been a *nomen nudum* in J. Smith, 1838 (p. 100). — Current status: synonym of *Ariadnaria borealis* (Broderip & G.B. Sowerby, 1829; *Trichotropis*) (E. A. Smith 1877: 136; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 135, pl. 107; Snyder 2022: 208).

Epitoniidae Berry, 1910 [1812]

aculeatus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1818b: 456, pl. 10, fig. 8 [mistakenly cited in the text as fig. 9], *non* Gmelin, 1791. — Type locality: “Left” bank of the Var, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary? — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Epitonium muricatum* (Risso, 1826; *Scalaria*) (van Aartsen 1996; Alf *et al.* 2020: 103, pl. 86).

Littorinidae Children, 1834

Neritoides — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 43, figs 14–15, 21–22 (just one species); 1844-C2: 25–26, *non* *Neritoides* Meuschen, 1779 [Naticidae]; Brown's Errata: synonymized with *Littorina*. Type species (M): *Nerita littoralis* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Turbo*). — Current status: synonym of *Littorina* Férussac, 1822, which has the same type species (ICZN Opinion 1159, 1980).

bartonensis, Littorina — T. Brown, 1841-F: 74, pl. 38, figs 54–55. New species based on *Turbo littoreus* Linnaeus,

1758, of J. Sowerby I (1814: 163, pl. 71, fig. 1 [upper set of figs]). — Type locality: Bramerton Hill, near Norwich, England; Crag [Norwich Crag Formation]. — Type age: Pleistocene (Early). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: synonym of *Littorina littorea* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Reid 1996: 95–100, text-figs 32–38; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 54; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107, pl. 90).

bifasciata, Phasianella — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 46, figs 44–45; 1838-C2: 10, pl. 10, figs 44–45. — Type locality: Portobello, Scotland; Bingham, on algae; Bingham coll. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Lacuna vincta* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 62–67, pl. 72, figs 10–12, pl. 74, figs 7–8, pl. 806, figs 6–8, pl. GG, fig. 4; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107, pl. 89).

communis, Littorina — T. Brown, 1841-F: 74, pl. 38, fig. 56. New species based on *Turbo littoreus* Linnaeus, 1758, of J. Sowerby I (1814: 163, pl. 71, fig. 1 [lower fig.]). — Type locality: Bramerton Hill, near Norwich, England; [Norwich] Crag Formation. — Type age: Pleistocene (Early). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: synonym of *Littorina littorea* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Turbo*) (Reid 1996: 95–100, text-figs 32–38; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 54; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107, pl. 90).

corneus, Phasianella — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 46, fig. 47; 1838-C2: 10, pl. 10, fig. 47. — Type locality: Portobello, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Lacuna vincta* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 62–67, pl. 72, figs 10–12, pl. 74, figs 7–8, pl. 806, figs 6–8, pl. GG, fig. 4; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107, pl. 90).

expansus, Turbo — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 101–102, pl. 1, figs 12–13, *ex* J. Smith ms; 1849-F: 254, pl. 33, figs 54–55. — Type locality: Dalmuir, on the Clyde, Scotland; J. Smith. — Type age: Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Littorina fabalis* (W. Turton, 1825; *Turbo*) (Reid 1996: 227–231, text-figs 82–88; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 54; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107, pl. 89).

glabrissimus, Nerita — T. Brown, 1818a: 532, pl. 24, fig. 12; 1827: iv, pl. 43, figs 9, 12; 1844-C2: 25, pl. 13, figs 9, 12, the last two as *Natica glabrissima*. — Type locality: Dublin Bay, Ireland; W. Turton. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possibly a *Lacuna* but a *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 345).

labiatus, Turbo — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 46, figs 20–21;

1838-C2: viii, 16, pl. 10, figs 20–21, *non* Montagu, 1803. — Type locality: Penzance, England; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Genus changed to *Littorina* in 1838 in Index [p. xiii] and Errata [p. 145]. — Current status: possible synonym of *Littorina arcana* Hannaford-Ellis, 1978 (Reid 1996: 264–267, text-figs 96–100).

montagui, *Lacuna* — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 128, pl. 57, fig. 8. — Type locality: Devon & Southampton, England. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Brown indicated that this had been mistaken for “*Lutea*” *lacuna* (Montagu, 1803; *Helix*). — Current status: synonym of *Lacuna puteolus* (Turton, 1819; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 58–60, pl. 72, figs 7–9, pl. 74, fig. 9), which is now a synonym of *Lacuna parva* (da Costa, 1778; *Cochlea*) (MolluscaBase; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 106–107, pl. 89).

neritiformia, *Littorina* — T. Brown, 1844; see: *neritiformis, Turbo*.

neritiformis, *Turbo* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 46, fig. 24; 1838-C2: 17, pl. 10, fig. 24; 1844-C2: 128, pl. 10, fig. 24, as *L. “neritiformia”*. — Type locality: Lough Strangford, Ireland, adhering to stones near Downpatrick. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: lost (Reid, 1996). — Current status: synonym of *Littorina obtusata* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Turbo*) (Reid 1996: 197–206, text-figs 76–81; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107–108, pls 91–92, 135).

retusa, *Lacuna* — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 128, pl. 10, figs 52–53. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Brown indicated that this is what he had illustrated in 1827 (pl. 46, figs 52–53) as *Lutea lacuna* (Montagu, 1803; *Helix*). — Current status: synonym of *Lacuna pallidula* (da Costa, 1778; *Cochlea*) (Jeffreys 1865: 353; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 106, pl. 89).

striatus, *Phasianella* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 46, fig. 49; 1838-C2: 10, pl. 10, fig. 49. St. — Type locality: St. Skae, Forfarshire, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Lacuna vincta* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 62–67, pl. 72, figs 10–12, pl. 74, figs 7–8, pl. 806, figs 6–8, pl. GG, fig. 4; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 107, pl. 90).

ventricosus, *Turbo* — T. Brown, 1838-C2: viii, 16, not figured; 1844-C2: Index [p. viii] and Errata [p. 145], changed to *Littorina, non Turbo ventricosus* S. Woodward, 1833. — Type locality: Clew Bay, Mayo, Ireland; James Macdonald. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Littorina saxatilis* (Olivi, 1792;

Turbo) (Jeffreys, 1865: 366), as synonym of *Littorina rudis* (Maton, 1797; *Turbo*), another synonym of *L. saxatilis*. — Current status: synonym of *Littorina saxatilis* (Olivi, 1792) (Reid 1996: 278–292, text-figs 101–111; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 108, pls 92–93).

Pomatiidae Newton, 1891 [1828]

bistriatus, *Cyclostoma* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 41, figs 29–30. — Type locality: none provided; John Trevelyan & Lady Jardine collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

marmorea, *Cyclostoma* — T. Brown, 1829: 12, pl. 1, figs 10–11; 1844-C2: 34, pl. 18, 2 figs 15. — Type locality: U.K.; James Gerard collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: probable synonym of *Pomatias elegans* (O.F. Müller, 1774; *Nerita*) (Forbes & Hanley 1852: 201–203, pl. 122, fig. 3, as *Cyclostoma*; Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 5–6).

Naticidae Guilding, 1834

Bulbus — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 103–104. Type species (M): *B. smithii* T. Brown, 1839. Genus and species had been *nomina nuda* in J. Smith (1839b: 119). — Current status: valid genus.

discrepans, *Natica* — T. Brown, 1843-F: 89, pl. 43, fig. 24. — Type locality: Bramerton, Norfolk, England; Suffolk crag [Norwich Crag Formation]. — Type age: Pleistocene (Early). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

smithii, *Bulbus* — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 104, pl. 1, fig. 18, *ex* Smith ms; 1849-F: 256, pl. 33*, fig. 77, as *Globulus*. — Type locality: Ardincaple near Helensburgh, Scotland; Lady John Campbell. — Type age: Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Bulbus smithii* T. Brown, 1839 (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 57–58; Torigoe & Inaba 2011: 5, pl. 1, fig. 1).

Newtoniellidae Korobkov, 1955

cancellatum, *Cerithium* — T. Brown, 1838-C2: 9, pl. 5, fig. 64, *non* Lamarck, 1804, *nec* Bronn, 1831. — Type locality: Holy Island, Northumberland, England. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. All preoccupied *Cerithium cancellatum* H. C. Lea, 1842, and of J. De C. Sowerby, 1850. — Current status: possible worn specimen of *Cerithium metula* Lovén, 1846 (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 198–199, pl. 91, figs 3–4), now *Cerithiella metula* (Lovén, 1846) (MolluscaBase).

Rissoidae J.E. Gray, 1847

Note: the Paleozoic species listed here certainly do not

belong in the Rissoidae, but it is difficult to assign them anywhere else at present.

Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv–v, pls 50–51 (many species); 1838-C2: 14–15; 1849-F: 254, *non* Röding, 1798 [Strombidae], *nec* Schumacher, 1817 [Trochidae]. — Type species (**SD herein**): *Turbo graphicus* T. Brown, 1818, a junior synonym of *Turbo trifasciata* J. Adams, 1800. — Current status: genus becomes a junior synonym of *Cingula* J. Fleming, 1818.

acuta, Rissoa — T. Brown, 1838-C2: viii, 11, pl. 9, figs 23–24, *non* Fréminville, 1814, *nec* Risso, 1826, *nec* J. De C. Sowerby, 1829. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. In his text, Brown indicated that this is what he had treated in his first edition as *Pyramis labiosus* “Maton & Racket” [Montagu, 1803; *Helix*]. By the time of his 1844 Index [p. viii] and Errata [p. 145], he had decided that this was instead a synonym of *Rissoa marginata* “Montagu”. — Current status: presumably a synonym of *Pusillina marginata* (Michaud, 1830; *Rissoa*; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 121, pl. 98).

acutissimus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 36; 1838-C2: 15, pl. 9, fig. 36. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Belton sands; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Aclis ascaris* (W. Turton, 1819; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 219–220, pl. 88, fig. 8), now *Alvania ascaris* (W. Turton, 1819) (MolluscaBase; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovalini 2011: 169).

albus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 75; 1838-C2: 11. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Belton sands; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. *Rissoa candida* T. Brown, 1838, replacement name. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 146).

approximus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 42; 1838-C2: 12, pl. 9, fig. 42, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Belton sands; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Alvania punctura* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 89–91, pl. 80, figs 8–9, as *Rissoa*; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 116, pl. 96).

binghami, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 29; 1838-C2: 10, pl. 9, fig. 29, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Peterhead, Saint Fergus Bay, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 146).

candida, Rissoa — T. Brown, 1838-C2: 11, pl. 9, fig. 75. —

Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Belton sands; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. Evidently intended as a replacement name for *Rissoa alba* (T. Brown, 1827; *Pyramis*), *non* *Rissoa alba* (J. Adams, 1797; *Turbo*), which he had treated on p. 12 [not noting that the latter was also a primary junior homonym in *Turbo: non* Pennant, 1777]. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 146).

candidus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 31; 1838-C2: 14, pl. 9, fig. 31. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Belton sands, Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Onoba semicostata* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (MolluscaBase; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 120, pl. 98).

decussatus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 57. — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Onoba semicostata* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 63; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 120, pl. 98).

discors, Turbo — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 5. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Alvania discors* (T. Brown, 1818) (Tabanelli *et al.* 2020: 25–26, text-fig. 21; Alf *et al.* 2020: 113, pl. 95).

discors, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 32; 1838-C2: 14, pl. 9, fig. 32. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Onoba semicostata* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 63; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 120, pl. 98).

discrepans, Turbo — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 4. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Alvania discors* (T. Brown, 1818) (MolluscaBase; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 113, pl. 95).

fallax, Rissoa — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 102, pl. 1, figs 7–8, *ex* J. Smith ms. — Type locality: Portrush, Northern Ireland; J. Smith. — Type age: unknown. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

fuscatus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 72; 1844-C2: 10–11, pl. 9, fig. 72. — Type locality: Port Seaton, England; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possible synonym of *Rissoa parva* (da Costa, 1778; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 98–100, pl. 76, figs 2, 6, pl. 77, figs 6–7,

- pl. 82, figs 1–4; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 123, pl. 99).
- graphicus, Turbo** — T. Brown, 1818a: 521–522, pl. 24, fig. 6; 1827: pl. 50, fig. 83; 1838-C2: 12–13, pl. 9, fig. 83. — Type locality: Dublin, Ireland; W. Turton; Turton collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Cingula trifasciata* (J. Adams, 1800; *Turbo*) (MolluscaBase; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 118, pl. 97).
- minutus, Turbo** — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 13. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Turbo minutus* Michaud, 1828, and of Totten, 1834. — Current status: synonym of *Crisilla semistriata* (Montagu, 1808; *Turbo*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 118, pl. 97), but possibly *C. beniamina* (Monterosato, 1884) (Alf *et al.* 2020: 118, pl. 97).
- obtusus, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, figs 27–28; 1838-C2: 10, pl. 9, figs 27–28. — Type locality: Peterhead, Saint Fergus Bay, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.
- oweni, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1841b: 223, pl. 7, figs 44–45; 1849-F: 254, pl. 21*, figs 44–45. — Type locality: Crimsworth Dean near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.
- pullus, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, fig. 25; 1838-C2: 13, pl. 8, fig. 25, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Holy Island, England; T. Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possible synonym of *Rissoa membranacea* (J. Adams, 1800; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 109–117, pl. 76, fig. 5, pl. 77, figs 1–3, pl. 81, fig. 3, as *Rissoa labiosa* Montagu, 1803; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 123, pl. 99).
- pusilla, Rissoa** — see: *pucilla, Rissoa*.
- reticulatus, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1841b: 222–223, pl. 7, figs 42–43; 1849-F: 254, pl. 21*, figs 42–43. — Type locality: Crimsworth Dean near Hebden Bridge, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.12044, holotype. — Current status: *Rhabdospira reticulata* (T. Brown, 1841) (Jackson 1952: 58).
- similis, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, fig. 20; 1838-C2: 13, pl. 8, fig. 20. — Type locality: Padstow Harbor, England; Rev. W. Molesworth; Goodall collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possible synonym of *Rissoa membranacea* (J. Adams, 1800; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 109–117, pl. 76, fig. 5, pl. 77, figs 1–3, pl. 81, fig. 3, as *Rissoa labiosa* Montagu, 1803; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 123, pl. 99).
- tigerina, Trochus** — T. Brown, 1818b: 464, pl. 10, fig. 11, non *Trochus merula tigrinus* Dillwyn, 1817. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Alvania* sp., possible synonym of *Alvania cimex* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Turbo*) (herein; species figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 112, pl. 95), or *A. mamillata* Risso, 1826 (Alf *et al.* 2020: 115, pl. 96).
- turgida, Turbo** — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 3. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possibly synonym of *Rissoa parva* (da Costa, 1778; *Turbo*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 123, pl. 99).
- turriculus, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 18; 1844-C2: 10; 1838-C2: 10, pl. 9, fig. 18, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Devon, England; Goodall; Goodall collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 146).
- verrucosus, Turbo** — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 12, non Gmelin, 1791, nec Röding, 1798. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possibly an *Alvania*.

Rissoinidae Stimpson, 1865

- pyramidillus, Pyramis** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 63, in synonymy with *Helix decussatus* Montagu, 1803; 1838-C2: 11, pl. 9, fig. 63, as *Rissoa*. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Zebinella decussata* (Montagu, 1803; *Helix*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 147–148).

Zebinidae Coan, 1964

- bryerii, Nassa** — T. Brown, 1838-C2: 5. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Schwartziella bryerea* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*), a western Atlantic species.
- bryerium, Buccinum** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 49, fig. 26. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Schwartziella bryerea* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*), a western Atlantic species.

Bithyniidae J.E. Gray, 1857

- Bithiana** — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 135. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Bithynia* Leach, 1818.
- ventricosa, Paludina** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 41, figs 74–

75; 1838-C2: pl. 14, figs 74–75; 1841-C2: 27, 1844-C2: ix. — Type locality: River Thames, Westminster, England; marshy ditches. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Bithynia leachii* (Sheppard, 1823; *Turbo*) (Kennard & Woodward 1926: 17–18; Vinarski & Kantor 2016: 201; Rowson *et al.* 2021: 106–107, discussed and figured but without synonymy).

Rissoellidae J.E. Gray, 1850

Note: some authors have listed *Pyramis glabrus* T. Brown, 1827, as the type species of *Rissoella* J.E. Gray, 1847, but this species remains a *nomen dubium* (here listed in the Pyramidellidae). The type species of *Rissoella* is actually *Rissoa diaphana* Alder, 1848; SD [Art. 70.3] (Petit 2012: 101).

Caecidae J.E. Gray, 1850

Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, figs 3, 6, 9–13 (7 species); 1844-C2: 124–125, pl. 124. Type species (**SD herein**): *Brochus striatus* T. Brown, 1827, a probable synonym of *Caecum trachea* (Montagu, 1803; *Dentalium*), the type species of *Caecum*. — Current status: synonym of *Caecum* J. Fleming, 1813.

Cornuoides — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, figs 49–50 (2 species); 1844-C2: 125. Type species: never designated. — Current status: *nomen dubium*, either based on young *Caecum* or a *Strebloceras* P.P. Carpenter, 1859.

annulatus, Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 12; 1844-C2: 125, pl. 56, fig. 12. — Type locality: Lough Strangford, Ireland; Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Caecum annulatum* (T. Brown, 1827) (P.P. Carpenter 1858: 423–424), preoccupying *Caecum annulatum* Emmons, 1858.

laevis, Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 6; 1844-C2: 125, pl. 56, fig. 6, in synonymy with *Dentalium imperforatum* “Montagu” [Kanmacher, 1798], but a “dubious synonym” (1827). — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Caecum trachea* (Montagu, 1803; *Dentalium*), species figured by Alf *et al.* (2020: 129, pl. 101).

major, Cornuoides — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 49; 1844-C2: 125, pl. 56, fig. 49. — Type locality: none provided in 1827; Sandwich, England; in sand; Mr. Walker. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Brown indicated that J. Fleming (1813: pl. 205, fig. 8) had figured this species without a caption, from whom Brown had evidently copied the image. There had also been an image in the earlier, unavailable Boys & Walker (1784: pl. 1, fig. 11 [mistakenly in Brown as “14”], as

“*Serpula recta*...”). — Current status: *nomen dubium*, perhaps based on a young *Caecum* or on a *Strebloceras* P.P. Carpenter, 1859.

minor, Cornuoides — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 50; 1844-C2: 125, pl. 56, fig. 50. — Type locality: none provided in 1827; Sandwich, England; in sand; Mr. Walker. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Brown indicated that J. Fleming (1813: pl. 205, fig. 9) had figured this species without a caption, from whom Brown had evidently copied the image. There had also been an image in the earlier, unavailable Boys & Walker (1784: pl. 1, fig. 12, as “*Serpula recta*...”). — Current status: *nomen dubium*, perhaps based on a young *Caecum* or a *Strebloceras* P.P. Carpenter, 1859.

reticulatus, Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 11; 1844-C2: 124–125, pl. 56, fig. 11. — Type locality: Killlough, County Down, Ireland; Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Caecum annulatum* (T. Brown, 1827) (P.P. Carpenter 1858: 423–424), species figured by Alf *et al.* (2020: 129, pl. 101).

striatus, Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 13; 1844-C2: 123, pl. 46, fig. 13. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Caecum trachea* (Montagu, 1803; *Dentalium*) (P.P. Carpenter 1858: 414) (species figured by Alf *et al.* (2020: 129, pl. 101)).

tracheiformis, Brochus — see: *trachiformis, Brochus*.

trachiformis, Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata], pl. 1, fig. 10; 1833: 158, pl. 19, fig. 25, as B. “*tracheiformis*”; 1844-C2: 124, pl. 56, fig. 10. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: subsequent invalid emendation of *Caecum trachea* (Montagu, 1803; *Dentalium*) (P.P. Carpenter 1858: 414; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovini 2011: 211).

arcuatus, Brochus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 1, fig. 9; 1844-C2: 125, pl. 56, fig. 9. Bear Haven, Bantry Bay, Ireland; General Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Caecum glabrum* (Montagu, 1803; *Dentalium*) (P.P. Carpenter 1858: 435–436). *Ditrypa arcuata* T. Brown, 1827 (Mörch 1863: 425). — Current status: synonym of *Ditrypa arietina* (O.F. Müller, 1776; *Dentalium*) (Hartman 1959: 569) [Annelida].

Iravadiidae Thiele, 1928

crystallinus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 76;

1838-C2: 13, pl. 9, fig. 76, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Tenby, Wales; George Lyons; Lyons collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: TENBM-1983.4329/1-5, 5 possible syntypes; -1983.4329, 12 possible syntypes. — Current status: synonym of *Hyala vitrea* (Montagu, 1803) (Oliver *et al.* 2020: 27, fig. 14; species figured by Alf *et al.*, 2020: 128, pl. 102).

virginea, *Rissoa* — T. Brown, 1838-C2: viii, 13, pl. 9, fig. 82. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Ceratia proxima* (Forbes & Hanley, 1850, *ex* Alder ms) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 127, pl. 75, figs 7–8; species figured by Alf *et al.* (2020: 127, pl. 102), the type species (M) of *Ceratia* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1852) (species name conserved under ICZN Code Art. 23.9). Concerning this species, see Ponder (1984: 52–54, text-fig. 18A–D).

Tornidae Sacco, 1896 [1884]

rugosus, *Trochus* — T. Brown, 1818a: 520, pl. 24, fig. 5; 1827: pl. 51, figs 16–17; 1838-C2: 18, pl. 11, figs 30–31, the latter two as a synonym of *Trochus subcarinatus* (Montagu, 1803; *Helix*). — Type locality: Portmarnock, Ireland; W. Turton. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tornus subcarinatus* (Montagu, 1803) (species figured by Alf *et al.*, 2020: 129, pl. 102).

Planaxidae J.E. Gray, 1850

Note: the genus *Fissilabia* has been sometimes attributed to T. Brown. The article describing it was unsigned and has since been attributed to MacGillivray (1836) (Iredale 1911: 259).

Eratoidea Gill, 1871

laevis, *Columbella* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, fig. 15; 1838-C2: 4, pl. 10, fig. 15, in synonymy with *Cypraea voluta* Montagu, 1803, in both editions. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Erato voluta* (Montagu, 1803) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 140, pl. 109).

Velutinidae J.E. Gray, 1840

undata, *Velutina* — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 102–103, pl. 1, fig. 15, *ex* J. Smith ms; 1849-F: 255, pl. 33*, fig. 80. — Type locality: Dalmeir, Scotland; J. Smith. — Type age: Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. Mistakenly listed as the senior synonym of the type species of *Limneria* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1851, by Wenz (1940: 956). — Current status: *Limneria undata* (T. Brown, 1839) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 102).

Aporrhaidae J.E. Gray, 1850

fittoni, *Rostellaria* — T. Brown, 1839-F: 54, pl. 33, fig. 15. New species based on *Rostellaria parkinsoni* Mantell, 1822, as figured by J. De C. Sowerby, 1827 (p. 112, pl. 558, fig. 3 [lower of two images]). — Type locality: Faversham, England. — Type age: Eocene (Ypresian?). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: synonym of *Aporrhais sowerbii* (J. Fleming, 1828; *Rostellaria*) (U. Wieneke pers. comm., September 19, 2025).

Xenophoridae Troschel, 1852 [1840]

mantelli, *Trochus* — T. Brown, 1841-F: 75, pl. 39, fig. 11. New species based on *Trochus agglutinans* Lamarck, 1804, of J. Sowerby (1813: 223–224, pl. 98, smaller two of the four figures) (cited by T. Brown as “pl.” 223); and as *Trochus umbilicaris* Linnaeus, 1758, of Solander (1766: 10, pl. 1, figs 4–5). — Type locality: Barton Cliff, Hamsey, Sussex, England; [Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — Type material: would be Sowerby's or Solander's material. — Current status: an uncertain *Xenophora*.

Granulinidae G.A. Covert & H.K. Covert, 1995

quadruplicata, *Voluta* — T. Brown, 1818b: 461, pl. 9, fig. 14. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Granulina*, perhaps closest to *G. marginata* (Bivona, 1832; *Volvaria*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 208, pl. 170).

Eulimidae R.A. Philippi, 1853

glaber, *Turbo* — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 2. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Eulima*, perhaps closest to *E. glabra* (da Costa, 1778; *Strombiformis*), which may have been what Brown intended, although he made no mention of da Costa and presented it as if it were a new species; species figured in Alf *et al.* (2020: 138, pl. 108).

minor, *Turritella* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, figs 57–58; 1838-C2: 9, pl. 8, figs 57–58. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: TENB.1983.4325, 4 syntypes. — Current status: *Aclis minor* (T. Brown, 1827) (Alf *et al.* 2020: 129, pl. 109; Oliver *et al.* 2020: 26–27, fig. 13).

nitidus, *Pyramis* — T. Brown, 1843b: 46, pl. 5, fig. 28. — Type locality: British seas. — Type age: Recent & Holo-

cene. — Type material: not located. — Current status: probable Eulimidae but status uncertain.

Cancellariidae Forbes & Hanley, 1851

minuta, *Cancellaria* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 253, pl. 33*, fig. 73, *non* Nyst, 1845. Both preoccupy the *Cancellaria minuta* Sandberger, 1859. — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: fossil, but no age provided. — Type material: not located. Listed by Petit & Harasewych (2005: 71). — Current status: uncertain.

Buccinidae Rafinesque, 1815

acutissimum, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1836a: 58, 1 fig. — Type locality: “Orkney” [west coast of Shetland, Norwegian Sea, July 1826]; William Nicol collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: NMS.Z.1959.43.12701, possible holotype. — Current status: synonym of *Buccinum undatum* Linnaeus, 1758, the type species (SD Montfort, 1810) of *Buccinum* Linnaeus, 1758 (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 167, pl. 137).

babylonicus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 127, pl. 57, fig. 19. — Type locality: Strand near Hull, England; T. Brown; Thomas Norris collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Variety of *Fusus antiquus* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Murex*) (Jeffreys, 1867: 325). — Current status: synonym of *Neptunea antiqua* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fraussen & Terryn 2007: 78–85, pls 46–55, text-figs 42–44; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 171, pls 140–141; Snyder 2022: 26).

elegans, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1841b: 221–222, pl. 7, figs 50–51, *non* J. De C. Sowerby, 1824; *nec* Risso, 1826, *nec* Kiener, 1834, *nec* Dujardin, 1837; *nec* Reeve, 1843. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

elongatum, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1836a: 58, 1 fig, *non* W. Wood, 1828. — Type locality: “Orkney” [west coast of Shetland, Norwegian Sea, July 1826]; William Nicol collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: NMS.Z.1959.43.12701, possible holotype. — Current status: synonym of *Buccinum undatum* Linnaeus, 1758, the type species (SD Montfort, 1810) of *Buccinum* Linnaeus, 1758 (MolluscaBase; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 167, pl. 137).

flemingii, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1841b: 222, pl. 7, fig. 52; 1849-F: 251–252, pl. 21*, fig. 52. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10232, holotype (Bolton 1893:

14; Jackson 1952: 53). — Current status: uncertain.

gibsoni, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1841b: 221, pl. 7, figs 48–49; 1849-F: 251, pl. 20*, figs 48–49. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shales. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

manni, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1841-F: 61, pl. 36, figs 20–21. New species based on *Murex rugosus* Parkinson, 1811 [itself *non* Born, 1778], as figured by J. Sowerby (1818: 225, pl. 199, figs 1–2). Brown incorrectly cited Sowerby’s plate as “190”. — Type locality: Plumstead, England; Crag. — Type age: Plio-Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. Snyder (2022: 125) misinterpreted this as a replacement name (and confused it with *Fusus parkinsonii* T. Brown, 1841). — Current status: *Searlesia manni* (T. Brown, 1841) (Snyder 2022).

manni, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1841b: 221, pl. 7, figs 53–54; 1849-F: 251, pl. 21*, figs 53–54. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10233, holotype (Bolton 1893: 14; Jackson 1952: 53–54). — Current status: uncertain.

parkinsonii, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1841-F: 61, pl. 36, fig. 17. New species based on *Murex rugosus* Parkinson, 1811 [itself *non* Born, 1778], as figured by Parkinson (1833: 64, pl. 5, fig. 16). — Type locality: Essex, England; Crag. — Type age: Plio-Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. Misinterpreted by Snyder (2022: 148) as a replacement name. — Current status: uncertain.

sigmiliniatus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1841: 63, pl. 35, fig. 11. — Current status: subsequent invalid emendation of *Buccinum sigmilineum* J. Phillips, 1836 (p. 230, pl. 16, fig. 12) from the Jurassic of England.

anglicanum, *Buccinum* — “T. Brown”, 1827-C1: pl. 49, fig. 11. Brown has been credited with this name (as for example: Kantor & Sysoev, 2005: 127), but it originated with Lamarck (1822: 264), which was a subsequent spelling of *Buccinum anglicum* Gmelin, 1791. — Current status: all are synonyms of *Buccinum undatum* Linnaeus, 1758, the type species (SD Montfort, 1810) of *Buccinum* Linnaeus, 1758.

Chauvetiidae Kantor *et al.*, 2021

subnigeris, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 58–59; 1844-C2: 7, as *F. subnigris*. — Type locality: St. Cyrus, Scotland; T. Brown; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Chauvetia brunnea* (Donovan, 1804;

Buccinum) (Bucquoy *et al.* 1883: 112; Snyder 2022: 191; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 167, pl. 137).

subnigris, *Fusus* — see: *subnigeris*, *Fusus*.

Columbellidae Swainson, 1840

Cominia — T. Brown, 1839-C2: 22. Type species (M): *Voluta hyalina* Montagu, 1808. Montagu's original specimen may have been a juvenile columbellid (MolluscaBase). — Current status: uncertain.

cingillus, *Conus* — T. Brown, 1838-F: 44, pl. 30, fig. 8. New species based on one of the four figures of *Conus dormitor* Solander, 1766, by J. Sowerby (1821: 179–180, pl. 301, fig. 1). — Type locality: Barton, Hamsey, Sussex, England; Miss Dent; [Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material, the figure of which was designated lectotype by Kohn (1992). — Current status: possibly Columbellidae (Kohn 1992: 270).

leathesii, *Buccinum* — T. Brown, 1838-F: 51, pl. 32, fig. 28. New species based on *Buccinum sulcatum* J. Sowerby, 1822 (p. 103, pl. 375, fig. 2), as figured by J. De C. Sowerby (1824: 122, pl. 477, fig. 4). J. Sowerby's original species was a junior homonym twice over: *non* Born, 1778, *nec* Bruguière, 1792. — Type locality: Suffolk, England; Crag [Coralline or Red Crag Formation]. — Type age: Pliocene-Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. Brown's species is the type species (OD) of *Striomitrella* U. S. Grant & Gale, 1931, now regarded as a synonym of *Mitrella* Risso, 1826. — Current status: *Mitrella leathesii* (T. Brown, 1838) (MolluscaBase).

nebulosa, *Voluta* — T. Brown, 1818b: 461, pl. 9, fig. 16. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Mitrella*, perhaps closest to *Mitrella scripta* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Murex*) (herein; figured by Alf *et al.* 2020: 178, pl. 148).

sedgwickii, *Melanopsis* — T. Brown, 1843-F: 95, pl. 45, fig. 6. New species based on one of the seven figures of *Melanopsis fusiformis* J. De C. Sowerby, 1826 (p. 36, pl. 332, fig. 1). — Type locality: Isle of Wight, England; upper marine formation [Bouldnor Formation?]; Sedgwick or G.B. Sowerby I. — Type age: Oligocene. — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: possibly Columbellidae.

Fasciolaridae J.E. Gray, 1853

rufus, *Fusus* — “T. Brown”, 1827-C1: pl. 48, figs 47–48. This has been listed as a species by Brown, but Brown cited *Murex rufus* Montagu, 1803, which is now *Prope-*

bela rufa (Montagu, 1803) [Mangeliidae]. This is thus a misidentification by Brown, not a separate species.

Nassariidae Iredale, 1916 [1835]

breve, *Turbo* — T. Brown, 1818b: 463, pl. 10, fig. 10. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Tritia*, species uncertain.

subglobosa, *Voluta* — T. Brown, 1818b: 461, pl. 10, fig. 14. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possibly a juvenile *Demoulia*, but uncertain.

Pisaniidae J.E. Gray, 1857

dentatus, *Murex* — T. Brown, 1818b: 462, pl. 10, fig. 1, *non* Burrow, 1815. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. Both preoccupy *Murex dentatus* Anton, 1839, a synonym of *Muricopsis cristata* (Brocchi, 1814; *Murex*). — Current status: perhaps closest to *Enginella leucozona* (R. A. Philippi, 1844; *Buccinum*) (figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 174, pl. 145).

Muricidae Rafinesque, 1815

asperrimus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 47, fig. 2, *ex* Leach ms; 1838-C2: 8, pl. 6, fig. 2. — Type locality: Dorset, England; “British Museum” collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus asperrimus* Millet, 1865, a synonym of *Muricopsis cristata* (Brocchi, 1814; *Fusus*). Listed by Snyder (2022: 29). — Current status: synonym of *Trophonopsis muricata* (Montagu, 1803; *Murex*) (Houart 1981: 13, as *T. “asperimus”*; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 202, pl. 167).

bullatus, *Pyrula* — T. Brown, 1839-F: 59, pl. 34, fig. 21. New species based on *Murex smithii* var. β of J. De C. Sowerby, 1827 (p. 151, pl. 578, fig. 3). — Type locality: Maida Hill, Paddington, England; London Clay [Formation]; G. A. Mantell collection. — Type age: Eocene (Ypresian). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: *Priscoficus* ?.

carinata, *Purpura* — T. Brown, 1838-F: 52, pl. 32, figs 41–42, *non* Schubert & Wagner, 1829. New species based on one of three figures *Buccinum crispatum* J. De C. Sowerby, 1823 (p. 12, pl. 413, fig. 2). — Type locality: Norfolk & Suffolk, England; Crag. — Type age: Pliocene-Pleistocene. — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. Sowerby's species itself was a junior homonym: *non* Dillwyn, 1817, *ex* Chemnitz ms. — Current status: as with Sowerby's species, possible synonym of *Nucella*

lapillus (Linnaeus, 1758; *Buccinum*)

craticulatus, Murex — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, fig. 60, *non* Linnaeus, 1758. — Type locality: Holy Island, England; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. This was indicated as a new species, and his image is very different than images of *Murex craticulatus* Linnaeus, 1758, now *Turritatus craticulatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) [Fascioliidae]. — Current status: uncertain; figure not close to any native muricid and not mentioned in subsequent literature.

dentii, Purpura — T. Brown, 1838-F: 52, pl. 32, figs 5–6. New species based on the “larger” [two] of three figures of *Buccinum desertum* Solander, 1766, in J. De C. Sowerby (1823: 14, pl. 415, figs 1). — Type locality Barton Cliff, Hamsey, Sussex, England; blue clay [Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

fittoni, Pyrula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 252, pl. 33*, figs 32–33. Replacement name for *Pyrula smithii* J. De C. Sowerby, 1836 (p. 336, pl. 11, fig. 15), *non* *Pyrula smithii* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1827; *Murex*), which Brown (1839-F: 59, pl. 34, figs 26–27) also placed under *Pyrula*. — Type locality: Cape Point, near Folkestone, Kent, England; the Gault [Gault Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: would be that of Sowerby. Brown did not know that Sowerby’s 1836 name was also a junior primary homonym. *non* *Pyrula smithii* I. Lea, 1833. — Current status: uncertain.

heywoodii, Fusus — T. Brown, 1841-F: 62, pl. 36, figs 13–14. New species based on *Murex peruvianus* Lamarck, 1816, as figured by J. De C. Sowerby, 1823 (p. 47, pl. 434, fig. 1). — Type locality: Woodbridge, Suffolk, England; Mrs. Cobbold; Crag [Red Crag Formation]. — Type age: Pliocene-Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. Misinterpreted as a replacement name by Snyder (2022: 100), who noted earlier references to it as a synonym of *Fusus scalariformis* A.A. Gould, 1839. — Current status: synonym of *Boreotrophon clathratus* (Linnaeus, 1767; *Murex*), the type species (M) of *Boreotrophon* P. Fischer, 1884. Species figured in Alf *et al.* (2020: 192–193, pl. 158).

gyrinus, Fusus — “T. Brown”, 1827-C1: pl. 48, figs 12–13. This has been listed as a Brown species in the synonymy of *Ocenebrina aciculata* (Lamarck, 1822; *Murex*), but Brown cited *Murex gyrinus* “Montagu”, and Montagu (1808: 170) cited *Murex gyrinus* Linnaeus, 1758, now regarded as *Gyrineum gyrinus* (Linnaeus, 1758) [Cymatiidae]. Listed by Snyder (2022: 96). This is thus a misiden-

tification by Brown, not a separate taxon.

imbricatus, Fusus — J. Smith, 1839a: 101, *ex* T. Brown *ms*, *nomen nudum*, in synonymy with *Fusus peruvianus* (Lamarck, 1816; *Murex*). Listed by Snyder (2022: 103). — Current status: could be listed in the synonymy of *Trophon geversianus* (Pallas, 1774; *Buccinum*).

Costellariidae MacDonald, 1860

triplicatus, Murex — T. Brown, 1818b: 462, pl. 9, fig. 19. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Ebenomitra*, possibly small *E. ebenus* (Lamarck, 1811) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 205, pl. 169, as *Pusia*).

Conidae J. Fleming, 1822

bartonensis, Conus — T. Brown, 1838-F: 44, pl. 30, figs 9, 11. New species based on one set of four figures of *Conus scabriculus* Solander 1766, in J. Sowerby, 1821 (p. 180, pl. 303, figs 2, var. β). — Type locality: Barton, Hamsey, Sussex, England; clay [Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — Type material: NHMUK PI-OR-43819, lectotype (Kohn 1992: 270). — Current status: synonym of *Conus scabriculus* Solander, in Brander, 1766 (Kohn 1992: 270, text-figs 538–539).

highgatensis, Conus — T. Brown, 1838-F: 44, pl. 30, figs 4–5. New species based on one of the two original figures of *Conus concinnus* J. Sowerby, 1821 (p. 180, pl. 302, fig. 1). — Type locality: Highgate Hill; London Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Ypresian). — Type material: Sowerby’s specimen, NHMUK PI-OR-43820, was designated lectotype by Kohn (1992). — Current status: synonym of *Conus concinnus* J. Sowerby, 1821 (Kohn 1992: 270).

Fusiturridae Abdelkrim *et al.*, 2018

sutura, Murex — T. Brown, 1818b: 455–456, pl. 10, fig. 6 [mistakenly cited in text as fig. 7]. — Type locality: Left bank of the Var, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Fusiturris*, species uncertain.

Mangeliidae P. Fischer, 1883

albus, Fusus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, fig. 62; 1838-C2: 7, pl. 5, figs 61–62. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus albus* Forbes, 1847, and of R. A. Philippi, 1852. — Current status: synonym of *Propebela rufa* (Montagu, 1803; *Murex*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 454–458, pl. 112, figs

- 3–5, pl. TT, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 167, pl. 221–222, pl. 180; Snyder 2022: 21).
- castaneus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 43–44. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus castaneus* Mörch, 1858, which is still in use in the northwestern Pacific, now *Volutopsius castaneus* (Mörch, 1858); **herein we propose *Volutopsius golikovi* Coan & Goodwin, as its replacement name**; named for the prominent Russian malacologist Aleksandr N. Golikov (1931–2010), for his work on the Russian Pacific gastropods. — Current status: synonym of *Propebela rufa* (Montagu, 1803; *Murex*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 454–458, pl. 112, figs 3–5, pl. TT, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 221–222, pl. 180; Snyder 2022: 49).
- cranchii, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, fig. 5. — Type locality: Devon coast, England; Leach & NHMUK collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Propebela rufa* (Montagu, 1803; *Murex*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 454–458, pl. 112, figs 3–5, pl. TT, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 221–222, pl. 180; Snyder 2022: 60).
- crassus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 8–9; 1838-C2: 7, pl. 5, figs 37–38. — Type locality: Prestons, Scotland; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus crassus* R. A. Philippi, 1887, and of Pallary, 1902. Synonym of “*Pleurotoma costata* Donovan” (Jeffreys 1867: 379–381). Listed by Snyder 2022: 61). — Current status: thus, now probable synonym of *Mangelia costata* (Pennant, 1777; *Murex*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 219–220, pl. 179).
- decussatus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 53, 55; 1838-C2: 7, pl. 5, figs 53, 55. — Type locality: Killough, Ireland; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus decussatus* I. Lea, 1833, and of Deshayes, 1835, and of Pictet & Roux, 1849. Synonymy of *Pleurotoma trevillianum* W. Turton, 1834 (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 452–454, pl. 112, figs 1–2), but given the relative dates, it would have to be the other way around. Listed by Snyder (2022: 68). — Current status: *Curtitoma decussata* (T. Brown, 1827).
- discors, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 6–7. — Type locality: Portobello, Scotland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Propebela rufa* (Montagu, 1803) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 454–458, pl. 112, figs 3–5, pl. TT, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 221–222, pl. 180; Snyder 2022: 71).
- discrepans, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 49–50. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Propebela rufa* (Montagu, 1803) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 454–458, pl. 112, figs 3–5, pl. TT, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 221–222, pl. 180; Snyder 2022: 72).
- elegans, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 47, fig. 3, *ex* Leach ms; 1838-C2: 8, pl. 6, fig. 3. — Type locality: Devon coast, England. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: NHMUK collection, not located. Preoccupies *Fusus elegans* J.E. Gray, 1838, and of Reeve, 1848. — Current status: synonym of *Smithiella costulata* (Risso, 1826; *Mangelia*) (Jeffreys 1867: 376–377; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 220, pl. 179, as *Mangelia*; Snyder 2022: 76; Spada *et al.* 2023: 44–46, text-fig. 23, the latter without synonymy).
- fasciatus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 41–42, *non* Röding, 1798. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Both preoccupy *Fusus fasciatus* Wolff, 1897. Synonym of “*Pleurotoma costata* Donovan” (Jeffreys, 1867: 379–381). — Current status: thus, now probable synonym of *Mangelia costata* (Pennant, 1777; *Murex*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 219–220, pl. 179; Snyder 2022: 81).
- fuscus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 3–4. — Type locality: Killinchy & Lough Strangford, Ireland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Propebela rufa* (Montagu, 1803; *Murex*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 454–458, pl. 112, figs 3–5, pl. TT, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 221–222, pl. 180; Snyder 2022: 87).
- minimus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 35–36. — Type locality: Holy Island, England; T. Brown; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of “*Pleurotoma costata* Donovan” (Jeffreys 1867: 379–381). — Current status: thus, now probable synonym of *Mangelia costata* (Pennant, 1777; *Murex*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 219–220, pl. 179; Snyder 2022: 131).
- pyramidatus, *Fusus*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 19–20; 1838-C2: 6–7, pl. 5, figs 19–20. — Type locality: St. Abbs Head, Scotland; T. Brown; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Mangelia striolata* Risso, 1826, the type species (SD J.E. Gray 1847) of *Mangelia* Risso, 1826 (Bucquoy *et al.* 1883: 99; species figured in Alf *et al.*

2020: 220, pl. 179; Spada *et al.* 2023: 3–6, fig. 2, without synonymy; Snyder 2022: 162).

reticulata, *Pleurotoma* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 29–30; 1838-C2: 8, pl. 5, figs 19–30. — Type locality: Rowe, Scotland [locality not identified]; Stewart Ker; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Pleurotoma reticulata* O. G. Costa, 1844. — Current status: perhaps this should now be *Curtitoma reticulata* (T. Brown, 1827) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 150, but as a synonym of the later *C. treveliana* (W. Turton, 1834; *Pleurotoma*)).

Mitromorphidae Casey, 1904

acuta, *Voluta* — T. Brown, 1818b: 461, pl. 9, fig. 17. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Voluta acuta* Risso, 1826, of Defrance, 1829, and of J. De C. Sowerby, 1832. — Current status: possibly a juvenile *Mitromorpha* (herein).

punctata, *Voluta* — T. Brown, 1818b: 461, pl. 9, fig. 15, “non Solander”, but that is a *nomen nudum*. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Voluta punctata* Swainson, 1823, of Risso, 1826, and of W. Wood, 1828. — Current status: possibly senior synonym of *Mitromorpha columbellaria* (Scacchi, 1836; *Mitra*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 216, pl. 178).

Raphitomidae Bellardi, 1875

boothii, *Fusus* — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 98, pl. 1, fig. 1; 1844-C2: 127, pl. 57, fig. 12, *ex* J. Smith ms. — Type locality: Rothesay Bay, Scotland; dredged by J. Smith. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. This had been a *nomen nudum* in J. Smith (1838: 100). Listed by Snyder (2022: 38). — Current status: synonym of *Leufroyia concinna* (Scacchi, 1836; *Pleurotoma*) (Høisæter 2016: 25–27, text-figs 2F, 3D, 21–23).

lineatus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 1–2; 1838-C2: 6, pl. 5, figs 1–2. — Type locality: Ireland; Dr. Drummond; Leach & NHMUK collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus lineatus* Menke, 1829, of Quoy & Gaimard, 1833, and of de Koninck, 1833 (this junior homonym was renamed *Fusus multisulcatus* Nyst, 1845), and of Dickerson, 1913 (this junior homonym renamed *Fusinus obtentus* Hanna, 1924). Synonym of *Mangelia lineolata* Risso, 1826 (Jeffreys 1867: 381; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovini 2011: 326–327). The latter was recently treated as a *nomen oblitum* in favour of *Mangelia multilincolata* (Deshayes, 1835; *Pleurotoma*) (Spada *et al.* 2023:

19, 21). Listed by Snyder (2022: 119). — Current status: Brown’s taxon might belong in that synonymy as well.

punctatus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 56–57; 1838-C2: 7, pl. 5, figs 56–57. — Type locality: Holy Island, Northumberland, England; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Fusus punctatus* Anton, 1839. Unidentifiable *Mangelia* (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 490). — Current status: possibly young, worn specimen of what is now known as *Raphitoma purpurea* (Montagu, 1803; *Murex*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 224, pl. 181; Snyder 2022: 160).

Unassigned Conoidea J. Fleming, 1822

brevis, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, fig. 34, *non* P. L. S. Müller, 1766. — Type locality: St. Abbs Head, Scotland; T. Brown; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Snyder 2022: 240).

minutus, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 48, figs 18, 24; 1838-C2: 8, pl. 5, figs 18, 24, *non* Röding, 1798, *neq* Lamarck, 1803; there are also three later homonyms. — Type locality: Lough Strangford, Ireland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Unidentifiable *Mangelia* (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 490). — Current status: an unidentifiable conoidean following this earlier literature (Snyder 2022: 130).

multilinearis, *Fusus* — T. Brown, 1838-C2: vii, 6, pl. 5, figs 22–23. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Unidentifiable *Mangelia* (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 490). — Current status: unidentifiable conoidean (Snyder 2022: 135).

Architectonicidae J.E. Gray, 1850

sowerbyii, *Solarium* — T. Brown, 1841-F: 78, pl. 41, figs 7–8. New species based on *Solarium patulum* Lamarck, 1804, as figured by J. Sowerby (1813: 35, pl. 11, two lower left-hand figs). Listed by Bieler & Petit (2005: 65). — Type locality: Highgate Hill, England; London Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Ypresian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

Omalogyridae G. O. Sars, 1878

pellucida, *Planaria* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, figs 53–55. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possible synonym of *Omalogyra atomus* (R. A. Philippi, 1841; *Truncatella*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 170), by implication for the spe-

cies they were then calling *Skenea nitidissima* (J. Adams, 1800; *Helix*); while Brown's species would be senior, ICZN Code Art. 23.9 might apply. Philippi's species was figured by Alf *et al.* (2020: 235, pl. 189).

Phylliroidae Menke, 1830

Phylliroe — T. Brown, 1833: 57. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Phylliroe* F. Péron & Lesueur, 1810.

Retusidae Thiele, 1925

Retusa — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 38, figs 1–6 (three species). Type species (SD Iredale, 1915; ICZN Opinion 568, 1959): *Bulla obtusa* Montagu, 1803. — Current status: valid genus, and basis of Retusidae Thiele, 1925.

Utriculus — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 58–59, pl. 19, figs 1–8, 10–11, 13–14, 39–40 (8 species, one not figured), *non* Schumacher, 1817 [Conidae]. Type species (SD Lemche, 1957; ICZN Opinion 568, 1959): *Bulla obtusa* Montagu, 1803. — Current status: synonym of *Retusa* T. Brown, 1827.

discors, Retusa — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 3–4; 1844-C2: 58, pl. 19, figs 3–4, as *Utriculus*. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Retusa obtusa* (Montagu, 1803; *Bulla*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 512–513, pl. 114C, figs 1–3, as *Cylichna*; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 272, pl. 207).

pellucida, Volvaria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 38, figs 35, 38; 1838-C2: 4, pl. 19, figs 45–46. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Retusa truncatula* (Bruguière, 1791; *Bulla*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 510–512, pl. 114B, figs 7–8, pl. VV, fig. 4; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 272–273, pl. 207; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 173).

plicata, Retusa — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 1–2; 1844-C2: 58, pl. 19, figs 1–2, as *Utriculus plicatus*. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Retusa obtusa* (Montagu, 1803; *Bulla*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 512–513, pl. 114C, figs 1–3, as *Cylichna*; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 272, pl. 207).

subcylindrica, Volvaria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 38, figs 36–37; 1838-C2: 3, pl. 19, figs 19–20. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Retusa umbilicata* (Montagu,

1803; *Bulla*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 519–520, pl. 114C, fig. 9; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 273, pl. 207; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 174).

retusa, Volvaria — “T. Brown”, 1827-C1: pl. 38, figs 17–18, in synonymy with *Bulla truncata* “Montagu” [J. Adams, 1800]; 1838-C2: 4, pl. 19, fig. 12, as *Volvaria retusa*, and with Brown listing *Volvaria regulbiensis* (G. Adams, 1798; *Bulla*) as another synonym. However, this was originally proposed as *Bulla retusa* Matton & Rackett, 1807. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Retusa truncatula* (Bruguière, 1792; *Bulla*).

Cylichnidae H. Adams & A. Adams, 1854

alba, Volvaria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: v, pl. 38, figs 43–44; 1838-C2: 3–4, pl. 19, figs 43–44. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Cylichna alba* (T. Brown, 1827) (Alf *et al.* 2020: 271, pl. 206; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 171).

producta, Bulla — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 15–16; 1844-C2: 56, pl. 19, figs 15–16. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Cylichna cylindracea* (Pennant, 1777; *Bulla*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 508–509, pl. 114B, fig. 6, pl. VV, fig. 3; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 271, pl. 206).

striata, Bulla — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 41–42; 1844-C2: 57, pl. 19, figs 41–42, *non* Bruguière, 1792, *nec* *Bulla ampulla striata* Röding, 1798. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker; Ker collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Roxania utriculus* (Brocchi, 1814; *Bulla*) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 533, pl. 114D, figs 8–9, pl. VV, fig. 2, but as *B. cranchii* J. Fleming, 1828, another synonym). — Current status: synonym of *Cylichna scalpta* (Reeve, 1855; *Bulla*) (Dautzenberg & H. Fischer 1912: 39–40).

Diaphanidae Odhner, 1914 [1857]

Diaphana — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 38, figs 7–8, 10–11, 13–14. Type species (SD Herrmannsen, 1847): *Diaphana candida* T. Brown, 1827, = *D. minuta* T. Brown, 1827. — Current status: valid type genus of the Diaphanidae. Preoccupies *Diaphana* Guppy, 1895, for which *Striatemoda* Baker, 1940, or *Analcadia* A. J. Wagner, 1908, are now in use. [both Helicinidae].

candida, Diaphana — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 13–14; 1844-C2: 59, pl. 19, figs 13–14. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. —

Current status: synonym of *Diaphana minuta* T. Brown, 1827 (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 169; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovalini 2011: 369).

minuta, Diaphana — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 7–8; 1844-C2: 58, pl. 19, figs 7–8, as *Utriculus*. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Diaphana minuta* T. Brown, 1827 (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 169; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovalini 2011: 369).

pellucida, Diaphana — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 10–11; 1844-C2: 59, pl. 19, figs 10–11, as *Utriculus*. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Diaphana minuta* T. Brown, 1827 (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 169; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovalini 2011: 369).

Philinidae J.E. Gray, 1850 [1815]

catina, Bullaea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 38, figs 33–34. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Philine catena* (Montagu, 1803; *Bulla*).

Laonidae Pruvot-Fol, 1954

lima, Bulla — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [ii — Errata], pl. 38, figs 39–40 [not listed in pl. expl.]; 1844-C2: 58, pl. 19, figs 39–40. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Type species (OD) of *Retusophilina* F. Nordsieck, 1972. — Current status: *Retusophilina lima* (T. Brown, 1827) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 172; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovalini 2011: 378, as *Philina*).

Akeridae Mazzarelli, 1891

flexilis, Akera — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 38, figs 31–32, in synonymy with *Bulla akera* “Lamarck” [Gmelin, 1791]; 1833: 97–98, 177, pl. 14, fig. 29; 1837: 378, pl. 17, fig. 109; 1844-C2: 59, pl. 19, figs 31–32. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of the still earlier *Akera bullata* O.F. Müller, 1776 (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 527–529, pl. 114D, figs 4–6, pl. VV, fig. 6; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 279, pl. 210).

Pyramidellidae J.E. Gray, 1840

Jaminia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, figs 10–11, 34–35, 38, pl. 51, figs 6–11, 18, *non* Risso, 1826 [Enidae]. Type species (SD Schander *et al.* 1999): *Turbo interstinctus* J. Adams, 1797). — Current status: synonym of *Parthenina* Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883 (Schander *et al.* 1999: 150).

crenatus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 53; 1838-C2: 14, pl. 9, fig. 53f. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Pyrgiscus crenatus* (T. Brown, 1827) (MolluscaBase).

discrepans, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, figs 70–71; 1838-C2: 13, pl. 9, figs 70–71. — Type locality: Devon, England; Goodall; Goodall collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

glabrus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 37; 1838-C2: 13, pl. 9, fig. 37. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

lacteus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 58; 1838-C2: 11, pl. 9, fig. 77, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: an *Odostomia* but *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 259).

laevis, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, figs 51–52; 1838-C2: 14–15, pl. 9, figs 51–52. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: possible senior synonym of *Eulimella acicula* (R. A. Philippi, 1826; *Melania*) (Peñas & Rolán 1997: 84, 86; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 291, pl. 218).

lamarckii, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 39; 1838-C2: 15, pl. 9, fig. 39. — Type locality: Belton, Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Parthenina interstincta* (J. Adams, 1797; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 296–298, pl. 97, fig. 1, as *Odostomia*; species figured in Cossignani & Ardovalini 2011: 347, as *Chrysallida*).

maculatus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, figs 5–6; 1838-C2: 12, pl. 9, figs 5–6, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Padstow, England; Sir A. Molesworth; Weymouth, England; Goodall; Goodall collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

nidens, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 77; 1838-C2: 11, as a synonym of *Rissoa lactea* (T. Brown, 1827; *Pyramis*). — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

obtusa, Jamina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 38; 1844-C2: 22, pl. 9, fig. 38. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland;

Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Parthenina interstincta* (J. Adams, 1797; *Turbo*) (Oliver *et al.* 2017: 386, text-fig. 36; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 294, pl. 219).

pullus, Jaminia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 11; 1844-C2: 22, pl. 9, fig. 11; Errata: changed to *J. pulla*. — Type locality: Montrose, Scotland; T. Brown; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Odostomia (Jaminia) pullus* (T. Brown, 1827) (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 308).

spirolinus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 66; 1838-C2: 15, pl. 9, fig. 66. — Type locality: St. Cyrus, Kincardineshire, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 249).

sulcatus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 50, fig. 69; 1844-C2: 10, pl. 9, fig. 69, as *Rissoa*. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: similar to *Tragula fenestrata* (Jeffreys, 1848; *Odostomia*), but *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 146).

vittatus, Pyramis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, fig. 29; 1838-C2: 15, pl. 8, fig. 29. — Type locality: Belton, East Lothian, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *nomen dubium* (Forbes & Hanley 1850: 146).

Lymnaeidae Rafinesque, 1815

Lutea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 46, figs 50–53. Type species (T): *Helix lutea* Montagu, 1803. — Current status: has precedence over *Ampullaceana* Servain, 1882, the type species of which (SD Kobelt, 1883) is *Helix balthica* Linnaeus, 1758, as is *Helix lutea* Montagu, 1803. However, Servain's genus might be conserved under ICZN Code Art. 23.9.

lacustris, Lymnaea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 42, figs 24–25, *non* Studer, 1820; 1844-C2: 30, as *Amphipeplea*. — Type locality: Loch Leven, Kinross, Scotland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Peregriana peregra* (O.F. Müller, 1884; *Buccinum*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 48–51, as *Limnaea (Radix)*). — Current status: synonym of *Myxas glutinosa* (O.F. Müller, 1774; *Buccinum*) (Vinarski & Kantor 2016: 316).

subpellucida, Lutea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 46, figs 50–51, in synonymy of *Helix lutea* Montagu, 1803. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Peregriana peregra* (O.F. Müller, 1884; *Buccinum*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 48–51, as *Limnaea (Radix)*).

Physidae Fitzinger, 1833

Amplexa — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 31. Subsequent incorrect spelling of *Aplexa* J. Fleming, 1820.

Planorbidae Rafinesque, 1815

Planaria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, figs 48–49, 53–55 (two species); 1838-C2: 20, *non* O.F. Müller, 1776 [Platyhelminthes]. Type species (**SD herein**): *Planaria alba* T. Brown, 1827, = *Planorbis albus* O.F. Müller, 1774. *Trochlea* Haldeman, 1842, replacement name. — Current status: both are synonyms of *Gyraulus* Charpentier, 1837 (Vinarski & Kantor 2016: 370).

alba, Planaria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, figs 48–49. — Type locality: between Dunbar & Saint Abbs Head, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. It is uncertain why Brown listed this as a “new species”. — Current status: synonym of *Gyraulus albus* (O.F. Müller, 1774; *Planorbis*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 75–77).

cochlea, Helix — T. Brown, 1818a: 528–529, pl. 24, fig. 10; 1827: pl. 41, fig. 33, in synonymy with *Helix carinata* “Montagu, 1803” [*Planorbis carinatus* O.F. Müller, 1774]. — Type locality: College Botanic Garden; Thomas Stephens; J. O’Kelly collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Turton (1819: 62–63, pl. 14, fig. 55) renamed Brown’s species as *Helix terebra*, without giving a reason. — Current status: synonym of *Planorbis planorbis* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Helix*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 69; Vinarski & Kantor 2016: 351).

striatus, Vermetus — T. Brown, 1842-F: 84, pl. 43, figs 14–15. — Type locality: Blackdown, Devon, England; Greensands [Upper Greensand Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: not located. As pointed out by Bieler & Petit (2011: 61), this is a very confusing entry, but not as they indicated a *nomen nudum*. Brown’s cited figures on p. 263 of his plate list (1849) are of a completely unrelated *Tornatella*, corresponding to *Tornatella striatus* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1824; *Acteon*) [*non Acteon striata* I. Lea, 1833, and not in Brown’s text], and these figures do not relate in any way to his written description nor to his reference to *Planorbis radiatus* J. Sowerby, 1816 (p. 92, pl. 140, fig. 5), the change in the specific name either being a typesetting error or an unjustified emendation. — Current status: synonym of J. Sowerby’s species, which may be either a planorbid or perhaps an annelid worm, thus a *nomen dubium*.

nitens, Planaria — T. Brown, 1843b: 49, pl. 6, fig. 19, *non* I. Lea, 1833. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, near Dunbar,

Scotland. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: possibly Annelida.

Enidae B.B. Woodward, 1903 [1880]

brevis, Bulimus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 41, fig. 21; 18xx: 36, as a variety of *B. obscurus* “Draparnaud” [O.F. Müller, 1774; *Helix*]. — Type locality: East Lomond Hill, Fife, Scotland; T. Brown, in a limestone quarry. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: presumably synonym of *Merdigera obscura* (O.F. Müller, 1774).

Vitrinidae Fitzinger, 1833

elliptica, Helix — T. Brown, 1818a: 525, pl. 24, fig. 8. — Type locality: Gullan[e] & Downpatrick, Ireland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Vitrina pellucida* (O.F. Müller, 1774; *Helix*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 186–188).

margaritacea, Vitrina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 40, figs 54–56; 1844-C2: 54, pl. 17, figs 54–56, as *Helix* (*Trigono-stoma*). — Type locality: Corstorphine Hill, near Edinburgh, Scotland; Gerard. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

Geomitridae C. Boettger, 1909

Heliomanes — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 49–51, *ex* Férussac ms (four species), *non* Newman, 1840 [Coleoptera]. Type species (**SD herein**): *Cochlea virgata* da Costa, 1778. Previously thought to have been first made available by Moquin-Tandon (1855), it was first used by Brown. We have been unable to find any earlier type designation. — Current status: while unavailable because it is a junior homonym, our type designation firmly places it as a synonym of *Cernuella* Schlüter, 1838, which has the same type species.

Trochoidea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 41, figs 80–81. Type species (M): *Trochus terrestris* Pennant, 1777, *sensu* “Montagu”, 1803, *i.e.* *Helix elegans* Gmelin, 1791 (under ICZN Code Art. 70.3; Bouchet & Rocroi, 2017: 250). — Current status: valid genus (R. Anderson 2005: 614).

elegans, Helix — T. Brown, 1818a: 528, pl. 24, fig. 9, *non* Gmelin, 1791; 1827: iii, pl. 40, fig. 28, as *Carocolla*; 1844-C2: 50–51, pl. 17, figs 37, 39, as a synonym of *Helix* (*Heliomanes*) *ericetorum* O.F. Müller, 1774. — Type locality: Kilmainham Jail, Ireland; Edward Stephens; J. O’Kelly collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Renamed by Turton (1819: 61–62, pl. 16, fig. 63) as *Helix disjuncta*, without giving a reason. — Current status: synonym of *Cernuella virgata* (da Costa,

1778; *Cochlea*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 210–213).

Hygromiidae Tryon, 1866

gibbsii, Helix — T. Brown, 1827, *ex* Leach ms: iii, pl. 40, figs 49–51. — Type locality: Devon, England; J.E. Leach. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller, 1774; *Helix*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 228–230, as *Theba*; Oliver *et al.* 2017: 385, text-fig. 31).

membranacea, Vitrina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 40, figs 3–5. — Type locality: Lomond Hills, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Vitrina membranacea* W. H. Benson, 1853, now *Helicarion membranaceus* (W. H. Benson, 1853) [Helicarionidae], and of Koch, 1876. Benson’s species is a *taxon inquirendum* at this time; if useful, his name would need to be replaced. — Current status: synonym of *Zenobiellina subrufescens* (J. S. Miller, 1833; *Helix*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 235–236).

Ellobiidae L. Pfeiffer, 1854 [1822]

discrepans, Auricula — T. Brown, 1843-F: 99, pl. 46, figs 42–43. New species based on *Bulla simulata* Solander, 1766, as figured by J. Sowerby (1817: 144, pl. 163, figs 7–8). — Type locality: Barton Cliff & Hordwell [Hordle], Hamsey, Sussex, England; London clay [Barton Clay Formation & Headon Hill Formation]. — Type age: Eocene Bartonian-Priabonian). — Type material: would be Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

jududae, Auricula — T. Brown, 1833: 90, pl. 13, fig. 13. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: incorrect subsequent spelling of *Auricula judae* Roissy, 1805.

quinquidens, Jaminia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 51, fig. 11; 1844-C2: 22, pl. 8, fig. 11. — Type locality: Prestonpans, Scotland; T. Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Myosotella myosotis* (Draparnaud, 1801; *Auricula*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 38–39, as *Phytia*; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 299, pl. 221).

Otinidae H. Adams & A. Adams, 1855

Galericulum — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 38, figs 27–28, 35–36 (two species); 1844-C2: 23–24. Type species (SD Herrmannsen, 1847): *Helix laevigata* Linnaeus, 1767, which is regarded as a *nomen dubium*. The genus *Otina* J.E. Gray, 1847, has been given precedence of this genus if the two are regarded as synonyms; its type species (OD) is *Helix otis* W. Turton, 1819, *non* [Lightfoot], 1786.

ovatum, Galericulum — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iv, pl. 38, figs 27–28; 1844-C2: 23–24, pl. 19, figs 27–28. — Type locality: Devon, England; J.E. Leach. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. An earlier but unavailable name for this species is *Helix otis* W. Turton, 1819, *non* [Lightfoot], 1786. — Current status: *Otina ovata* (T. Brown, 1827) (Forbes & Hanley 1851: 321–323, pl. 99, figs 2–3, pl. OO, fig. 4; R. Anderson 2005: 616). See also: ICZN Opinion 335 (1955).

Ferussaciidae Bourguignat, 1883

alba, Achatina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 41, fig. 82, pl. 48, fig. 61, in both editions in synonymy with *Buccinum terrestre* Montagu, 1803. — Age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of the still-older *Cecilioides acicula* (O.F. Müller, 1774; *Buccinum*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 281–283).

minutus, Bulimus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 41, fig. 26; 1844-C2: 35, pl. 14, fig. 26, as *Acme*. — Type locality: Douglas Castle, Scotland; low meadow below old tower; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Cecilioides fusca* (Montagu, 1803; *Turbo*) (Forbes & Hanley, 1852; 204–205, pl. 125, fig. 7, but now synonym of *Acme lineata* (Draparnaud, 1801; *Bulimus*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 6–9).

Lauriidae Steenberg, 1925

labiata, Pupa — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 41, fig. 7. — Type locality: Portmarnock, Ireland. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Truncatellina cylindrica* (Férussac, 1807; *Vertigo*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 126–128). — Current status: synonym of *Lauria cylindracea* (da Costa, 1778; *Turbo*) (Mollusca-Base).

Valloniidae Morse, 1864

Amplexis — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 41, figs 77–79 (2 species). Type species (SD Pilsbry 1935): *Helix paludosa* da Costa, 1778, a synonym of *Vallonia pulchella* (O.F. Müller, 1774; *Helix*). — Current status: synonym of *Vallonia* Risso, 1826 (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 135).

Amplexus — T. Brown, 1845: ix, 61–62. Invalid emendation of *Amplexis* T. Brown, 1827.

Oxychilidae Hesse, 1927 [1879]

foetida, Helix — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 40, figs 48, 52. — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Oxychilus alliarius* (J. S. Miller, 1822; *Helix*)

(Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 177–178).

vitrea, Helix — T. Brown, 1829: 12, pl. 1, figs 12–14, *non* Born, 1778, *nec* Férussac, 1821. — Type locality: Corstorphine Hill, Edinburgh, Scotland; James Gerard. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Vitrea crystallina* (Müller, 1774; *Helix*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 183–185).

Class Bivalvia

Nuculidae J.E. Gray, 1824

argentea, Nucula — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 25, figs 14–15; 1844-C2: 85, pl. 33, figs 14–15, *non* *Nucula argentea* (da Costa, 1777; *Glycymeris*), now regarded as a synonym of *Nucula nucleus* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Arca*). — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Expressly indicated as a new species without reference to da Costa. — Current status: probably also synonym of *Nucula nucleus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Forbes & Hanley 1849: 218, footnote; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 304, pl. 230).

crenistriata, Nucula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 186, pl. 76, fig. 91. New species based on *Nucula lineata* “var. β ” of J. Phillips (1841: 39, pl. 18, fig. 6b). — Type locality: Boggy Point [Baggy Point], north Devon, England; shale, in limestone nodules. — Type age: Devonian (Famennian). — Type material: would be Phillips’ material. — Current status: uncertain.

pisum, Nucula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 186, pl. 76, figs 46–47, *non* G.B. Sowerby I, 1833. — Type locality: Newcastle-on-Tyne, England; Robertson; coal measures. — Type age: Permian. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

subcompressa, Nucula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 186, pl. 76, fig. 90. — Type locality: Bolland [Ballyadams, County Laois], Ireland; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous. Replacement name for *Nucula undulata* J. Phillips (1836: 210, pl. 5, fig. 16), *non* J. De C. Sowerby, 1827, which Brown had discussed on p. 185. However, *Nucula phillipsii* McCoy (1844: 70) was an earlier replacement name. — Current status: *Nucula undulata* J. Phillips, 1836 (Hind 1897: 181–182, pl. 14, figs 28–31, pl. 15, fig. 33), who missed the homonymy; thus, now synonym of *Nucula phillipsii* McCoy, 1844.

Nuculanidae H. Adams & A. Adams, 1858 [1854]

dubia, Nucula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 186, pl. 76, fig. 30, *non* Münster, in Alberti, 1834. New species based on *Nucula* sp. of J. Phillips, 1835 (p. 100, 179, pl. 4, fig. 4). — Type

locality: Malton, Yorkshire, England; Coralline Oolite [Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Oxfordian). — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: a *Nuculana* but of uncertain status.

longirostra, *Nucula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 187, pl. 76, figs 68–69. New species based on *Nucula claviformis* J. De C. Sowerby, 1824, as figured by J. Phillips (1836: 210, pl. 5, fig. 17). — Type locality: Harelaw & Otterburn, Northumberland, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Nucula laevirostrum* Portlock, 1843 (Hind 1897: 183, pl. 15, figs 32, 34–38, 38a).

oblonga, *Nucula* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 25, fig. 17; 1844-C2: 84, pl. 33, fig. 17. — Type locality: Saltcoats, Scotland; Stewart Ker. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Nuculana pernula* (O.F. Müller, 1779; *Arca*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 310; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 306, pl. 232).

truncata, *Nucula* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 25, fig. 19; 1844-C2: 84, pl. 33, fig. 19, *non* Bosc, 1801, *nec* Nilsson, 1827. — Type locality: Saltcoats, Scotland; Stewart Ker. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. All preoccupy *Nucula truncata* Gabb, 1864, for which *Acila demessa* Finlay, 1927, was a replacement name. — Current status: synonym of *Portlandia arctica* (J.E. Gray, 1824; *Nucula*) (Soot-Ryen 1964), the type species of *Portlandia* (ICZN Opinion 769, 1966).

Mytilidae Rafinesque, 1815

Crenella — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 31; 1844-C2: 75. Type species (M): *Crenella elliptica* T. Brown, 1827, = *Crenella decussata* (Montagu, 1808; *Mytilus*). — Current status: valid genus.

aequilatus, Mytilus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 171, pl. 71, fig. 15. New species based on one of three figures of *Mytilus antiquorum* J. Sowerby, 1821 (p. 133, pl. 275, fig. 3). — Type locality: Ipswich, England; Suffolk Crag [Red Crag Formation]. — Type age: Pliocene-Pleistocene. — Type material: would be Sowerby's material, which is in the NHMUK. — Current status: uncertain.

antiquus, Lithophagus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 257, pl. 72, figs 44–45. — Type locality: Malton, Yorkshire, England; coral rag [Coralline Oolite Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Oxfordian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

elegans, Mytilus — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 29, figs 14–15; 1844-C2: 76, pl. 27, figs 14–15, *ex* Leach ms. — Type locality: Bell Rock, Firth of Forth, Scotland; Rob-

ert Stevenson. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Mytilus edulis* Linnaeus, 1758 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 330–331, pls 264–265).

elliptica, Crenella — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 31, figs 12–14; 1844-C2: 75, pl. 23, figs 12–14, in synonymy with *Crenella decussata* (Montagu, 1808; *Mytilus*) in both editions. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Crenella decussata* (Montagu, 1808) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 325, pl. 258).

flexuosa, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 173, pl. 72, fig. 18. — Type locality: the Marlstone, Gloucestershire, England; lower bed of oolitic series; Thomas Allis collection. — Type age: Jurassic (Middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

minuta, Modiola — T. Brown, 1841b: 227–228, pl. 7, fig. 75; 1849-F: 174, pl. 72, fig. 29. — Type locality: Low Moor, near Bradford, Yorkshire, England; shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. Junior secondary homonym of *Modiolus minutus* (Zieten, 1833; *Mytilus*). — Current status: uncertain.

prideauxiana, Modiola — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 9, fig. 9; 1841-C2: pl. 27, fig. 9; 1844-C2: 78, xi. — Current status: unjustified emendation of *Rhomboidella prideauxii* (Leach, 1815; *Modiola*).

Modiolidae G. Termier & H. Termier, 1950

Note: *Modiola* Lamarck, 1801, is a subsequent incorrect spelling of *Modiolus* Lamarck, 1799.

aldami, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 172, pl. 72, fig. 17. New species based on *Modiola aspera* J. Sowerby, 1818, “var.” of J. Phillips (1835: 128, pl. 11, fig. 9). — Type locality: Blue Wick [Blea Wyke], Glaisdale, Yorkshire, England; Inferior Oolite [Group]. — Type age: Jurassic (Aalenian-Bajocian). — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: uncertain.

ballii, Modiola — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 132, pl. 39, fig. 36 [cited in text as pl. “37”]. — Type locality: Youghal, Ireland; Robert Ball. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: lost (Forbes & Hanley 1849: 192). — Current status: synonym of *Lioberus agglutinans* (Cantraine, 1835; *Modiolus*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 327, pl. 260).

decussata, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 175–176, pl. 61***, figs 22–23. — Type locality: “various”; Bath oolite [Great Oolite Group]. — Type age: Jurassic (Bathonian). — Type material: not located. Brown indicated that this might be the *Modiola* sp. of Jelly (1839). — Current status: uncertain.

latissima, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 174, pl. 71, fig. 21. Replacement name for *Modiola cuneata* J. Sowerby, 1819 (p. 87, pl. 248, fig. 2), *non Modiola cuneata* J. Sowerby, 1818 (p. 19, pl. 211, fig. 1), which Brown had also discussed (p. 174, pl. 72, figs 30–31). — Type locality: Bourton, near Cropredy & Banbury, Oxfordshire, England; Rev. W. D. Conybeare; clay; also found near Bath, England; [Great Oolite Group?]. — Type age: Jurassic (Batonian?). — Type material: would be that of Sowerby. — Current status: uncertain.

moorei, Modiola — T. Brown, 1841b: 227, pl. 7, fig. 74; 1849-F: 173–174, pl. 72, fig. 27. — Type locality: Crimsworth Dean, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10229, holotype (Jackson 1952: 69). — Current status: uncertain.

radiata, Modiola — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 29, figs 5–6. — Type locality: Cornwall, England; W. C. Trevelyan; Trevelyan collection. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Gibbomodiola adriaticus* (Lamarck, 1819; *Modiola*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 326, pl. 258).

rectus, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 174, pl. 72*, fig. 7, *non Modiolus rectus* Conrad, 1837. — Type locality: Yorkshire, England; middle oolite [Coralline Oolite Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Oxfordian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

undulata, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 174, pl. 72, fig. 38. — Type locality: South Cave, Scarborough, Yorkshire & Kelloways Rock [Osgodby Formation], England. — Type age: Type age: Jurassic (Callovian). — Type material: not located.

Arcidae, s.l.

elongata, Arca — T. Brown, 1849-F: 191, pl. 77, fig. 34, *non* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1824; *Cucullaea*), *nec* W. Wood, 1828, *nec* Buckman, in Murchison, 1844. — Type locality: Blackdown, West Sussex, England; greensand [Upper Greensand Formation]. — Type age: Cretaceous (Albian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

oviformis, Cucullaea — T. Brown, 1849-F: 193, pl. 78, fig. 3. New species based on *Cucullaea antiqua* J. De C. Sowerby, in Murchison, 1839 (pp. 602, 709, pl. 3, fig. 1b), presumably as opposed to fig. 12a on the same plate also cited by Sowerby. Brown specified only “fig. 1”. — Type locality: Horeb Chapel [Capel Horeb] & Felindre on the Teme, Wales; Ludlow, Shropshire, England; Old Red Sandstone. — Type age: Devonian. — Type material:

would be Sowerby’s material. — Current status: uncertain.

papillosa, Arca — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 104, pl. 1, fig. 19, *ex* Smith ms; 1849-F: 191, pl. 77, fig. 28. — Type locality: Portrush, Ireland. — Type age: Pleistocene; J. Smith. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tetrarca tetragona* (Poli, 1795; *Arca*) (Forbes & Hanley 1849: 234–238, pl. 45, figs 9–10, pl. P, fig. 1; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 310, pl. 235, as *Arca*).

Glycymerididae Dall, 1908 [1847]

obliquus, Pectunculus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 189, pl. 77, fig. 9. — Type locality: Bromeswell, Suffolk, England; Red Crag [Formation]. — Type age: Pliocene-Pleistocene. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

delectus, Pectunculus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 189, pl. 77, fig. 13. New species based on *Pectunculus costatus* J. Sowerby, 1813 (p. 72, pl. 27, fig. 2). — Type locality: Barton, Sussex, England; London Clay [Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — This is a puzzle in that it appears to be in synonymy of a valid J. Sowerby species, without any words to differentiate it. — Current status: synonym of *Glycymeris costatus* (J. Sowerby, 1813).

Pteriidae J.E. Gray, 1847 [1820]

Note: some of the Paleozoic spp. listed here will belong to related families.

anglica, Avicula — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 31, fig. 3; 1844-C2: 74, pl. 23, fig. 3, *ex* Leach ms. — Type locality: Devon, England; W. E. Leach; NHMUK collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Pteria hirundo* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mytilus*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 336, pl. 269).

decepta, Avicula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 162, pl. 83, fig. 18. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

humata, Avicula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 161, pl. 66**, fig. 1. Replacement name for *Avicula obliqua* T. Brown, 1841, *non* J. De C. Sowerby, in Murchison, 1839. — Current status: uncertain.

longiarea, Avicula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 257, pl. 61**, fig. 14. — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: none provided. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

murchisoni, Avicula — T. Brown, 1849-F: 161, pl. 66*, fig. 18. New species based on one of the two figures of *Avicula orbicularis* J. De C. Sowerby, in Murchison, 1839 (p. 635,

pl. 20, fig. 3). — Type locality: Acton Scott, Shropshire, England; Caradoc sandstone [Caradoc Series]. — Type age: Ordovician. — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: uncertain.

neptune, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 163, pl. 61**, fig. 21. — Type locality: Westmorland, England; limestone. — Type age: Silurian (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

novemcostae, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 162, pl. 66**, fig. 12. New species based on *Avicula inaequalis* J. Sowerby, 1819, of J. Phillips, 1835 (p. 133, pl. 14, fig. 4). — Type locality: "many"; marlstone. — Type age: presumably Jurassic. — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: uncertain.

obliqua, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1841b: 225, pl. 7, fig. 64, *non* J. De C. Sowerby, in Murchison, 1839. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. *Avicula humata* T. Brown, 1849, replacement name. — Current status: uncertain.

oweni, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 160, pl. 65, fig. 13. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal measures. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

plicata, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 160, pl. 65, fig. 8, *non* A. d'Orbigny, 1845. — Type locality: Middleton, near Leeds, Yorkshire, England; coal measures. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

samuelsii, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1841b: 225, pl. 7, fig. 65; 1849-F: 161, pl. 66**, fig. 29. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10228, holotype (Jackson 1952: 62). — Current status: probably synonym of *Pterinopecten papyraceus* (J. Sowerby, 1823; *Pecten*) based on a young specimen (Hind 1903: 51–52, pl. 7, figs 7–13).

simili, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 160, pl. 65, fig. 12. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal measures. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

squamula, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 161, pl. 68, fig. 10. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Posidoniella minor* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 98–100, pl. 6, figs 15, 17–18, 22–23).

tenera, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 163, pl. 61**, fig. 11. New species based on *Avicula papyracea* "Goldfuss"

[*Pecten papyraceus* J. Sowerby, 1822] as figured by Goldfuss (1835: 126, pl. 116, fig. 5). — Type locality: Bradford, Yorkshire, England; coal measures. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: would be Goldfuss' material. — Current status: uncertain.

tenua, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 161, pl. 68, fig. 9. New species based on a figure in Binney (1841: pl. 5, fig. 23). — Type locality: Pendleton Coal Mine, near Manchester, England; Black Bass. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: would be Binney's material. — Current status: uncertain.

Bakevelliidae W. King, 1850

binneyi, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1841a: 65, pl. 6, figs 27–28; 1849-F: 161, pl. 66**, figs 5–6. — Type locality: Newtown, Lancashire, [Manchester], England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: MM LL.2848, LL.2850, LL.2853, LL.2855, syntypes, number unknown (Nudds 1992: 84). Synonym of, and valid name for *Bakevellia antiqua* (Münster, in Goldfuss, 1836; *Avicula*), the type species (SD W. King, 1850) of *Bakevellia* W. King, 1848, which was *non Avicula antiqua* Defrance, 1816 (Hautmann, 2015: 886). — Current status: *Bakevellia binneyi* (T. Brown, 1841). (Logan 1967: 32, pl. 4, figs 1–2; Pattison 1970: 147, pl. 21, figs 1–2; Prinoth & Posenato 2023: 12–14, text-fig. 8).

discors, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1841a: 65, pl. 6, fig. 28; 1849-F: 163, pl. 66**, fig. 3. — Type locality: Newtown, near Manchester, England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Late?). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Bakevellia binneyi* (Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 147, pl. 21, figs 1–2).

inflata, *Avicula* — T. Brown, 1841a: 65, pl. 6, figs 25–26; 1849-F: 161, pl. 66**, figs 4, 8, *non Münster, 1840*. — Type locality: Newtown, Lancashire, Manchester, England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Late?). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Bakevellia binneyi* (Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 147, pl. 21, figs 1–2).

minor, *Gervillia* — T. Brown, 1841b: 227, pl. 7, fig. 70; 1849-F: 165, pl. 61**, fig. 31. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.12030, holotype (Bolton 1893: 12–13; Jackson 1952). — Current status: *Posidoniella minor* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind, 1897: 98–100, pl. 6, figs 15, 17–18, 22–23; Jackson 1952: 68).

Posidoniidae Neumayr, 1891

Note: *Catillus* Brongniart, 1822, is now considered to be a synonym of *Inoceramus* J. Sowerby, 1814, large Mesozoic clams. The following bivalves from the Paleozoic must belong somewhere else, probably here.

- anodontoidea, *Posidonia*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 168, pl. 61**, fig. 1. New species based on *Posidonia becheri* Bronn, 1828, as figured by J. De C. Sowerby, in Sedgwick & Murchison (1840: unnumbered p. of pl. explanations, pl. 52, fig. 2). — Type locality: Venn Quarry, Devon, England; limestone [Codden Hill Chert Formation?]. — Type age: Carboniferous (Visean?). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: uncertain.
- costatus, *Catillus*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 226, pl. 7, fig. 68; 1849-F: 167, pl. 68, fig. 24. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10248, holotype (Jackson 1952: 68). — Current status: synonym of *Posidoniella kirkmani* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 96–97, pl. 6, figs 16, 19–21).
- kellyii, *Catillus*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 226–227, pl. 7, fig. 73; 1849-F: 167, pl. 68, fig. 17. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10246, holotype (Jackson 1952: 66). — Current status: synonym of *Posidoniella laevis* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 94–96, pl. 6, figs 12–14, 24).
- kirkmani, *Catillus*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 225–226, pl. 7, fig. 66; 1849-F: 167, pl. 67, fig. 24. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM, “holotype” (Bolton 1893: 12), but not listed by Jackson (1952). — Current status: *Posidoniella kirkmani* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 96–97, pl. 6, figs 16, 19–21).
- laevis, *Catillus*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 226, pl. 7, fig. 67; 1849-F: 167, pl. 67, fig. 22. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10230, holotype (Bolton 1893: 12; Jackson 1952: 66). — Current status: *Posidoniella laevis* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 94–96, pl. 6, figs 12–14, 24).
- minutus, *Catillus*** — T. Brown, 1841b: 226, pl. 7, figs 71–72; 1849-F: 167, pl. 68, figs 18–19. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10247, holotype (Jackson 1952: 66). — Current status: synonym of *Posidoniella laevis* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 94–96, pl. 6, figs 12–14, 24).

obliquatus, *Catillus* — T. Brown, 1841b: 226, pl. 7, fig. 69; 1849-F: 167, pl. 67, fig. 33. — Type locality: High Greenwood, Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10249, holotype. Synonym of *Posidoniella kirkmani* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 96–97, pl. 6, figs 16, 19–21). — Current status: *Posidonia obliquata* (T. Brown, 1841) (Hind 1897: 96, pl. 6, figs 16, 19–21; Ramsbottom 1959: 406, pl. 71, figs 11–12).

truncata, *Posidonia* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 168, pl. 61**, fig. 26. New species based on *Posidonia becheri* Bronn, 1828, “var.,” as figured by J. De C. Sowerby, in Sedgwick & Murchison (1840: unnumbered p. of pl. explanations, pl. 52, fig. 4). — Type locality: Venn Quarry, Devon, England; limestone [Codden Hill Chert Formation?]. — Type age: Carboniferous (Visean?). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material. — Current status: uncertain.

Pterineidae Meek, 1864

rostrata, *Modiola* — Noted by Hind (1901: 20) as being on a label in the MM, in synonymy with his new *Leiopteria longirostris* Hind, 1901 (pp. 20–21, pl. 4, figs 14–15). — Type age: Carboniferous.

Naiaditidae Scarlato & Starobogatov, 1979

- curtata, *Modiola*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 173, pl. 72, figs 19–20, *ex* Williamson ms. — Type locality: Wakefield, West Yorkshire, England; coal shale; Williamson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: MM LL.2834, holotype? (Nudds 1992: 83). Synonym of *Anthracomya modiolaris* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1840; *Unio*) (Hind, 1895: 95–96, pl. 13, figs 10, 12, pl. 14, figs 1–11, 32, pl. 16, figs 49–53). — Current status: *Anthraconaia curtata* (T. Brown, 1849) (Weir 1966: 361, pl. 40, figs 1–5).
- funata, *Modiola*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 172, pl. 71, figs 12–13, *ex* Williamson ms. — Type locality: Wakefield, West Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Naiadites modiolaris* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1840; *Avicula*) (Hind 1895: 131–135, pl. 17, figs 8–10, 12–30).
- gracilis, *Modiola*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 173, *ex* Williamson ms, in synonymy with *Modiola subtruncata* T. Brown, 1849, and *non* Klipstein, 1845, *nec* R. A. Philippi, 1847. — Current status: can be listed in the synonymy of *Naiadites subtruncatus* (T. Brown, 1849).
- modioliforme, *Avicula*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 162, pl. 66*, fig. 19. — Type locality: Woodhall, on the River Leith, near Edinburgh; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. —

Type material: not located. Listed with “*Avicula modiola* Rhind” in synonymy, but no such name occurs in Rhind (1838: “167, pl. 2, fig. S”, and his plates have letters not numbers). — Current status: synonym of *Naiadites crassus* (J. Fleming, 1828; *Mytilus*) (Hind 1895: 147–150, pl. 20, figs 1–11).

producta, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 173, pl. 72, figs 11–12, *ex* Williamson ms. — Type locality: Wakefield, West Yorkshire, England; coal shale; Williamson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Naiadites quadrata* (D. de C. Sowerby, 1840; *Avicula*) (Hind 1895: 140–143, pl. 18, figs 17–21, 23–25).

robertsoni, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 173, pl. 72, figs 24–25. — Type locality: Newcastle; coal shale; Robertson collection. — Type age: Permian. — Current status: synonym of *Anthracomya modiolaris* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1840; *Unio*) (Hind 1895: 95–96, pl. 13, figs 10, 12, pl. 14, figs 1–11, 32, pl. 16, figs 49–53).

subtruncata, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 173, pl. 72, figs 15–16, *ex* Williamson ms. — Type locality: Wakefield, West Yorkshire, England; coal shale; Williamson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Naiadites modiolaris* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1840; *Avicula*) (Hind, 1895: 131–135, pl. 17, figs 8–10, 12–30). — Current status: *Naiadites subtruncatus* (T. Brown, 1849) (*Carbonicola turgida* T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1898: 252).

williamsoni, Modiola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 172, pl. 71, figs 24–25. — Type locality: Wakefield, West Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. *Modiola elongata* Williamson ms. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Anthracomya williamsoni* (T. Brown, 1849) (Hind 1895: 99–100, pl. 14, figs 12–31, pl. 15, fig. 10; Hind 1898: 25).

Pinnidae Leach, 1819

elegans, Pinna — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 30, fig. 2; 1844-C2: 76, pl. 26, fig. 2, *ex* Leach ms. — Type locality: Devon, England; Charles Prideaux; Lady Jardine & NHMUK collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Atrina fragilis* (Pennant, 1777; *Pinna*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 334, pls 267–268).

Ostreidae Rafinesque, 1815

indistincta, Ostrea — T. Brown, 1849-F: 148, pl. 58, fig. 8. — Type locality: Scarborough, North Yorkshire, England; Oxford Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Callovian-Oxfordian). — Type material: could be

Phillips’ material. Brown suggested this might be the same as the *Ostrea* sp. of J. Phillips (1835: 109, 180, pl. 5, fig. 12). — Current status: uncertain.

Gryphaeidae Vialov, 1936

phillipsii, Gryphaea — T. Brown, 1849-F: 149, pl. 61, figs 13–14. New species based on *Gryphaea* sp. of J. Phillips (1835: 123, 182, pl. 9, fig. 26), which came from Cloughton Wyke. — Type locality: Yorkshire, England; [Cloughton Formation?]. — Type age: Jurassic (Bajocian?). — Type material: would be Phillips’ material. — Current status: uncertain.

Anomiidae Rafinesque, 1815

aculiata, Anomia — T. Brown, 1849-F: 144, pl. 57, fig. 17. Subsequent incorrect spelling of *Anomia aculeata* O.F. Müller, 1776. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Heteranomia squamula* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Anomia*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 314, pl. 242).

pellucida, Anomia — T. Brown, 1818a: 514–515; 1827: iii, pl. 10*, fig. 5; 1844-C2: 70, in synonymy of *A. aculeata* O.F. Müller, 1776. — Type locality: Cullercoats, near Tynemouth, Portmarnock & Dublin Bay, Ireland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Anomia ephippium* Linnaeus, 1758 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 314, pls 241–242).

lineata, Anomia — “T. Brown, 1849-F”: 144, pl. 57, figs 5–8. Not a Brown name. This was a replacement name for *Anomia striata* J. De C. Sowerby, 1828 [*non* Röding, 1798, *nec* Schroeter, 1803, *nec* Brocchi, 1814], by J. De C. Sowerby (1828) in the unpaginated “Corrections and Observations” at the end of *Mineral Conchology* Vol. 5.

Pectinidae Rafinesque, 1815

discrepans, Pecten — T. Brown, 1849-F: 157, pl. 65, fig. 17. — Type locality: South Cave, Scarborough, Yorkshire; Hackness & Kelloways Rock [Osgodby Formation], England. — Type age: Jurassic (Callovian). — Type material: not located. New “large variety” of *Pecten fibrosus* J. Phillips (1829: 112, pl. 6, fig. 3). — Current status: synonym of *Radulopecten scarburgensis* (G. Young & Bird 1822; *Pecten*) (Johnson 1984: 209–216, pl. 10, figs 19 ?, 23, 25–29, ? pl. 11, figs 1, 3; text-figs 193–200).

flemingi, Pecten — T. Brown, 1849-F: 153, pl. 56*, fig. 40. — Type locality: Melton [Mowbray], Leicestershire, England; J. Fleming; Great Oolite [Group]; J. Fleming collection. — Type age: Jurassic (Middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

nebulosus, Pecten — T. Brown, 1835: [9]; 1844-C2: 72, pl. 22, fig. 17. — Type locality: Largs, mouth of the Clyde, Scotland; John Blythe. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Pseudamussium peslutrae* (Linnaeus, 1771; *Ostrea*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 322, pl. 253).

spinus, Pecten — T. Brown, 1827-C1: iii, pl. 31, fig. 8; 1844-C2: 73, pl. 24, fig. 8. No locality originally provided in 1827; 1844-C2: — Type locality: Herd Sands, South Shields, England; T. Brown & Seaton, England; W. C. Trevelyan. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Listed with “*Hinnites pusio* Sowerby”. — Current status: *Talochlamys pusio* (Linnaeus, 1858; *Ostrea*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 322, pl. 253).

Limidae Rafinesque, 1815

ambiguum, Plagiostoma — T. Brown, 1849-F: 152, pl. 66, fig. 8. New species based on *Plagiostoma* sp. of J. Phillips (1836: 247, pl. 6, fig. 23). — Type locality: Yorkshire, England; mountain limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous? — Type material: would be Phillips’ material. — Current status: uncertain.

dubium, Plagiostoma — T. Brown, 1849-F: 152, pl. 66, fig. 16. New species based on *Plagiostoma* sp. of J. Phillips (1835: 180, pl. 5, fig. 10). — Type locality: Yorkshire, England; Oxford Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Callovian-Oxfordian). — Type material: would be Phillips’ material. — Current status: uncertain.

goodallii, Lima — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 74, *ex* Leach ms, in synonymy with *Lima fragilis* (Gmelin, 1791; *Ostrea*). — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Limaria loscombi* (G.B. Sowerby I, 1823; *Lima*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 316, pl. 244).

sulcata, Lima — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 31, figs 4–5; 1844-C2: 74, pl. 23, figs 4–5, *ex* Leach ms, *non* Lamarck, 1819, in the synonymy of *Pecten* “*suborbicularis* Montagu”, an error for *P. subauriculata* Montagu, 1808. Both preoccupy *Lima sulcata* Münster, in Goldfuss, 1836. — Age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Limatula subauriculata* (Montagu, 1808; *Pecten*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 316, pl. 244).

vitrina, Lima — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 31, figs 10–11; 1844-C2: 74, pl. 23, figs 10, 10*, 11, 11*. — Type locality: Ballantrae, Scotland; T. Brown. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: syn-

onym of *Limaria hians* (Gmelin, 1791; *Ostrea*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 315–316, pl. 244).

Laevitrigoniidae Saveliev, 1958

pustulata, Trigonina — T. Brown, 1849-F: 183, pl. 75, fig. 12. New species based in part on *Trigonina gibbosa* J. Sowerby, 1818 var. β (p. 61, pl. 236, lower figure). — Type locality: Tisbury (Sowerby); Portland, Vale of Wardour, Swindon & Brill, Buckinghamshire, England; Portland Stone [Formation]. — Type age: Jurassic (Tithonian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: probable synonym of *Laevitrigonia gibbosa* (J. Sowerby, 1819; *Trigonina*), the type species (OD) of *Laevitrigonia* Lebküchner, 1832.

Schizodidae Newell & Boyd, 1975

minima, Lucina — T. Brown, 1841a: 66, pl. 6, fig. 33, *non* F. A. Roemer, 1836. — Type locality: Newtown, Manchester, England; Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: MM LL.2852, holotype (Nudds 1992: 84). — Current status: synonym of *Schizodus obscurus* (J. Sowerby, 1821; *Axinus*) (Pattison 1970: 149–154, pl. 21, fig. 12, pl. 22, figs 1–3).

parvus, Axinus — T. Brown, 1841a: 65, pl. 6, fig. 30; 1849-F: 195, pl. 79, fig. 12. — Type locality: Newtown, Manchester, England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Schizodus obscurus* (J. Sowerby, 1821; *Axinus*) (Pattison 1970: 149–154, pl. 21, fig. 12, pl. 22, figs 1–3).

portlockii, Amphidesma — T. Brown, 1849-F: 224, pl. 91, fig. 40. New species based on *Venus carbonaria* J. De C. Sowerby, 1840, of Portlock, 1843 (pp. 438–439, pl. 36, fig. 8, as *Amphidesma*). — Type locality: Tyrone, Ireland; Clogher; limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: would be Portlock’s material. — Current status: synonym of *Protoschizodus axiniformis* (Portlock, 1843; *Venus* ?) (Hind 1898: 228–229, pl. 17, figs 10, 13–14, 16–19), now *Schizodus axiniformis* (Portlock, 1843), because *Protoschizodus* de Koninck, 1885, is considered to be a synonym of *Schizodus* W. King, 1845.

pucillus, Axinus — T. Brown, 1841a: 66, pl. 6, fig. 32; 1849-F: 195, pl. 79, fig. 10; Errata: change to *A. pusillus*. — Type locality: Newtown, Manchester, England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material:

MM LL.2851, holotype? (Nudds 1992: 84). — Current status: synonym of *Schizodus obscurus* (J. Sowerby, 1821; *Axinus*) (Pattison 1970: 149–154, pl. 21, fig. 12, pl. 22, figs 1–3).

pusillus, *Axinus* — see: *pucillus*, *Axinus*

undatus, *Axinus* — T. Brown, 1841a: 65–66, pl. 6, fig. 31; 1849-F: 195, pl. 79, fig. 9. — Type locality: Newtown, Manchester, England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Schizodus obscurus* (J. Sowerby, 1821; *Axinus*) (Pattison 1970: 149–154, pl. 21, fig. 12, pl. 22, figs 1–3).

Unionidae Rafinesque, 1820

contorta, *Anodon cygneus* — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 81, pl. 30, figs 7–8; 1845: 106, pl. 18, figs 1–2. — Type locality: Smedley Hill at Repton, Burton-upon-Trent, Westmoreland, England; Thomas Glover. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Anodonta anatina* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mytilus*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 331–332). — Current status: synonym of *Anodonta cygnea* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mytilus*) (Vinarski & Kantor 2016: 37).

hamatus, *Pachyodon* — T. Brown, 1843a: 395, pl. 16*, fig. 6; 1849-F: 179, pl. 72*, fig. 18, as *Unio* “*humatus*”. — Type locality: Gristhorpe Bay, North Yorkshire, England; Oxford Clay [Formation]; J. Fleming; J. Fleming collection. — Type age: Jurassic (Callovian-Oxfordian). — Type material: MM L.10502, holotype. — Current status: “*Unio*” *hamatus* (T. Brown, 1843) (Jackson 1952: 71), but generic and family affiliations uncertain.

humatus, *Unio* — see: *hamatus*, *Pachyodon*

subrhombea, *Anodon cygneus* — T. Brown, 1845: 104–105, pl. 26, figs 3–4. — Type locality: Irwell, near Manchester, England; Samuel Gibson; Dinting Vale, near Glossop, Derbyshire, England; Robert Darbishire. Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Anodonta anatina* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mytilus*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 331). — Current status: synonym of *Anodonta cygnea* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mytilus*) (Freshwater Mussel Database).

Margaritiferidae Henderson, 1929 [1910]

arcuata, *Alasmodon margaritiferus* — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 84, pl. 30*, fig. 3; 1845: 115, pl. 23, fig. 3, *non Alasmodonta arcuata* Barnes, 1823. — Type locality: River Derwent, Bassenthwaite, Cumberland, below Ouse Bridge, Cumbria, England. — Type age: Recent. — Type material:

not located. — Current status: synonym of *Margaritifera margaritifera* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mya*) (Simpson 1900: 675; Simpson 1914: 515).

olivacea, *Alasmodon margaritiferus* — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 84, pl. 30*, fig. 1; 1845: 115, pl. 23, fig. 1. — Type locality: Smedley Hill, in the Leven, below Lake Windermere, Westmoreland, England; Thomas Glover. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Margaritifera margaritifera* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Mya*) (Simpson 1900: 675; Simpson 1914: 515).

vetustus, *Pachyodon* — T. Brown, 1843a: 395, pl. 16*, fig. 7; 1849-F: 181, pl. 72*, fig. 19, as *Alasmodon* “*vetustus*”. Type locality: Gristhorpe, North Yorkshire, England; Dr. J. Fleming; [Cornbrash Formation?]. — Type age: Jurassic (Bathonian-Callovian?). — Type material: MM L.10501, holotype. — Current status: synonym of *Margaritifera distorta* (W. Bean, 1836; *Unio*) (Jackson 1911; Jackson 1952: 71), but generic and family affiliations uncertain.

vetustus, *Alasmodon* — see: *vetustus*, *Pachyodon*.

Pandoridae Rafinesque, 1815

Trutina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: I, pl. 13. Type species (M): *Trutina solenoidea* T. Brown, 1827. — Current status: synonym of *Pandora* Bruguière, 1797 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

solenoidea, *Trutina* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 13, fig. 5, in the synonymy of *Solen pinna* Montagu, 1803; 1844-C2: 104. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Pandora albida* (Röding, 1798; *Calopodium*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 344, pl. 279).

Thraciidae Stoliczka, 1870 [1839]

dubia, *Thracia* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 229, pl. 93, figs 7–9. — Type locality: Bognor, Sussex, England; London Clay [Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Ypresian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

ovalis, *Anatina* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: I, pl. 11, fig. 4; 1844-C2: 110, pl. 44, fig. 4, as *Thracia ovata*, subsequent incorrect spelling. — Type locality: Colorcot [Cullercoats], England; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Preoccupies *Thracia ovalis* (Stutchbury, 1830; *Anatina*), which was renamed *Thracia (Eximiothracia) stutchburyi* M. Huber, 2010. — Current status: synonym of *Thracia villosiuscula* (MacGillivray, 1827; *Anatina*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 347, pl. 281).

ovata, *Thracia* — T. Brown, 1844 — see: *ovalis*, *Anatina*.

Periplomatidae Dall, 1895

Bontaea — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 106, *ex* Leach ms, listed in the synonymy of *Mya praetenuis* “Montagu” [Pulteney, 1799]. — Current status: can be listed in the synonymy of *Cochlodesma* Couthouy, 1839 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

Cuspidariidae Dall, 1886

brevirostris, Anatina — T. Brown, 1829: 11, pl. 1, figs 1–4; 1844-C2: 110, pl. 44, figs 11–14, as *Thracia*. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland; James Gerard. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Cuspidaria cuspidata* (Olivi, 1792; *Tellina*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 348, pl. 282).

Lyonsiidae P. Fischer, 1887

Hiatella — T. Brown, 1827-C1: i, pl. 16, *non* Bosc, 1801. Type species (M): *Mya striata* Montagu, 1816. *Myatella* T. Brown, 1833, replacement name. — Current status: synonym of *Lyonsia* W. Turton, 1822.

Lionsia — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 137. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Lyonsia* W. Turton, 1822.

Magdala — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 11; 1844-C2: 111, pl. 44, figs 1–2, 10, *ex* Leach ms. Type species (M): *Magdala striata* T. Brown, 1827, *ex* Leach ms. — Current status: synonym of *Lyonsia* W. Turton, 1822.

Myatella — T. Brown, 1833: 142–143, pl. 16, figs 12, 30; 1844-C2: 111. Replacement name for *Hiatella* T. Brown, 1827, *non* Bosc, 1801.

montagui, Myatella — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 111. Replacement name for *Myatella striata* (T. Brown, 1827).

pellucida, Mya — T. Brown, 1818a: 505, pl. 24, fig. 1; 1827: pl. 11, figs 1–2, as a synonym of *Magdala striata* T. Brown, 1827. — Type locality: Bantry Bay, Ireland; Hutchins; Taylor collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Lyonsia norwegica* (Gmelin, 1791; *Mya*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 345, pl. 279).

striata, Magdala — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 11, figs 1–2, 10, *ex* Leach ms. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland; James Gerard. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Brown may have given this name precedence over his *Mya pellucida* because he thought that Leach had invented that name earlier. He regarded *Mya striata* Montagu, 1816, to belong in his genus *Myatella*. — Current status: synonym of *Lyonsia norwegica* (Gmelin, 1791; *Mya*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 345, pl. 279).

Pholadomyidae W. King, 1844

compressa, Pholadomya — T. Brown, 1849-F: 232, pl. 95, fig. 5, *non* Agassiz, 1845. — Type locality: Kettering, Northamptonshire, England; great oolite [Rutland Formation?]. — Type age: Jurassic (Bajocian-Bathonian). — Type material: MM LL.371, holotype (Jackson 1952: 72). — Current status: uncertain.

phillipsii, Pholadomya — T. Brown, 1849-F: 232, pl. 95, fig. 11. New species based on *Pholadomya murchisoni* J. De C. Sowerby, 1827, as figured by J. Phillips (1829: 189, pl. 7, fig. 9). — Type locality: Scarborough, England; Cornbrash Formation. — Type age: Jurassic (Bathonian-Callovian). — Type material: would be Phillips' material. — Current status: uncertain.

Pleuromyidae Zittel, 1895

inflata, Petricola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 220, pl. 90, figs 1–3. — Type locality: Kirby Tunnel beyond Coventry, England. — Type age: Jurassic. — Type material: MM LL.372, holotype. — Current status: *Pleuromya inflata* (T. Brown, 1849) (Jackson 1952: 71–72).

Lucinidae J. Fleming, 1828

dubia, Lucina — T. Brown, 1841b: 228, pl. 7, fig. 78. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: Lucinidae probably wrong.

trinitea, Mya — T. Brown, 1818b: 456, pl. 9, fig. 3. — Type locality: Sand banks at La Trinité, W. side of the Plain of Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Myrtea spinifera* (Montagu, 1803; *Venus*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 354, pl. 286).

Thyasiridae Dall, 1900 [1895]

Bequania — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 99, *ex* Leach ms, in synonymy with *Cryptodon* W. Turton, 1822. Type species (M): *Cryptodon flexuosus* (Montagu, 1803; *Tellina*). — Current status: synonym of *Thyasira* Lamarck, 1818.

Binghami — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 31, figs 17–18; 1844-C2: 142. Type species (M): *B. paradoxus* T. Brown, 1827. — Current status: an indeterminate thyasirid genus and species (Kamenev pers. comm., January 5, 2025).

dubius, Axinus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 194, pl. 79, fig. 8. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; sandstone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM, holotype (Jackson 1952: 63), not located. Preoccupies *Axinus dubius* Dautzenberg & H.

Fischer, 1897, a synonym of *Leptaxinus incrassatus* (Jeffreys, 1876; *Axinus*). — Current status: uncertain.

latus, *Axinus* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 194, pl. 79, fig. 4. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England; sandstone. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type age: MM L.10514, holotype (Jackson 1952: 63). — Current status: uncertain.

minimus, *Axinus* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 195, pl. 79, figs 2–3. — Type locality: Newtown, Manchester; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Schizodus obscurus* (J. Sowerby, 1821; *Axinus*) (MolluscaBase).

paradoxus, *Binghami* — T. Brown, ii, 1827: pl. 31, figs 17–18; 1844-C2: 142, pl. 23, figs 17–18. — Type locality: Leith Roads, Scotland; dredged by Bingham; Bingham collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: indeterminate thyasirid genus and species (Kamenev pers. comm., January 5, 2025).

rotundatus, *Axinus* — T. Brown, 1841a: 65, pl. 6, fig. 29; 1849-F: 195, pl. 79, fig. 1. — Type locality: Newtown, Manchester, England; New Red Sandstone [Manchester Marls Formation]. — Type age: Permian (Guadalupian-Lopingian). — Type material: not located. Synonym of *Schizodus obscurus* (J. Sowerby, 1821; *Axinus*) (Pattison 1970: 149–152, pl. 21, fig. 12, pl. 22, figs 1–3). — Current status: *Schizodus rotundatus* (T. Brown, 1841) (Muromtseva & Guskov 1984: 81, pl. 35, figs 5–7, pl. 36, figs 17–18, pl. 39, fig. 4).

undulata, *Mya* — T. Brown, 1818b: 456–457, pl. 9, fig. 13. — Type locality: La Trinité, W. side of the Plain of Nice, France, sand banks; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Thyasira* sp. (herein).

Cardiniidae Zittel, 1881

scutula, *Cardinia* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 213–214, pl. 88, figs 13–14. New species based on *Unio concinna* J. Sowerby, 1819, of Stutchbury, 1842 (p. 485, pl. 10, figs 15–16). — Type locality: Langar, Nottinghamshire, Saltford & Weston, near Bath, England. — Type age: Jurassic (Early). — Type material: would be Stutchbury's material. — Current status: uncertain.

Carditidae Férussac, 1822

acuticosta, *Venericardia* — T. Brown, 1849-F: 203, pl. 83, fig. 32. — Type locality: Bracklesham Bay, Stubbington, Hampshire, & Barton, Sussex, England; London clay

[Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — Type material: not located. *Venericardia carinata* J. Sowerby, 1820 (p. 106, pl. 259, fig. 2) cited in synonymy. This is a puzzling entry in Brown (1849) in that Sowerby's species is not a junior homonym, Brown cited Sowerby's locality in addition to two of his own, and he did not point to any differences. — Current status: presumably synonym of *Venericardia carinata* J. Sowerby, 1820.

Astartidae d'Orbigny, 1844 [1840]

Mactrina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 16, fig. 25; 1844-C2: 108–109; 1849-F: 226–227. Type species (M): *Mactra triangularis* Montagu, 1803. — Current status: synonym of *Goodallia* W. Turton, 1822, which has the same type species (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

Mactroidea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii. Alternate spelling for *Mactrina*. — Current status: synonym of *Goodallia* W. Turton, 1822, which has the same type species (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

convexiuscula, Crassina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 18, fig. 7. — Type locality: “Color Cots” [Cullercoats], Northumberland, England; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta montagui* (Dillwyn, 1817; *Venus*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 344; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 342, pls 277).

corrugata, Crassina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 16, fig. 24; 1844-C2: 96, pl. 40, fig. 24. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta borealis* Schumacher, 1817 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 341–342, pls 275–276).

depressa, Crassina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 18, fig. 2; 1844-C2: 96, pl. 38, fig. 2. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta borealis* Schumacher, 1817 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 341–342, pls 275–276).

elliptica, Crassina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 18, fig. 3; 1844-C2: 96, pl. 38, fig. 3. — Type locality: Firth of Forth & Greenock, Scotland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Tridonta elliptica* (T. Brown, 1827) (Huber 2010: 247; Alf *et al.* 2020: 342, pl. 276).

multicostata, Crassina — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a:

104–105, pl. 1, fig. 20, *ex* Smith ms. — Type locality: North Sea, Sweden & Norway — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta montagui* (Dillwyn, 1817; *Venus*) (MolluscaBase; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 342, pls 277).

obliqua*, *Crassina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 18, fig. 6. Color Cots [Cullercoats], Northumberland, England; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta montagui* (Dillwyn, 1817; *Venus*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 344; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 342, pls 277).

obliqua*, *Astarte — T. Brown, 1849-F: 211, pl. 61***, fig. 27. — Type locality: Barton & Dundry, England; Inferior Oolite [Group]. — Type age: Jurassic (Aalenian-Bajocian). — Type material: not located. *Astarte planata* J. Sowerby, 1820 (p. 103, pl. 257) was cited in synonymy. It is not clear what Brown intended to do here. Sowerby's name is not a junior homonym, and whereas Brown cited different localities than those of Sowerby, he did not point to any differences. — Current status: synonym of *Astarte planata* J. Sowerby, 1820.

ovata*, *Crassina — T. Brown, 1829: 12, pl. 1, fig. 9; 1844-C2: 96, pl. 38, figs “11–12” [in his Errata: figs changed to 12–13], *non Crassina ovata* J. Phillips, 1829 (p. 128, pl. 3, fig. 25, from the Coralline Oolite at Malton, Wilts & Oxon). — Type locality: Helensburgh, mouth of the Clyde, Scotland; Henry Witham; James Gerard collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: there is a lot in the NMS that may contain some of Brown's original specimens, but it appears to be a combination of material from multiple sources. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta elliptica* (T. Brown, 1827) (Forbes & Hanley 1848: 459–461, pl. 30, fig. 8; Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 242; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 342, pl. 276).

striata*, *Crassina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 18, fig. 8; 1844-C2: 96–97, pl. 38, figs 6–8, *non* Nilsson, 1822. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta montagui* (Dillwyn, 1817; *Venus*) (Forbes & Hanley 1848: 464–467, pl. 30, figs 1–3, although at that time this species was known as *Astarte compressa* (Montagu, 1808; *Venus*), a junior primary homonym (*non Venus compressa* Linnaeus, 1771) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 342, pl. 277).

triangulata*, *Astarte — T. Brown, 1849-F: 212, pl. 86, fig. 9. New species based on one of the four figures *Astarte rugatus* J. Sowerby, 1821 (p. 13, pl. 316, fig. 3). — Type locality: Highgate, England; London Clay [Formation].

— Type age: Eocene (Ypresian). — Type material: would be Sowerby's material.

withami*, *Crassina — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 105, pl. 1, figs 24–25, *ex* Smith ms. — Type locality: Bridlington Quay, Yorkshire, England; marine alluvia; H. Witham; Rothesay Bay, Scotland; dredged by J. Smith. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta borealis* Schumacher, 1817 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD, but credited to J. Smith; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 341–342, pls 275–276).

compressa*, *Crassina — “T. Brown”, 1827-C1: pl. 18, figs 4–5. Listed by Kantor & Sysoev (2005: 343) as if it were a Brown species, it had its origin as *Venus compressa* Montagu, 1808, *non* Linnaeus, 1771, a synonym of *Tridonta montagui* (Dillwyn, 1817; *Venus*) (also listed by Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 344).

gairensis*, *Astarte — “T. Brown”, 1844-C2: 96, *ex* Nicol ms. The name was listed by Brown here in connection with what he had described and figured as *Crassina ovata* in 1829, no doubt realizing that the latter was a homonym of the same name by J. Phillips, 1829 (see above). However, this presumable replacement name had appeared a year earlier in Morris (1843: 79), also *ex* Nicol ms, who simultaneously listed Phillips' species, so it should be credited to him. Brown later figured the species from the Pleistocene under this new name (T. Brown, 1849-F: 212, pl. 87, fig. 14). Kantor & Sysoev (2005: 343) credited *Astarte gairensis* to J. Smith (1839a: 72, 73, 90), but it was there, as a *nomen nudum*, and as *A. “gairensis”*. — Current status: synonym of *Tridonta elliptica* (T. Brown, 1827).

Carbonicolidae L. R. Cox, 1932

Note: *Pachyodon* Stutchbury, 1842, is *non* Meyer, 1838; the generic name now in use for many of the following species is *Carbonicola* McCoy, 1855 (ICZN Opinion 292, 1954).

agrestis*, *Pachyodon — T. Brown, 1843a: 393, pl. 16, fig. 11; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 20, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Sheden [Shedden Clough, near Cliviger, Lancashire], England; ironstone shale; Thomas M. Embleton collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola acuta* (J. Sowerby, 1813; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 50–55, pl. 3, figs 1–12, pl. 4, figs 8–17, pl. 5, figs 1, 3–37, 39; pl. 6, figs 1–42).

aldamii*, *Pachyodon — T. Brown, 1843a: 394, pl. 16*, fig. 3; 1849-F: 179, pl. 73, fig. 18, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Whitehaven, Cumbria, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Carbonicola aldamii* (T. Brown, 1843).

- amygdala, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 392, pl. 16, fig. 3; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 4, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Low Moor, Yorkshire, England; ironstone shale. — Type age: Jurassic (Early). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.
- antiquus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 394–395, pl. 16*, fig. 4, *non* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1828; *Unio*). — Type locality: Low Moor, near Bradford, England; ironstone shale; Thomas M. Embleton & Samuel Gibson collections. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. *Unio senex* T. Brown, replacement name. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola acuta* (J. Sowerby, 1813; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 50–55, pl. 3, figs 1–12, pl. 4, figs 8–17, pl. 5, figs 1, 3–37, 39; pl. 6, figs 1–42).
- bipennis, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 391–392, pl. 15, fig. 9; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 27, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Low Moor, Yorkshire, England; ironstone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola aquilina* (J. De C. Sowerby, 184; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 69–75, pl. 5, fig. 2, pl. 9, figs 1–10, 12–37, pl. 10, figs 1–42, pl. 11, figs 31–33).
- blaydsii, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 394, pl. 16*, fig. 2; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 2, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Middleton, near Leeds, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola turgida* (T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 66–68, pl. 8, figs 8–25).
- dawsoni, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 392, pl. 15, fig. 10; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 3, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Low Moor, near Bradford; West Yorkshire, England; Gibson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola subconstrictus* (J. Sowerby, 1812; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 59–61, pl. 6, fig. 44, pl. 7, figs 5–15).
- discrepans, *Unio*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 181, pl. 88, fig. 24. — Type locality: Bradford, Yorkshire, England; coal measures. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola robusta* (J. De C. Sowerby, 1840) (Hind 1896: 174).
- dubius, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 392, pl. 16, fig. 5; 1849-F: 177–178, pl. 73, fig. 13, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Newcastle-upon-Tyne, England; coal shale; Robertson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola turgida* (T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 66–68, pl. 8, figs 8–25).
- embletoni, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 393, pl. 16, fig. 9; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 6, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Middleton, near Leeds, Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola subconstrictus* (J. Sowerby, 1812; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 59–61, pl. 6, fig. 44, pl. 7, figs 5–15).
- exoletus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 392, pl. 16, fig. 4; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 25, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Whitehaven, Cumbria, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola acuta* (J. Sowerby, 1813; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 50–55, pl. 3, figs 1–12, pl. 4, figs 8–17, pl. 5, figs 1, 3–37, 39; pl. 6, figs 1–42).
- gerardi, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 390–391, pl. 15, figs 1–2; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 23–24, as *Unio* [Errata: fig. 24 omitted from text]. — Type locality: Dalkeith, Midlothian, Scotland; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.
- heyii, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 393, pl. 16, fig. 10; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 1, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Sheden [Shedden Clough, near Cliviger, Lancashire], England; ironstone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola subconstrictus* (J. Sowerby, 1812; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 59–61, pl. 6, fig. 44, pl. 7, figs 5–15).
- lateralis, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 391, pl. 15, fig. 3; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 26, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Whitehaven, Cumbria, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola aquilina* (J. De C. Sowerby, 184; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 69–75, pl. 5, fig. 2, pl. 9, figs 1–10, 12–37, pl. 10, figs 1–42, pl. 11, figs 31–33).
- levedensis, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 395, pl. 16*, fig. 8; 1849-F: 179, pl. 73, fig. 30, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Middleton, near Leeds Yorkshire, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola acuta* (J. Sowerby, 1813; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 50–55, pl. 3, figs 1–12, pl. 4, figs 8–17, pl. 5, figs 1, 3–37, 39; pl. 6, figs 1–42).
- nanus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 392, pl. 16, fig. 1; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 7, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Middletown, near Leeds Yorkshire, England; Thomas M. Embleton & Samuel Gibson collections. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Carbonicola similis* (T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 76–78, pl. 11, figs 6–13, 15, 17–23, 25–28; Hind, 1898: 252).

- nucleus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 394, pl. 16*, fig. 1; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 8, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Woodhall, N. side of Pentland Hills, near Edinburgh, Scotland; coal shale; Thomas M. Embleton collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: suppressed ICZN Opinion 858 (1968) in favour of *Carbonicola antiqua* Hind, 1894.
- polmontensis, *Unio*** — T. Brown, 1849-F: 180, pl. 78, figs 32–33. New species based on *Unio* sp. of Rhind (1838: 167, pl. 2, figs c-d). — Type locality: Polmont, near Falkirk, Scotland; W. Rhind; coal shale; Rhind collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: would be Rhind's material. — Current status: *Carbonicola polmontensis* (T. Brown, 1849) (Hind 1894: 58–59, pl. 7, figs 1–4).
- pyramidalus, *Unio*** — see: *pyramidalus, Pachyodon*.
- pyramidalus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 396, pl. 16*, fig. 9; 1849-F: 179, pl. 73, fig. 19, as *Unio* “*pyramidalus*”. — Type locality: Low Moor & Woodhall, near Edinburgh, Scotland; ironstone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Carbonicola pyramidata* (T. Brown, 1843).
- rhindii, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 392, pl. 16, fig. 2; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 5, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Polmont, Stirlingshire, Scotland; coal shale; William Rhind collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola ovalis* (Martin, 1809; *Mya*) (Hind 1894: 56–58, pl. 4, figs 18–22, pl. 5, fig. 38).
- rugosus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 391, pl. 15, figs 6–7; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, figs 14–15, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Sheden [Shedden Clough, near Cliviger, Lancashire], England; S. Gibson; Gibson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Carbonicola rugosa* (T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 1894: 49, pl. 1, figs 7, 8–8a; Hind 1898: 251).
- similis, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 393–394, pl. 16, fig. 12; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 9, as *Unio*. Middleton, near Leeds, Yorkshire, England; coal shale; W. C. Williamson collection. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Current status: *Carbonicola similis* (T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 76–78, pl. 11, figs 6–13, 15, 17–23, 25–28; Hind 1898: 252).
- smithii, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 393, pl. 16, figs 7–8; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, figs 10–11, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Sheden [Shedden Clough, near Cliviger, Lancashire], England; ironstone shale; Thomas M. Embleton & Samuel Gibson collections. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: —
- ous.** — Type material: not located. — Current status: —
- Current status:** synonym of *Carbonicola subconstrictus* (J. Sowerby, 1812; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 59–61, pl. 6, fig. 44, pl. 7, figs 5–15).
- subrotundus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 391, pl. 15, fig. 8; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, fig. 22, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Oldham, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Carbonicola subrotunda* (Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 65–66, pl. 8, figs 3–7; Hind 1898: 252).
- subtriangularis, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 393, pl. 16, fig. 6; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, fig. 12, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Coalbrookdale, Shropshire, England; ironstone shale. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola subconstrictus* (J. Sowerby, 1812; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 59–61, pl. 6, fig. 44, pl. 7, figs 5–15).
- sulcatus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 391, pl. 15, figs 4–5; 1849-F: 177, pl. 73, figs 28–29, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Whitehaven, Cumbria, England; coal shale. — Type age: Carboniferous (Late). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola aquilina* (J. De C. Sowerby, 184; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 69–75, pl. 5, fig. 2, pl. 9, figs 1–10, 12–37, pl. 10, figs 1–42, pl. 11, figs 31–33).
- transversus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 395, pl. 16*, fig. 5; 1849-F: 178–179, pl. 73, fig. 21, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Middleton, near Leeds, Yorkshire, England; coal shale; J. Fleming collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Carbonicola acuta* (J. Sowerby, 1813; *Unio*) (Hind 1894: 50–55, pl. 3, figs 1–12, pl. 4, figs 8–17, pl. 5, figs 1, 3–37, 39; pl. 6, figs 1–42).
- turgidus, *Pachyodon*** — T. Brown, 1843a: 394, pl. 16, figs 13–14; 1849-F: 178, pl. 73, figs 16–17, as *Unio*. — Type locality: Wakefield, West Yorkshire, England; coal shale; William Rhind collection. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Carbonicola turgida* (T. Brown, 1843) (Hind 1894: 66–68, pl. 8, figs 8–25).
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- variabilis, *Posidoniella*** — Hind, 1897: 100–101, pl. 7, figs 7–9, ex T. Brown ms. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). Based on specimens in the MM (L.10227) labeled by Brown as “*Mytilus variabilis*”.

Cardiidae Lamarck, 1809

- discrepans, *Cardium*** — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 21, fig. 9, non Basterot, 1825. — Type locality: Montrose, Scot-

land; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain.

tenuis, *Cardium* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata — corrected to “*tenue*”], ii, pl. 22, fig. 4; 1844-C2: 88, pl. 35, fig. 8. — Type locality: Lough Strangford, Ireland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: probable synonym of *Cerastoderma glaucum* (Bruguière, 1789; *Cardium*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 365, pl. 299).

tigerina, *Tellina* — T. Brown, 1818b: 458, pl. 9, fig. 11. — Type locality: sand banks at La Trinité, W. side of the Plain of Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Fulvia fragilis* (Forsskål, 1775; *Cardium*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 365–366, pl. 300).

zonatum, *Cardium* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 21, fig. 8; 1844-C2: 88, pl. 35, fig. 8. — Type locality: Seaton, Devon, England; John Hancock; Devon, England; Goodall; Goodall, Hancock & Lady Jardine collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Cerastoderma glaucum* (Bruguière, 1789; *Cardium*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 365, pl. 299).

Sportellidae Dall, 1899

lactea, *Mastra* — T. Brown, 1818b: 460, pl. 9, fig. 9, *non* Gmelin, 1791, *nec* Poli, 1895. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Sportella recondita* (P. Fischer, in Folin 1872; *Scintilla*) (herein; figured in Cossignani & Ardo-vini 2011: 448).

Lasaeidae J.E. Gray, 1842

Lasaea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 20, figs 18–19; 1844-C2: 93, *ex* Leach ms. Type species (M): *Lasaea rubra* (Montagu, 1803; *Cardium*). — Current status: valid genus (Huber 2015: 140–143).

Tellimya — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 14, figs 10–21; 1844-C2: 106–107. Type species (SD Gray 1847): *Mya ferruginosa* Montagu, 1808. — Current status: valid genus (Huber 2015: 151–152).

elliptica, *Tellimya* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 14, figs 16–17; 1844-C2: 106–107, pl. 42, figs “16–17” [Errata: actually fig. 19], in synonymy of *Mya ferruginosa* Montagu, 1808. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tellimya ferruginosa* (Montagu, 1808; *Mya*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5

on CD; species figured in Cossignani & Ardo-vini 2011: 446).

glabra, *Tellimya* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 42, figs 18–19; 1844-C2: 107, pl. 42, figs 20–21; 1849-F: 225, pl. 90, fig. 32, as *Montacuta glabra*. Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham; Bingham & Lady Jardine collections. — Type age: Recent. Also Sutton, Suffolk, England; coral crag [Pliocene] (1849-F). — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tellimya ferruginosa* (Montagu, 1808; *Mya*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Cossignani & Ardo-vini 2011: 446).

lactea, *Tellimya* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 14, figs 10–11; 1844-C2: 106, pl. 42, figs 10–11. — Type locality: Devon, England; W. E. Leach; NHMUK. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803; *Mya*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 348; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 357, pl. 288).

ovata, *Tellimya* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 14, figs 20–21. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; T. Brown; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Tellimya ferruginosa* (Montagu, 1808; *Mya*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Cossignani & Ardo-vini 2011: 446).

punctatus, *Mya* — T. Brown, 1818b: 459, pl. 9, fig. 5. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain, but seems to belong in this family.

punctura, *Psammobia* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 16, fig. 7. In synonymy of *Solen squamosus* Montagu, 1803. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Lepton squamosum* (Montagu, 1803; *Solen*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 357–358, pl. 288).

tenuis, *Tellimya* — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 14, figs 12–13; 1833: 138, pl. 17, fig. 14; 1844-C2: 106, pl. 42, figs 12–13. — Type locality: Newbigging, Scotland; Walter Calverley Trevelyan; Wallington collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Kellia suborbicularis* (Montagu, 1803; *Mya*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 348; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 357, pl. 288).

Mastridae Lamarck, 1809

Psammophila — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 12, fig. 1; 1844-C2: 109, in synonymy of *Lutraria* Lamarck, 1799. Type species (M): *Lutraria solenoides* Lamarck, 1801. Intro-

duced in synonymy of *Lutraria*, but available under ICZN Code Art. 11.6.1 because it was subsequently used as valid before 1961 (Thiele 1934). — Current status: synonym of *Lutraria* Lamarck, 1799 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

elliptica, Mactra — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 15, fig. 6; 1844-C2: 108, pl. 41, fig. 6. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Spisula elliptica* (T. Brown, 1827) (Huber 2010: 448; Alf *et al.* 2020: 385, pl. 232).

striata, Mactra — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 15, fig. 7; T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 106, pl. 1, fig. 22; 1844-C2: 108, pl. 41, fig. 10; 1849-F: 226, pl. 91, fig. 42, *non* Gmelin, 1791, *nec* Spengler, 1802. — Type locality: Lough Strangford, Ireland; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Spisula subtruncata* (da Costa, 1778; *Trigonella*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 393–394; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 386, pl. 324).

triangulata, Mactra — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 15, figs 11–12. — Type locality: Seaton, Devon, England; W. C. Trevelyan; Wallington collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: probably synonym of *Mactra glabrata* Linnaeus, 1767 (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 384, pl. 321).

Sphaeriidae Deshayes, 1855 [1820]

Piscidium — T. Brown, 1849-F: 209–210, pl. 86, figs 10–11, 27. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Pisidium* C. Pfeiffer, 1821.

citrina, Cyclas — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 132, pl. 39, fig. 37 [cited in text as pl. “37”]. — Type locality: The Leven, below Lake Windermere, Westmoreland, England; Thomas Glover. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Sphaerium corneum* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Tellina*) (Vinarski & Kantor 2016: 85).

pusilla, Tellina — T. Brown, in Leach & T. Brown, 1823: 408, *non* Lamarck, 1806, *nec* W. Turton, 1819; 1827-C1: ii, pl. 17, fig. 15, as *Cyclas*. — Type locality: none given. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. All preoccupy *Tellina pusilla* R. A. Philippi, 1836. — Current status: synonym of *Sphaerium corneum* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Tellina*) (Kennard & B.B. Woodward 1926: 302–304).

Tellinidae Blainville, 1814

Arcopagia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 16, figs 8–10 (2 species), *ex* Leach ms. Type species (SD Herrmannsen,

1846): *Tellina crassa* Pennant, 1777. — Current status: valid genus (Huber 2015: 258).

Bosempra — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 100, *ex* Leach ms, as *Bosempra squalida* “Leach” [Pulteney, 1799; *Tellina*], in synonymy with *Tellina depressa* “Maton & Rackett” [Gmelin, 1791]. — Current status: this genus was never subsequently used, and the genus and species involved are now known as *Bosemprella incarnata* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Tellina*). The genus can be listed in the synonymy of *Bosemprella* Huber, Langleit & Kreipl, in Huber 2015).

Limecola — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 101, *ex* Leach ms, in synonymy with *Tellina solidula* Pulteney, 1799, a synonym of *Macoma balthica* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Tellina*). — Current status: synonym of *Macoma* Leach, 1819.

elliptica, Tellina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 16, figs 20–21; 1844-C2: 101, pl. 40, figs 20–21, in synonymy with *Tellina planata* “Pennant” [Linnaeus, 1758], *non* *Tellina elliptica* Brocchi, 1814, *nec* Lamarck, 1818; all pre-occupy the later Scacchi, 1833. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; Bingham. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Peronaea planata* (Linnaeus, 1758) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 375, pl. 311).

jugosa, Tellina — T. Brown, 1818a: 506–508, pl. 24, fig. 2; 1827-C1: ii, pl. 16, figs 4–6, as *Psammobia*; 1844-C2: 102, pl. 40, figs 4–6. — Type locality: Bantry Bay, Ireland; Hutchins; Taylor collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Gastrana fragilis* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Tellina*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 357; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 372, pl. 308).

obsoleta, Tellina — T. Brown, 1818b: 459–460, pl. 9, figs 7–8. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary & Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Arcopella balaustina* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Tellina*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 369–370, pl. 305).

ovata, Arcopagia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 16, figs 9–10; 1844-C2: 99–100, pl. 40, figs 9–10. — Type locality: Newbigging, Scotland; W. C. Trevelyan; Wallington collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Arcopagia crassa* (Pennant, 1777; *Tellina*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 369, pl. 305).

pellucida, Tellina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 16, fig. 22; 1844-C2: 101, pl. 40, fig. 22, *non* Spengler, 1798, *nec* Brocchi, 1814. — Type locality: Seaton, Devon, England; W. C. Trevelyan; Wallington collection. — Type age:

Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain, probably not Tellinidae.

prismaticum, Amphidesma — T. Brown, 1849-F: 224, pl. 91, fig. 47. — Type locality: Sutton, Suffolk, London, England; coral crag [Coralline Crag Formation]. — Type age: Pliocene. — Type material: not located. From its shape, this is more likely a member of the Tellinidae than the Semelidae.

proxima, Tellina — T. Brown, in J. Smith, 1839a: 105–106, pl. 1, fig. 21, *ex* Smith ms. Also in G.B. Sowerby I, in J.E. Gray & G.B. Sowerby I, 1839 (p. 154, pl. 44, fig. 4), *ex* Brown ms. Neither work has an exact date in 1839. — Type locality: Dalmuir & Helensburgh, Scotland; J. Smith. — Type age: Recent & Late Pliocene. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Macoma calcarea* (Gmelin, 1791; *Tellina*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 373, pls 309–310).

Psammobiidae J. Fleming, 1828

Gobraeus — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 102, *ex* Leach ms, listed in the synonymy of *Psammobia vespertina* (Gmelin, 1791; *Solen*), a synonym of *Gari depressa* (Pennant, 1777; *Tellina*). — Current status: synonym of *Gari* Schumacher, 1817 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

Semelidae Stoliczka, 1870 [1825]

striata, Mya — T. Brown, 1818b: 456, pl. 9, fig. 12, *non* Montagu, 1816. — Type locality: sand banks at La Trinité, W. side of the Plain of Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Ervilia castanea* (Montagu, 1803; *Donax*) (herein; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 380–381, pl. 317).

truncata, Ligula — T. Brown, 1827-C1: I, pl. 14, fig. 4 [only in Systematic Index, not in pl. expl.]; 1844-C2: 106, pl. 42, fig. 4, as *Amphidesma*. — Type locality: Greenock, Scotland; Stewart Ker; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: probable synonym of *Abra tenuis* (Montagu, 1803; *Mactra*), associated but not synonymized with this species by Forbes & Hanley (1848: 325) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 380, pl. 317).

Solecurtidae d'Orbigny, 1846

Azor — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 113, *ex* Leach ms, *non* Azor J. De C. Sowerby, 1824 [Tellinidae], “*ex* Leach ms”. Type species (M): *Solen antiquatus* Pulteney, 1799, a synonym of *Solen chamasolen* da Costa, 1778. Unnecessarily renamed *Zozia* Winckworth, 1930 (p. 15). — Current

status: synonym of *Azorinus* Récluz, 1869, which originated as an unjustified emendation, but later treated as a valid name (Rehder 1944: 22), and has the same type species.

Ungulinidae J.E. Gray, 1854

Note: *Mysia* Lamarck, 1818, is a genus in the Veneridae. Brown (1827) and others used it for species in the Ungulinidae, but this is not a separate Brown genus, merely a misuse.

densus, Tellina — T. Brown, 1818b: 459, pl. 9, fig. 6. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Diplodonta rotundata* (Montagu, 1803; *Tellina*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 391, pl. 328).

Veneridae Rafinesque, 1815

Clausina — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 19, figs 12–13. Type species (M): *Venus reflexa* Montagu, 1808, a synonym of *Venus casina* Linnaeus, 1758. Preoccupies *Clausina* Jeffreys, 1847, a synonym of *Mendicula* Iredale, 1924 [Thyasiridae]. — Current status: synonym of *Venus* Linnaeus, 1758 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

Cytheria — T. Brown, 1827-C1: [2, Errata], pl. 19, figs 2–4. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Cytherea* Lamarck, 1805.

Exoleta — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 20. Type species (T): *Dosinia exoleta* (Linnaeus, 1758). — Current status: synonym of *Dosinia* Scopoli, 1777 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

Ortygia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 19, *non* Boie, 1826 [Aves]. Type species (M): *Ortygia subcordata* T. Brown, 1827, *ex* Leach ms. — Current status: synonym of *Chamelea* Mörch, 1853 (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD).

Timoclea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 19. Type species (M): *T. ovata* (Pennant, 1777; *Venus*). — Current status: valid genus (Huber 2010: 369–371).

antiqua, Cytheraea — T. Brown, 1841b: 228, pl. 7, fig. 76. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: MM L.10245, holotype (Jackson 1952: 67). Oddly redescribed as *Schizodus antiquus* Hind (1898: 224–225, pl. 18, figs 24–27, pl. 19, figs 4–5). — Current status: *Schizodus antiquus* (T. Brown, 1841).

costata, Ortygia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 20, fig. 13; 1844-C2: 90, pl. 36, fig. 13, as *Venus*. — Type locality: Seaton, Devon, England; Lady Jardine collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Clausinella fasciata* (da Costa,

1778; *Pectunculus*) (Forbes 1838: 52; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 394–395, pl. 334).

distorta, Venus — T. Brown, 1818b: 460, pl. 9, fig. 10. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Irus irus* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Donax*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 396–397, pl. 336).

laevis, Petricola — T. Brown, 1849-F: 220, pl. 90, figs 4–5. — Type locality: Barrow[-in-Furness], Cumbria, England. — Type age: Jurassic. — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain; the rocks at this locality are older and non-fossiliferous (S. Schneider pers. comm., January 30, 2026).

minuta, Cytherea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 19, fig. 4; 1844-C2: 92, pl. 37, fig. 4. — Type locality: Dunbar, Scotland; T. Brown; Brown collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Gouldia minima* (Montagu, 1803; *Venus*) (Kantor & Sysoev 2005: 389; Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 396, pl. 336).

pennantii, Timoclea — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 19, fig. 11, *ex* Leach ms, in synonymy with *Venus ovata* “Montagu” [Pennant, 1777]. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Timoclea ovata* (Pennant, 1777; *Venus*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 400, pl. 341).

orbiculata, Exoleta — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 20, figs 2–3, in synonymy with *Exoleta exoleta* “Montagu” [*Venus exoleta* Linnaeus, 1758]. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Dosinia exoleta* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Venus*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 395, pl. 335).

parva, Artemis — T. Brown, 1841b: 228, pl. 7, fig. 77; 1849-F: 205, pl. 85, fig. 9. — Type locality: Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire, England. — Type age: Carboniferous (middle). — Type material: not located. — Current status: uncertain, but probably not Veneridae.

prideauxiana, Ortygia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 20, fig. 12; 1844-C2: 90, in synonymy with *Ortygia sulcata* T. Brown, 1827. — Type locality: Devon, England; Charles Prideaux. — Type age: Recent. — Current status: synonym of *Chamelea striatula* (da Costa, 1778; *Pectunculus*) (species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 394, pl. 334).

radula, Exoleta — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 20, fig. 1. — Type locality: Firth of Forth, Scotland; James Gerard; Gerard collection. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Dosinia exoleta* (Linnaeus, 1758; *Venus*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 395, pl. 335).

subcordata, Ortygia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 19, figs

14–15. — Type locality: None provided. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Chamelea striatula* (da Costa, 1778; *Pectunculus*) (MolluscaBase; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 394, pl. 334).

sulcata, Ortygia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: ii, pl. 20, fig. 12; 1844-C2: 90, pl. 36, fig. 12, as *Venus*. — Type locality: Devon, England; Charles Prideaux. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Chamelea striatula* (da Costa, 1778; *Pectunculus*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 394, pl. 334).

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moulinesii, Grateloupia — T. Brown, 1843b: 108, pl. 11, fig. 8. *Grateloupia* is an incorrect subsequent spelling of *Gratelupia* Desmoulin, 1828, that began before Brown in 1830. “Known only in the fossil state”. This was listed in Sherborn (1925: 1884) as if it were a Brown species, but it had its origin as *Gratelupia moulinesii* I. Lea, 1833.

Myidae Lamarck, 1809

Spenia — T. Brown, 1827-C1: pl. 14. — Current status: subsequent incorrect spelling of *Sphenia* W. Turton, 1822.

Corbulidae Lamarck, 1818

rosea, Corbula — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 105, pl. 42, fig. 6, *ex* Leach ms, *non* Röding, 1798. — Type locality: Falmouth, England; NHMUK & Leach collections. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. Brown listed this as if it had appeared in his first edition, but it was not there. — Current status: synonym of *Varicorbula gibba* (Olivi, 1792; *Tellina*) (Huber 2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 390, pl. 327).

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costata, Corbula — “T. Brown, 1849-F”: 223, pl. 91, figs 11–13. — Type locality: Barton Cliff, Hamsey, Sussex, England; London clay [Barton Clay Formation]. — Type age: Eocene (Bartonian). — Type material: not located. Given as if a new species based on *Corbula revoluta* (Brocchi, 1814; *Tellina*) as figured by J. Sowerby (1818: 16, pl. 209, figs 11–13, var. β). However, Sowerby himself had given this subspecific name to his var. β . — Current status: *Corbula costata* J. Sowerby, 1818.

Pholadidae Lamarck, 1809

sulcata, Pholas — T. Brown, 1827-C1: I, pl. 9, figs 17–18. — Type locality: none provided. — Type age: Recent. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Pholadidea loscombiana* W. Turton, 1819 (Huber

2015: chapter 5 on CD; species figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 387, pl. 325).

Hiatellidae J.E. Gray, 1824

Note: Brown used *Panopaea* Lamarck, 1818, an incorrect subsequent spelling of *Panopea* Ménéard de la Groye, 1807.

Coramya — T. Brown, 1844-C2: 103, *ex* Leach ms, in synonymy of *Hiatella minuta* “Lamarck” [*Solen minutus* Linnaeus, 1767]. — Current status: can be listed in the synonymy of *Hiatella* Bosc, 1801.

elongata, Mya — T. Brown, 1818b: 459, pl. 9, fig. 2, *non* Brocchi, 1814. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Hiatella arctica* (Linnaeus, 1767; *Mya*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 358–359, pl. 389).

oblata, Panopaea — T. Brown, 1849-F: 230, pl. 93, fig. 22. Replacement name for *Mya gibbosa* J. De C. Sowerby, 1823 (p. 19, pl. 419, fig. 1), *non Mya gibbosa* (J. Sowerby, 1813; *Mactra*), which Brown had discussed on the same page. — Type locality: Osmington, Dorset, England; Kimmeridge Clay [Formation]; Miss Bennet. — Type age: Jurassic (Kimmeridgian). — Type material: would be that of Sowerby. — Current status: uncertain.

sinuosa, Mya — T. Brown, 1818b: 459, pl. 9, fig. 4. — Type locality: Pointe de Saint-Hospice, Nice, France; T. Allan. — Type age: Quaternary. — Type material: not located. — Current status: synonym of *Hiatella arctica* (Linnaeus, 1767; *Mya*) (herein; figured in Alf *et al.* 2020: 358–359, pl. 389).

Kalenteridae Marwick, 1953

costata, Arca — T. Brown, 1841a: 66, pl. 6, figs 33–34 [not “35” as cited in text]; 1849-F: 191, pl. 77, fig. 32 [Errata: also fig. 31]. — Type locality: Newton, Manchester, England; new red sandstone. — Type age: Permian-Triassic. — Type material: not located. Not preoccupied by Meuschen (1787), an unavailable work. Type species (M) of *Permophorus* Chavan, 1954. — Current status: *Permophorus costatus* (T. Brown, 1841) (Pattison 1970: 155, pl. 21, figs 7, 9; Muromtseva & Guskov 1984: 84, pl. 5, fig. 1, pl. 52, figs 1c, 2c, 3–7, 10–11, 13–14; Wasmer *et al.* 2012: 1065–1066, text-fig. 8N–T).

Class Rostroconchia

Hippocardia — T. Brown, 1843-F: 97, pl. 8, fig. 10. Type species (OD): *Cardium hibernicum* J. Sowerby, 1815. — Type age: Paleozoic. — Current status: valid genus and basis of the family Hippocardiidae Pojeta & Runnegar, 1976.

longipennis, Pleurorynchus — T. Brown, 1849-F: 202, pl. 82, fig. 10. — Type locality: Dovedale, Derbyshire, England; J. Fleming, limestone. — Type age: Carboniferous. — Type material: not located. — Current status: *Conocardium longipennis* (T. Brown, 1849) (Rogalla & Amler 2006: 41).

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- 1818b. Fossil shells. Pp. 455–464, pls 9–10, in: T. ALLAN, Sketch of the geology of the environs of Nice, France. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Edinburgh* 8 (2): 427–464, pls 8–10. Concerning this paper: Barale (2020a). <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/40639537>
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- 1827 [C1]. *Illustrations of the Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland. Drawn from Nature.* W.H. Lizars & D. Lizars, Edinburgh & S. Highley, London, [i–vi] + i–v pp., 52 pls 1–52, 10*, with unpaginated plate explanations. All part covers dated 1827 [dating: Davis 1949]. doi: 10.5962/bhl.title.10336

Part	Pages	Plates & unpaginated plate explanations
1		18, 23–24, 39
2		3, 4, 6, 8
3		10, 13, 21, 24
4		5, 7, 9, 45
5		29, 36, 43–44
6–7		12, 19, 20, 22, 30, 32–33, 47
8–9		2, 15, 25, 26, 28, 37, 40, 42,
10		11, 14, 17, 34
11		1, 35, 38, 52
12	[i–vi] + i–v	10*, 16, 31, 41, 46, 48–51

- 1829a. Descriptions of five new British species of shells. *Edinburgh Journal of Natural and Geographical Science* 1 (1): 11–12, 80 [plate explanation], pl. 1 (October). <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/61398417>
- 1829b. Observations on Mr. Kenyon’s paper on British and freshwater shells. *Edinburgh Journal of Natural and Geographical Science* 1 (1): 65–66 (October). <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/61398443>
1830. A monography on *Pisidium*, a new genus of British freshwater Testacea. *Edinburgh Journal of Natural and Geographical Science* 1 (6): 411–413 (Mar.). <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/61398789>

1833. *The Conchologist's Text-Book, Embracing the Arrangements of Lamarck and Linnaeus, with a Glossary of Technical Terms*. Archibald Fullarton & Co., Glasgow, i-x + 11–180 pp., pls i–xix [first 9 pls from *The Elements of Conchology*, 1816]. This work went through several identical “editions” [reprints] – 2nd [1834?] & 3rd [1835], 4th [1836, 1837], 5th [1839]. [see also the completely new edition as 1845 below]. doi: 10.5962/bhl.title.12438

1835. Description of a new British shell—the clouded scallop.—*Pecten nebulosus*. *The Edinburgh Journal of Natural History, and of the Physical Sciences* 1 (3): [9] (November 21, 1835). <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/33664901>

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1836b. List of land and freshwater shells. Pp. 140–142, in W. RHIND, *Excursions Illustrative of the Geology and Natural History of the Environs of Edinburgh*, 2nd ed. John Anderson, Jr, Edinburgh, i–iv + 1–146 pp., frontis. [map]. https://play.google.com/store/books/details/Excursions_illustrative_of_the_geology_and_natural?id=YbVYAAAAcAAJ

1837. Conchology. Pp. 374–381, pls 17–19, in: *The Popular Encyclopedia; Being a General Dictionary of Arts, Sciences, Literature, Biography, History, and Political Economy*. ... 2 (1). Blackie & Son, Glasgow. [chapter unsigned but the tightly packed plates signed by Brown, and he later noted his authorship; volumes undated but external sources indicate an 1837 publication date]. <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/17807848>

1837–1849 [F]. *Illustrations of the Fossil Conchology of Britain and Ireland, with Descriptions and Localities of all the Species* [title on some original part covers varies]. Smith, Elder & Co., Edinburgh & London, i–viii + [1 p. Errata] + 273 + [1] pp. + [1 p. authors list], 98 uncaptioned pls + uncaptioned pls 3*, 20*, 20**, 21*, 29*, 33*, 37*, 52*, 53*, 54*, 55*, 56*, 61*, 61**, 61***, 66*, 72*, 74* [collation based on Sherborn (1905: 359), McMillan (1992), and an online copy from Harvard University with pages and most but not all plates in the original covers]. doi: 10.5962/bhl.title.12502

Number(s)	Pages	Plates	Date in or before
1	1–4	1, 3, 5–6	1837
2	5–8	2, 4, 7–8	1837
3	9–16	9–12	1837
4	17–20	13–16	1837
5	21–24	18–20, 28	1837
6	25–28	23, 25–27	1837
7	29–32	17, 22, 24, 30	1837
8	33–36	21, 29, 35, 37	1837
9	37–40	31–32, 34, 38	1838
10	41–44	33, 36, 39–40	1838
11	45–48	41–44	1838
12	49–52	45–48	1838
13–14	53–60	49–50, 52, “56” [later 55], 57, 60–62	1839
15	61–64	29*, 58–59, 70	Oct. 17, 1841

Number(s)	Pages	Plates	Date in or before
16	65–68	20*, 51, 63, 69	Oct. 17, 1841
17–18	69–80	21*, 66–68, 71, 74	Oct. 17, 1841
19–20	81–88	64–65, 66*, 66**, 72, 72*, 73, 76	Likely 1842, but without evidence, has to be regarded as 1843
21	89–108	75	November 21, 1843
22–23	109–116	77–82, 84, 88	July 9, 1844
24–25	117–124	52*, 85, 87, 89–90, 93–94, 96	1845
26–28	125–136	53, 53*, 54, 54*, 55*, 56, 56*, 74*, 86, 91–92, 95	1845
29–36	137–273, i–viii + 1 p. [Errata] + 1 p. [Authors]	3*, 20**, 33*, 37*, 61**, 61***, 83, 97–98	1849

Collation does not account for plates 51–52, 60–61, 61*, 62–63 or 69. A completely new version was issued in 1889 [see below].

1838–1844 [C2]. *Illustrations of the Recent Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland, with the Description and Localities of all the Species, Marine, Land and Fresh-water*, 2nd ed., *Greatly Enlarged*. Smith, Elder & Co., London, i–xiii + 1–144 pp. + [145 – Errata], 1–59 uncaptioned pls + pls 18*, 28*, 30* [pl. 9 misprinted as “III” and hand-corrected; pl. 24 bound as frontis.] Limited collations from Reynell (1921) and McMillan (1992), supplemented by a copy at Harvard University in its original covers. Because the dates of the parts after 8 are unknown, with the original covers undated, even though we know the contents of the parts, most of the work has to be dated as 1844. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.124615>

Part(s)	Pages	Plates	Date in or before
1	1–8	1–4	Mar. 14, 1838
2	9–12	5–8	Mar. 14, 1838
3	13–16	9–12	Mar. 14, 1838
4	17–20	14, 16, 22, 26	Mar. 14, 1838
5	21–24	13, 17, 24, 36	1839
6–8	25–36	15, 19–21, 25, 27, 34, 40, 44, 46, 52, 54	Oct. 17, 1841
9–11	37–48	28, 35, 37–38, 43, 49–51, 53, 55–56	1844
12–13	49–72	33, 42, 47–48	1844
14–15	73–88	23, 28*, 30*, 31–32, 45	1844
16–17	89–120	18, 18*, 29–30	1844
18–19	121–144, t.p., i–xiii, Errata	39, 57–59	1844

Leaves the issuance of only pl. 41 [some mactrids] uncertain.

1839. Description [of new species on] Plate I. Pp. 98–106, pl. 1, in: J. SMITH, On the last changes in the relative levels of the land and sea in the British Islands. *Memoirs of the Wernerian Society* 8: 49–113, pls 1–2. <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/page/35485515>

1841a. Description, by Captain Brown, of the fossil shells found at Newton. Pp. 63–66, 234 [pl. expl.], pl. 6, in E.W. BINNEY, Sketch of the geology of Manchester and its vicinity. *Transactions of*

the Manchester Geological Society 1: 35–66, pl. 6. <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044102929452&seq=75>

1841b. Description of some new species of fossil shells, found chiefly in the Vale of Todmorden, Yorkshire. *Transactions of the Manchester Geological Society* 1: 212–229, 234–235 [pl. expl.], pl. 7. <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044102929452&seq=224>

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1845. *Illustrations of the Land and Freshwater Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland, with Figures, Descriptions, and Localities of all the Species*. Smith, Elder & Co., London, i–xi + 1–142 pp., pls 1–27. This work was also advertised on his book flyleaves as both *Illustrations of the Land and Fresh-water Conchology of the British Islands* and as *Illustrations of the Land and Fresh-water Shells of Ireland*, with specific paginations and prices noted, but neither version was ever produced. doi: 10.5962/bhl.title.10333

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c. 1851–1855? [Journal title pages undated]. Elementary treatise on fossil conchology. *The Imperial Journal of Art, Science, Mechanics and Engineering* 2: 545–549, 3 pls [incorrectly labelled as “2”, “2” & “?”, but actually 2, 3 & 1]; 3: 86–88, pl. 3 [“missing” in online copy, actually located in Volume 2]; 158–163, pl. 4; 279–283, pl. 6; 348–352, pl. 7; 484–487, pl. 8; 503–507; 575–579; 650–654; 666–673; 689–694 [article segments unsigned]. Vol. 2: <https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=gri.ark:/13960/t9189r236&seq=647>; Vol. 3: <https://archive.org/details/imperialjournalo03unse/page/86/>

1889. *An Atlas of the Fossil Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland with Descriptions of all the Species*. Swan Sonnenschein & Co., London, iii + 115 pp., 98 pls A completely redone version, with uncoloured copies of the original plates accompanied by abbreviated plate explanations. It is not apparent who produced it. doi: 10.5962/bhl.title.150415

Two further items were said to have been issued, neither with a known date or pagination, and neither appears online or in any library catalogues we've examined. It is possible they were advertised but never produced: (1) *A Catalogue of the Recent Conchology of Great Britain and Ireland* and (2) *A Catalogue of the Land and Fresh-water Shells of Great Britain and Ireland for "purposes of labelling collections"* (Sherborn 1905: 360).

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The preceding originated with Oliver Goldsmith's (b. 1730? – d. 1774) *An History of the Earth, and Animated Nature; Illustrated with Copperplates* (1774). J. Nourse, London, 8 vols. It went through several editions before T. Brown issued his first version. Later he issued a second version:

1832. *A History of the Earth and Animated Nature. By Oliver Goldsmith. With Copious Notes; and an Appendix Containing Explanations of Technical Terms, and an Outline of the Cuvierian and Other Systems* [footnotes by Brown throughout]. [Reprinted: 1838, 1840]. A. Fullarton, Edinburgh, Glasgow & London. Vol. 1 (1): pp. i–xii, 1–288, frontis. portrait of Oliver Goldsmith, 13 variously numbered pls, incl. 1 fold-out of Mountains; vol. 1 (2): 289–552, 13 variously numbered pls; vol. 2 (1): 1–276, with variously numbered pls; vol. 2 (1, corrected in ink to “2”): 277–552, 13 variously numbered pls; 3 (1): 1–300, 12 variously numbered pls; 3 (2): 301–567, 14 variously numbered pls; 4 (1): 1–344, 41 variously numbered pls; 4 (2): 1–4 + 345–703, 15 variously numbered pls. The 1832 edition is not online; 1840 edition [with differently included plates]: doi: 10.5962/bhl.title.24591

1839. *Biographical Sketches and Authentic Anecdotes of Dogs, Exhibiting Remarkable Instances of the Instinct, Sagacity, and Social Disposition of this Faithful Animal: Illustrated by Representations of the Most Striking Varieties, and by Correct Portraits of Celebrated or Remarkable Dogs from Drawings Chiefly Original. Also[,] a Historical Introduction; and a Copious Appendix on the Breeding, Feeding, Training, Diseases, and Medical Treatment of Dogs; Together with a Treatise on the Game Laws of Great Britain*. Oliver & Boyd, Edinburgh; Simkin & Marshall, London, 570 pp. <https://archive.org/details/biographicalske00browgoog>

1830. *Biographical Sketches and Authentic Anecdotes of Horses, and the Allied Species. Illustrated by Portraits, on Steel, of Celebrated and Remarkable Horses*. Daniel Lizars, Edinburgh; Whittaker, Treacher & Arnot, London; W. Curry, Jun., Dublin, 1–580 pp., 9 pls. <https://archive.org/details/biographicalsket1830brow>

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- Vol. 2: 1–15–[16] pp., pls 1–105 (1832). An original work based on descriptions from Cuvier, Temminck, Latreille, Lamarck, and others, with drawings gathered by the publishers. There seems to have been only a single edition. Vol. 1: https://archive.org/details/b21513454_0001/, Vol. 2: https://archive.org/details/b21513454_0001
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	12	455–486	56–60	Apr. 1886
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	49	241–280	AAA, CCC, 132–133	Dec. 1, 1852
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